

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

DOCTOR OF COMMUNICATION PROGRAM

YOURGIN OCLARES MONTEJO

**THE REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME IN LICENSURE EXAMINATION
THROUGH THE COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF PERSONNEL OF A
REGULATORY BODY: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY**

Dissertation Adviser:

Dr. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

23 October 2023

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No

Student's signature:

Dissertation adviser signature:

University Permission Page

THE REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME IN LICENSURE EXAMINATION THROUGH THE COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF PERSONNEL OF A REGULATORY BODY: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

YOURGIN O. MONTEJO

October 23, 2023

Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **YOURGIN OCLARES MONTEJO** with the title: **“THE REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME IN LICENSURE EXAMINATION THROUGH THE COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF PERSONNEL OF A REGULATORY BODY: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Communication.

JEANA A. SALUDADEZ, PhD
Chair, Dissertation Committee

(Date)

BENJAMINA PAULA G. FLOR, PhD
Member, Dissertation Committee

(Date)

MELINDA F. LUMANTA, PhD
Member, Dissertation Committee

(Date)

DIEGO S. MARANAN, PhD

Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

23 October 2023

Biographical Sketch

Yourgin O. Montejo graduated with the degree Bachelor of Science in Management from the University of the Philippines Tacloban College (UPTC) on April 29, 2010. He pursued further studies and earned the degree Master of Management (Public Management) also from UPTC on December 29, 2016.

He obtained a Civil Service 2nd Level (Professional) eligibility by passing the career service examination held in Tacloban City on April 25, 2010, and was recognized as one of the top passers of the said examination in Region VIII. He first served as a Job Order employee in government on May 16, 2011 and was issued an original appointment as Professional Regulations Assistant on August 20, 2012. He was promoted to the position Administrative Officer I (Cashier I) on June 1, 2016 and, in view of his Agency's reorganization, was promoted as Supervising Administrative Officer on June 29, 2018. He is currently the Planning Officer of the Finance & Administrative Division in his Regional Office. His occasional involvement as Building Supervisor in licensure examinations gave him the idea of pursuing a communication research on licensure examination administration.

He previously served as Lecturer I in UP Tacloban College in 2019 and handled graduate courses for Master of Management (MM) students in the Division of Management, such as PM 211 (Public Organization and Governance) and Mgt 221 (Human Resource Management). And in 2020, after the expiration of his appointment as a part-time Lecturer, he started to pursue his Doctor of Communication (DComm) degree in the UP Open University.

Acknowledgement

This would not have been possible at all if not for the blessings, efforts, contributions, and prayers of those who helped me make it:

To God, the Almighty Father, thank You for the chance to live at least once and to create a legacy worth leaving behind. All glory and honor is Yours forever;

To my Dissertation Adviser, Dr. Jean A. Saludadez, the best Adviser a DComm student could ever have, thank you for the guidance, the firmness, and the patience for an “extremist” like me. I never expected to finish this paper earlier than I thought. I learned a lot from your advices and guiding words. A million Thank You’s would not suffice, but I will always include you in my prayers forever;

To my Dissertation Committee Members, Dr. Benjamina Paula G. Flor and Dr. Melinda F. Lumanta, thank you for enriching my presentation with your ideas and perspectives. You helped me appreciate different approaches on how my Study could be developed;

To my classmates in the DComm program, Shainne, Monalice, Wilzen, Ayriss, Geff, Bryan, Seven, Thatha, Jomar, Atty. Rochelle, Sudi, Benny, Carol, Chelle, Danyx, Denden, Epi, Evelyn, Gab, Grichelle, James, JC, Jonnell, Joyce, Jude, Jun, Kahrein, Kei, Laya, Leah, Maki, Marj, Monica, Natalie, Nel, Nicka, Norman, Robert, Rom, Rommel, Shirley, Val, and others who I missed, thank you for being with me in this journey. I argue that our batch of DComm students is the “Best Batch Ever”;

To my “Toi” group, Quiri, Wayne, Mark, Jan Andre, Milky, Jepernick, thanks for the beer bottles we’ve all shared through the years and cheers for more;

To my circle of friends, Yanus, Clareyse, Karen, Rosario, Tintin, Rebecca, Brian, thanks for believing in me since our high school days and being my true friends to this day;

To my family in the Office, Mam Mahal, Sir Randie, Mano Allan, Mam Malyn, Mam Beth, Ate Lecel, Ate Jeanne, Ate May, Mam Helda, Ate Yves, AJei, DJ, Myra, Cheding, Raymund, Ate Sharon, Jerico, Ate Edelyn, Sir Bimbo, and Sir Armond, thank you for the support. Special shout-out to BB (Shenna) who assisted me in the data gathering process, thank you for the friendship and the help;

To my in-laws, Mama Ai-ai, Papa Ambet, Kuya Abet, Mabeth. Thank you for accepting me into your family, for treating me as if I was your own flesh and blood, and for all the support you have given me and Ayen from the very beginning;

To Kuya Youssef and Papa (Mike), thank you for everything, the sacrifices, and for teaching me things I needed to survive;

To Mama (Aida) who is in heaven now, thank you for everything, the sacrifices, and for the love. I hope I made you proud up there. I wish I could see you smile again;

To my children, Youvenn Crono and Youvert Cyann, thank you for “choosing to be born” to your Mommy and to me as your Daddy. I love you both! Sorry for the nights that I could not lay down beside you to sleep. May you both have a good future, and may you both be prepared for the realities that this world has to offer;

And to my wife, Marlene... Ayen... Mommy... Miming... My true love, my whole heart... The one out there who got me, the one reserved for me... Thank you for choosing me to be your better half, for choosing to love me despite what I am not, and for choosing to live with me everyday. Thank you for being an amazing mother to our children and for being a faithful wife to me. I love you! I always did. And I always will.

In omnibus amare et servire Domino...

**For my wife (Ayen)
and my kids (Yuno & Yuan):
may they find pride and joy in what Daddy loved doing.**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vii
Table of Contents	viii
List of Tables	x
List of Figures	xi
ABSTRACT	xiii
CHAPTER I: RATIONALE	1
Background of the Study	1
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Regulating Occupational Licensing & Managing Reputation	8
Conducting Examinations and Proctoring	14
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH FRAMEWORK & RESEARCH QUESTIONS	25
Research Framework	25
Research Questions	28
CHAPTER IV: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	29
Research Design	29
Research Participants	33
Site Access	37
Data Collection	38
Data Analysis and Interpretation	38
Ensuring Plausibility in the Findings	54
CHAPTER V: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	55
Communicative Practices of Examination Personnel	55
Roaming Around	55
Resolving Issues	61
Retaining Professional Composure	62
Reviewing Exam Statistics	63
Re-Checking Documents	66

Retrieval Procedure is Secured	68
Reprimanding Personnel	75
Reporting of Incidents & Violations	76
Reporting of Issues	106
Reminding of Procedures to Prevent Cheating	106
Removing Prohibited Materials that Compromise Exam Integrity	110
Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency	111
Respective Badges are Put in Place	113
Referring Issues to Higher Authority	114
Recording of Accountable Persons is Ensured	115
Synthesis of the Communicative Practices	120
Reproducing Rule Regime in Licensure Examinations	124
Rule Alignment	124
Rule Implementation	125
Rule Compliance	126
Rule Preservation	128
Rule Authority	129
Synthesis of Rule Regime Reproduction	130
 CHAPTER VI: RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	 133
Summary	133
Conclusion	135
Implications	136
Recommendations	137
Theoretical	138
Methodological	138
Practical	139
 BIBLIOGRAPHY	 140
 APPENDICES	
Appendix A. Letter-Request to the Regional Director of the Study Site	146
Appendix B. Letter to the Participants	147
Appendix C. Guide Questionnaire for the Key Informant Interview (KII)	148

List of Tables

Table 1. Demographics Profile of the Participants	35
Table 2. Matrix of Qualitative Data Analysis	40
Table 3. Communicative Practices of Examination Personnel	121

List of Figures

Figure 1. Hierarchy of Examination Personnel in Licensure Examinations	37
Figure 2. Answer Sheets Mother Envelope Labelling sample	71
Figure 3. ID Sheets Mother Envelope Labelling sample	72
Figure 4. Label on the Overall Packaging of the Answer Sheets	73
Figure 5. Label on the Overall Packaging of the ID Sheets	74
Figure 6. Room Watcher's Report sample	77
Figure 7. Seat Plan sample	78
Figure 8. List of Examinees sample	79
Figure 9. Examinees Record of Attendance sample	79
Figure 10. Test Questionnaire Accountability Form sample	80
Figure 11a. Floor Supervisor's Report sample (Page 1)	82
Figure 11b. Floor Supervisor's Report sample (Page 2)	83
Figure 12. Floor Supervisor's Attendance Report Form sample	84
Figure 13a. Floor Supervisor's Test Questions Distribution & Accountability Form sample (Page 1)	85
Figure 13b. Floor Supervisor's Test Questions Distribution & Accountability Form sample (Page 2)	86
Figure 14a. List of Examinees with Discrepancies Form sample (Page 1)	87
Figure 14b. List of Examinees with Discrepancies Form sample (Page 2)	88
Figure 15. Sequence of Reports of the Building Supervisor	90
Figure 16a. Building Supervisor's Report sample (Page 1)	92
Figure 16b. Building Supervisor's Report sample (Page 2)	92
Figure 17. Delivery Receipts for Answer Sheets, Used/Excess/Extra Test Question Sets sample	93

Figure 18. Delivery Receipts for PERRCs / Mailing Envelopes / Identification Sheets sample	95
Figure 19. Delivery Receipts for Sealed Extra & Spoiled Examinee Identification / Answer Sheets Sets sample	96
Figure 20. List of Absentees Form sample	97
Figure 21. Report on Incomplete / Questionable Test Questions sample	98
Figure 22. Certification of Untampered/Sealed Boxes sample	99
Figure 23. Record/Certification of Attendance of Security Officers sample	101
Figure 24. Security Officer's Report of Activities in the Testing Center Sample	102
Figure 25a. Report on Violation by Examinees sample (Page 1)	104
Figure 25b. Report on Violation by Examinees sample (Page 2)	105
Figure 26a. Attendance Record sheet sample for Over-all Exam Personnel	117
Figure 26b. Attendance Record sheet sample for Room Watchers	118
Figure 27a. General Payroll sheet sample for Over-all Exam Personnel	119
Figure 27b. General Payroll sheet sample for Room Watchers	119

Abstract

This study explored the communicative practices of personnel assigned in licensure examinations and how their communicative practices reproduce rule regime in licensure examination administration. The research framework used in this Study is the Socio-Cultural Tradition of Communication Theory, which theorizes communication as the (re)production of social order (Craig, 1999). Using this framework, this Study assumed that rule regime is reproduced by the communicative practices established from the participants. The use of Ethnomethodology as a qualitative research method in this Study explored the participants' acts of communication in licensure examinations towards surfacing themes that described their communicative practices. Eight (8) participants were identified in this Study, each with rich experiences in their specific roles in the licensure examination administration. The participants' narratives were subjected to Grounded Theory Method (GTM) and Thematic Analysis for data interpretation.

Fifteen (15) communicative practices of assigned personnel in licensure examinations emerged in the analysis: (1) roaming around; (2) resolving issues; (3) retaining professional composure; (4) reviewing exam statistics; (5) re-checking documents; (6) securing retrieval procedures; (7) reprimanding; (8) reporting incidents and violations; (9) reporting issues; (10) reminding procedures to prevent cheating; (11) removing prohibited materials or items in the examination room; (12) rendering support to ensure consistency; (13) the wearing of respective badges; (14) referring issues to higher authority; and (15) ensuring the record of accountable persons.

These communicative practices reproduced five dimensions of the rule regime in the licensure examination: (1) rule alignment; (2) rule implementation; (3) rule compliance; (4) rule preservation; and (5) rule authority.

Roaming around, resolving issues, and retaining professional composure align knowledge and actions with the rules. Reviewing exam statistics, re-checking documents, and securing retrieval procedures of examination paraphernalia are performed to ensure that rules are implemented. Reprimanding, reporting of violations, and reporting of issues are done when rules are not complied. Reminding procedures to prevent cheating, removing prohibited materials or items in the examination room, and rendering support to ensure consistency are meant to preserve the integrity of the examination process. Finally, by putting in place respective badges, referring issues to higher authority, and recording of accountable persons, the established authority is recognized.

Keywords: licensure examination administration, room watcher, exam supervisor, communicative practice, reporting violations, rule regime, rule alignment, rule authority

Chapter I

RATIONALE

Background of the Study

The establishment of functioning public institutions in a society is a means to preserve justice and to protect the sovereignty, freedom and independence of the state and its people (Ceva, 2022). It helps legitimize the action of the state to structure power relations among citizens and to enact their will and freedom. As such, public institutions are viewed as *rule-based* structures of procedures, and as *role-based* structures of human relations. The rule-based view helps make sense of the basic features of an institution, while the role-based view takes an appreciation of how people occupy governing roles by which they embody institutional rules. These perspectives are deemed essential in understanding how rules reproduce an organization and shape the dynamics of relationships among people.

Public institutions are functionalized by the enforcement of rules (Ceva, 2022). These rules are utilized by organizational members to organize social activities and to shape social order (Burns & Carson, 2000). In effect, people conform to rule systems in various capacities, based on their role or identity in the organization, on how they know and appreciate such rules, on what meanings they attribute to them, and on the consequences of not complying or violating the rules, among other factors.

Social interaction among people is mostly organized and regulated through rules or systems of rules that are reproduced socially by people (Burns & Carson, 2000). These rules are implemented and applied in institutions such as regulatory

agencies, guiding the actions of personnel towards achieving specific mandates, goals, and objectives.

Among such institutions are government regulatory bodies that have unique, specific mandates. These regulatory bodies are driven by human social activity, organized by rules and systems of rules continuously produced and reproduced by people associated in it (Burns & Carson, 2000).

There are agencies of government that are mandated to uphold public interest and welfare, such as those mandated to conduct and administer licensure examinations to individuals aspiring to be accredited in their respective professions. For a licensure examination to take place, it involves the utilization of personnel who act as examination supervisors, room examiners, and other essential staff, subject to policies or guidelines that govern the proper conduct of examination administration.

Schorr (1985) defines Practice as “any professional service rendered to a person or group of persons as a skill or in providing access to a skill or material benefit.” Governing such professional practice entails the formulation and implementation of policies i.e. externally imposed laws, rules, understandings, and procedures that determine how practice is performed (Schorr, 1985). On the other hand, a License is defined as “a formal permission to do something – an authorization by law to do some specified thing e.g. *license* to marry, practice medicine, hunt, etc. (Guralnik, 1976).” Thus, tantamount to the grant of authority to engage in professional practice is the issuance of a license to any individual legally determined by law to have possessed the minimum qualifications to practice in a competent manner, such as the possession of an appropriate educational degree, passing a licensure examination, and other requirements imposed by applicable laws.

The conduct of licensure examinations towards the grant of license to qualified professionals involves organizing people in relationships bound by an authoritative complex of rules, known as *rule regime* (Burns & Carson, 2000). As such, an institution is conceptualized as a structure that organizes people in relationships bound by *rule regime*. Rule regime in any institution paves way to a meaningful and systematic basis for institutional members to frame, interpret, and analyze their actions, and to produce appropriate behavior, discourses and communicative practices (Burns & Carson, 2003).

Regulatory bodies of professional licensure implement plans, policies, programs, and guidelines relative to the conduct of licensure examinations. They are supported by an organizational structure composed of divisions, sections, and units operating with focus on the examination.

Each personnel assigned in the conduct of licensure examinations shares their respective skills and expertise to ensure the success and the preservation of the credibility, integrity, and inviolability of licensure examinations. Moreover, the organizational structure of the examination personnel is designed such that it ensures the smooth and orderly conduct of licensure examinations. However, as each personnel respectively embraces the examination duties and responsibilities assigned upon them, there is no outright assurance that the licensure examination conducted will be smooth and orderly, nor does the mere assignment of examination personnel automatically safeguard the credibility, integrity, and inviolability of the licensure examination.

On June 13, 2022, I had the experience of being assigned as Building Supervisor at one of the testing centers for a Licensure Examination, which took place on June 12 to 14, 2022. During the second subject on that day, there was an

incident involving an examinee who had been caught using a mobile phone by the assigned Security Officer. The said officer approached me to report that he confiscated a mobile phone from a female examinee whom he caught using the said device as he was inspecting the classrooms. He showed me the confiscated phone, with an open Google Chrome browser with the keywords typed by the examinee appearing on the search box. To validate the Security Officer's report, I investigated how it happened, and I found out that the examinee hid the mobile phone under her left thigh and discreetly used it while the examination was ongoing. When we asked the assigned Room Watcher how the examinee obtained her mobile phone, he mentioned that though he collected the mobile phones of all examinees in the room prior the start of the first subject and placed the phones on top of his table, he took a nap during lunch break but overlooked that the examinee's phone was no longer in his custody. The assigned Floor Supervisor was initially unaware of this incident, but I instructed her to monitor the situation in the room as well as in other rooms assigned under her supervision.

As soon as I informed the Examination Coordinator of this incident, he immediately proceeded to the testing site to investigate. Upon establishing the facts about this incident, he ruled that the examinee should surrender her mobile phone and that she could no longer continue taking the examination any further due to her violation of examination rules and regulations. As soon as I reported back to the Office, I submitted an Incident Report to the Regional Director and turned over the mobile phone to his custody as evidence of the examinee's violation.

The said incident is treated as a clear breach of examination rules and regulations. Despite repeated and numerous briefing orientations for assigned examination volunteers (i.e. room watchers and examination supervisors), there

remains a probability of examination rules being violated over and over again. Rules indeed do not completely regulate people's actions; the implementation of rules stems from generating innovation based on collective experience, adjustment, and adaptation (Burns & Carson, 2000). This leads to an instance of social change in which actions of individuals and groups have a substantial deviation from prescriptions in an institutionalized rule system.

Professional Licensure, or the act of licensing, is "a process by which an agency of government grants permission to an individual to engage in a given occupation upon finding that the applicant has attained the minimal degree of competency required to ensure that public health, safety, and welfare will be reasonably well-protected (Shimberg & Roederer, 1994)." It is designed to protect citizens from mental, physical, or economic harm that may be caused by practitioners who do not have sufficient competency to practice a given profession (Schmitt, 1995).

Considering that conducting and administering licensure examinations involve the coordination of individuals through acts of communication, this Study attempted to explore how licensure examinations are administered by personnel employed, what acts of communication they perform to manifest rule regime in this practical context.

To achieve the overall purpose of conducting licensure examinations, it is assumed that all assigned examination personnel must work and function collectively through the performance of various tasks and communicative actions based on rules governing licensure examinations, to systematically undertake procedures towards the smooth and orderly conduct of the licensure examination. Such assumption is influenced by Pearce and Cronen's Coordinated Management of Meaning (CMM)

Theory, which presupposes that people communicate on the basis of rules (West & Turner, 2010). CMM generally refers to how individuals establish rules for the creation and interpretation of meaning, and how these rules are entangled in conversations in which meaning is constantly being coordinated to produce action. Conceiving that rule regime exists in the institutional function of administering licensure examinations, the coordination of meaningful communicative actions by assigned individuals is grounded in institutionalized rules.

The literature on the act of administering examinations is limited, as most studies specifically focus on the context of test administration in the school setting i.e. between teachers and students (e.g. Rukundo & Magambo, 2010; Sadiq & Saeed, 2017; and Al Ghafri, Audeh, & Al-Gadallah, 2019). Limiting focus on such context creates a gap on communication research concerning test administration in the context of examinees in an actual licensure examination setting. In addition, there is a scarcity of literature that analyzes how people adhere to rules that organize social activities and shape social order (Burns & Carson, 2000) in a public institutional setting. This study intends to bridge such gap towards theorizing on how rule regime provides opportunities as well as constraints in social interaction. Rule systems can generate opportunities for interaction that may seem impossible, such as in coordinating with other people, in gaining access to resources, mobilizing resources, and solving complex problems through organized collective actions. In like manner, rule systems may also put constraints on action possibilities (Burns & Carson, 2000). Identifying socio-cultural patterns could help understand why certain actions within a rule system cannot be pursued, realized, or achieved. Theorizing on rule regime helps discover socio-cultural patterns that guide and regulate social interaction.

Social situations challenge human efforts to regulate and maintain order (Lotman, 1975). Through rule regime and continuously evolving rule systems, social actors attempt to reproduce order amidst an uncertain environment, such as in administering a licensure examination. Exploring this context could help develop theories that recognize socio-cultural patterns that are understandable and meaningful in implementing rule systems within a regulatory body.

In the context of exploring communication, focus will be placed on “*un-muting the voices*” of assigned personnel in licensure examination, through discovering how examination procedures contribute to public policy implementation on professional licensure and professional practice, highlighting on how rule regime is reproduced in their communicative practices.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Regulating Occupational Licensing & Managing Reputation

Occupation regulation is essential in the protection of public interest and welfare against incompetent, unscrupulous, and irresponsible persons practicing professional services (Kleiner & Krueger, 2011). In the United States (US), it commonly involves administering an examination by an agency of the government, or an accredited private, non-profit agency, prior to the grant of a certification permit to examination passers who demonstrated sufficient skills level and knowledge for certification. Occupations such as travel agents and automotive mechanics require certification, but not really a license. However, there are occupations in which it is illegal to practice without being granted a professional license. Examples of professions which require a license include accountants, engineers, lawyers, physicians, architects, etc. Each federal state in the US implements their respective licensure laws for various occupation classifications. There are as many as 800 occupations that require professional licensing in a state (Council on Licensure, Enforcement, and Regulation [CLEAR], 2004).

One particular study that looks at professional regulation is that of Adams (2016). It explores the views of policymakers and legislators on professional self-regulation and public interest in Canada. Adams quoted Streeck and Schmitter (1985) that professional associations constitute as one of the four institutional bases of social order, the others mainly refer to the community, the market, and the state. The laws and rules that regulate professions bind them to be responsive to the interests of the general public, which enable them to contribute to social order while pursuing their private interests (Adams, 2016). Regulatory legislations, therefore,

place a sense of control among individuals who wish to engage in professional practice. In Adams' study, findings showed that state actors' and policymakers' perception of public interest have become more attached to the pursuit of professional accountability and efficient service delivery, while assuring human rights and the protection of business interests in society. Findings of the study suggest that change in institutional rules is rooted in change on how public interest is conceptualized. With this argument, exploring public interest as embedded in rules would help develop an understanding of the dynamic nature of professional regulation.

Bach et al. (2022) examined how regulatory agencies manage their reputation through communicative acts. The study conceives public organizations (i.e. regulatory agencies) to be politically-conscious actors that exhibit distinct strategies such as patterned responses to manage their reputation, particularly when faced with reputational threats (Waeraas & Maor, 2015). This organizational behavior suggests that regulatory agencies are particularly sensitive to negative public judgments that may likely put "blame" or negative bias toward them by relevant audiences such as clients, internal and external stakeholders, and the general public itself. Such view likewise applies to the performance of different tasks in specific functional areas of an organization towards the fulfilment of its mandate and consequently, the maintenance of its own reputation; these are understood to be of material importance to public interest. Recognizing the need to further establish the generalizability of the *bureaucratic reputation theory*, the researchers conducted a single case-study on the German financial regulator named BaFin, on how it employs communicative responses to public judgments based on four reputational dimensions (Carpenter, 2010), namely *performative reputation* (i.e. the effective

attainment of a regulatory agency's mandate or mission), *procedural reputation* (i.e. compliance to established rules and ensuring due process), *moral reputation* (i.e. commitment to ethical aspects such as honesty and responsiveness to clients' problems, issues, and concerns), and *technical reputation* (i.e. organizational capacity and expertise). The study presented that BaFin was 6.1 times more likely to respond to threats or negative opinions compared to positive ones, 2.4 times more likely to respond to a judgment targeting its procedural reputation, but did not show significant propensity to react to threats against its technical and moral reputation. Findings suggested that BaFin, as a regulatory agency, tends to display a higher propensity of communicative responses for public judgments targeting the performative and procedural dimensions of its organizational reputation. Bach et al. suggested for future research undertakings that inwardly look at the act of organizational decision-making, in which agency heads or leaders have tight control of communicative practices in light of reputational implications. This proposed study could help discover how organizational leaders (e.g. examination coordinators) engage in social interaction towards making leadership decisions that manage its reputation and dispense its official function. In the case of the licensing regulatory body, this analysis may then be applied on the context of administering licensure examinations by involved examination personnel to secure the integrity and reliability of licensure examinations in regulating professional licensure in the Philippines. Methodological approaches suggested in the said study include participant observation and ethnography (Bach et al, 2022).

Understanding reputational management in public agencies is assumed to be crucial in establishing how rule regime is manifested within their bureaucratic frameworks. As previously alluded to, Carpenter (2010) classifies performative and

procedural reputations as two of the four reputation dimensions by which public organizations, through their leaders, manage the creation of an image in which it satisfactorily delivers its outputs and outcomes to its stakeholders, as it concurrently adheres to appropriate procedural and legal requisites in making decisions relative to formal affiliations established upwards (i.e. to superiors) and downwards (i.e. to subordinates). This applies to the implementation of laws and rules that regulate its activities in an appropriate manner. Christensen (2019) identifies four (4) relevant conditions in managing an organizational reputation: *time, sector, task, and audience*. I wish to highlight two of those conditions, namely task and audience. Task is embedded in the *instrumental perspective* of an organization as it involves the systematic utilization of human agents (e.g. actors) and non-human agents (e.g. material and financial resources) towards the achievement of certain goals. This alludes to the performative aspect of managing organizational reputation, such that it is core to the pursuit of specific outputs and outcomes in the organization. As public resources are committed to such pursuit, managing procedural reputation becomes one of its success indicators. This is where the *audience*, its organizational stakeholders, exert more influence in ensuring accountability from those who represent the organization in the implementation of its procedures and systems of rules. Christensen's study (2019) made an analysis of reputation management among four regulatory agencies, two of which are in the education sector while the other two are in the financial/competition sector. The findings indicated that the performative dimension is the most prominent feature of regulatory agencies in reputation management; that regulatory agencies seek to protect their esteem of being a professional agency which duly implements policies regardless of how procedures are carried out. The study then calls for disentangling and further

theorizing institutional dynamics of regulatory activities, in pursuit of good reputation and safeguarding public interest.

One of the examples that put the capacity of a licensing and regulatory body to a test was an incident during the May 2019 Civil Engineering Licensure Examination. Reyes (2021, March 29), in his blog website, Engineer Dee's Blog, revealed that during an inspection of devices before the start of the said licensure examination, a total of eleven (11) examinees attempted to use a modified scientific calculator, Casio 991-ES Plus, as a communication device that could be used for cheating purposes. A unit of the said modified scientific calculator allegedly costs One Hundred Thousand Pesos (₱100,000.00). Upon disassembly of the said modified calculators, the police found a sim card with battery and wires, capable of receiving information or communication by using the device. In response, the customized calculators were confiscated and the examinees were perpetually disqualified to take future licensure examinations. Casio 991-ES Plus was since then removed from the list of allowed scientific calculators for the Civil Engineering Licensure Examination. The prevention of this irregularity is an example of preserving the integrity of its licensure examinations. It remains a mystery if the room watchers in the room where such examination was held would have detected the examinees' attempt to cheat through the use of such modified calculators. The mere possession of the said calculator would have shown no obvious or noticeable acts of communicative gesture by the examinees themselves, something that could have been difficult to detect by any room watcher or examination supervisor at first glance. It is alarming though that said examinees would resort to a lame cheating tactic, in order to earn a professional license. Theorizing communicative practices in licensure

examinations could then help contextualize how the integrity of the overall examination is maintained and preserved by its assigned examination personnel.

It is a routine for governments to provide justifications of ruling legitimacy, of the entitlement to rule. For any regime to be considered legitimate, it is important to explain how it rules and whether such regime is a stable one (Tannenberget al., 2020). This legitimacy is built on a dualistic concept of structure as rules and as resources (Stryker, 1994). Rules, as defined by Sewell (1992), refer to generalized procedures applied to enact or reproduce social life; these rules may come either through formal or informal generalizable procedures which may or may not elicit cognitive awareness from actors. On the other hand, resources are human attributes and non-human agents that can be utilized to enhance or maintain power. Stryker's argument is based on Sewell's definitions that when people utilize rules to sustain power, these rules provide, activate, and even become resources. These rules and resources become the foundation of a structure that shapes action and contributes to social order. The concept of legitimacy would then be based on collective recognition of and orientation to those rules based on attitudinal approval and behavioral consent (Stryker, 1994). In this premise, this Study intends to contextualize the collective behavior exhibited by examination personnel to reproduce a legitimate regime of rules in the conduct of licensure examinations. These rules are an application of examination procedures that utilize people and resources to shape actions that preserve the integrity and reliability of licensure examinations. The collective perceptions of actors who follow these rules and enforce others to follow them shape what is known as an operative "institutional paradigm", a shared normative-cognitive frame (Burns & Carson, 2000) in sense-making of the reality, in organizing and interpreting their perceptions, in making situational judgments, and in

solving institutional problems, in which rule regime in licensure examination administration is applied and implemented.

Conducting Examinations & Proctoring

Licensure examinations form part of the professional licensure policies of the government through agencies that regulate professional practice to protect public interest. Activities such as licensure examinations are crucial in achieving the objective of determining the most competent individuals who will be granted a license or authority to practice their profession lawfully. With this notion, it is important to look at empirical studies that assess the objectivity and reliability of administering examinations relative to such nature.

Sadiq and Saeed (2017) conducted a qualitative study that explored the problems of students during board examinations in the intermediate and secondary levels of education in Pakistan. Various factors were identified as crucial in satisfactorily administering the examinations, such as the physical environment, the management and conduct of exams, and how technical errors in the examination are addressed. In the study, six themes emerged which describe the problems that students faced in relation to the management and conduct of exams, such as strict invigilation of examinees, irrelevant interruption during the examinations, non-cooperative behavior of board authorities, the delay in the delivery of test questionnaires, improper seat plan, and fear of paper leak-out. Findings show that students feel discomfort and are disheartened due to the prevalence of these factors in their examinations, making them feel unsatisfied with the general conduct of board examinations. To address these issues, four recommendations from the respondents emerged: the provision of a comfortable testing environment, proper behavior of allocated examination staff, active engagement in addressing complaints from

examinees, and the cooperative attitude of the examiners. Specifically, the respondents suggested that the testing environment should have proper arrangement of light, electricity, and clean water; the invigilators should properly relay essential information to examinees in a polite manner; examinees should be given ample time to raise complaints to avoid inconvenience in taking the exams; and examiners should cooperate with students who are experiencing difficulty and problems during the examinations. Overall, the researchers recommended further research on a broader level to address the problems identified in the study. Conducting a research on the behavior of examination personnel that manages and conducts the examinations could help promote an understanding of the nature of their work. Contextualizing their communicative acts could provide meaning to their examination roles and help define their behavior. When their roles and communicative practices are established and clearly defined, policy implementers could formulate enhanced guidelines that nurture the cooperative attitude of examination personnel in a licensure examination setting. As the focus of Sadiq and Saeed's study (2017) is on students as respondents, a similar study on licensure examinees as respondents would likewise be conceivable.

Childs & Umezawa (2009) conducted a study on test proctors in an elementary education setting. The study investigated what Grade 3 teachers from Ontario, Canada would do under situations of test administration dilemmas and why; these teachers concurrently act as proctors in administering standardized examinations within the classroom setting to elementary students. Vignettes or scenarios had been presented to the respondents of the Study wherein hypothetical dilemmas were situated. Based on the findings of the Study, many respondents predicted that they would not strictly comply with the test administration instructions

when faced with a student who has made a careless mistake in filling-out an answer sheet (vignette one) or is writing very short responses to questions requiring explanation or further description (vignette two), despite the fact that proctors administering Ontario's assessment tests to their examinees are required not to say and do anything else other than to administer the test procedures. However, the respondents in this Study have said that if faced with these situations, they would either act non-compliantly – in which a proctor chooses to do something that he/she believes is contrary to the preparation or administration instructions, or creatively compliant – in which a proctor chooses to do something that he/she believes is contrary to the intent of the instructions, but not contrary to a literal interpretation of the instructions. Among the rationale behind these responses from proctors include supporting the examinees to do their best work and ensuring a positive testing experience for the examinees. These findings suggest that test developers need to consider the role of the proctor when they formulate guidelines for test administration for standardized examinations, since the comparability and accuracy of test results will be compromised if proctors are choosing not to follow the test administration instructions. Said Study opens the opportunity for a similar research undertaking in the Philippine setting, to understand how assigned room watchers perform test administration in licensure examinations and to explore how their behavior, constituted in their communicative practices, affects the overall integrity of the licensure examination being administered. This would also serve as a blueprint reference for test developers and as licensure examination conduct implementer to evaluate their test administration policies and procedures, particularly in the employment of room watchers or proctors, to ensure the integrity and credibility of its licensure examinations.

Ettien (2018) conducted a research that aimed to understand why proctors, whose role and duty is to watch over candidates (i.e. examinees) in order to prevent cheating on their part, can suddenly become the candidates' protectors against examination supervisors. It is mentioned in Ettien's study that cheating is one of the tools that most "unprepared" examinees use during the examinations to gain leverage in obtaining higher examination rating. Such act is classified as academic dishonesty, and it requires the attention of the national government authorities to compel all involved in organizing the examinations to maintain its integrity. The role of proctors in conducting examinations is deemed indispensable, as no examination could be held normally without their presence in the testing centers. As representatives of the government, being employed as volunteers, it is expected that proctors and all other examination personnel are free of criminal records, and that they embrace fairness, justice, courtesy, and impartiality in their behavior. Proctors are expected to obey and follow instructions given by authorities in the conduct of the examinations. Ettien argues that if the cheating among proctors really exists, then it follows that candidates themselves also cheat, that proctors who cheat would aim to foster the success of examinees. In the study's investigation, it was found that most of those who engage in exam proctoring are suffering from poor financial conditions, and that they accept monetary offers from candidates to enable cheating in the testing environment. The practice of "Upside Down Proctoring" is then identified as the act of proctors' "normalizing" free and noiseless communication between the candidates upon taking their "bribe", leading to the normalization of dishonest acts as if these are acts of honesty during the course of the examinations (Ettien, 2018). Such actions are a blatant display of the breach in integrity in conducting examinations, since both proctor and candidate collude towards a

mutual, beneficial gain; the proctors gets a financial advantage in being bribed, while the candidate gets an intellectual advantage by communicating with his/her co-candidates to seek answers for the examination. In conclusion, the study recommends the granting of fair compensation for examination proctors and for the government to reconsider the examination proctoring conditions for its volunteers, to ultimately prevent cheating. While the grant of monetary payment for volunteers serves as the reward for their part in the conduct of examinations, it is believed that it is not the sole factor that must be assessed to determine the extent of integrity being observed in the act of test administration. The mere act of “free and noiseless” communication between proctors and examinees is another factor that needs to be explored, which Ettien’s study in 2018 did not fully capture. Studying this aspect could help reveal the reality of test administration, particularly on how proctors and other examination personnel communicate through verbal and non-verbal means with its examinees in licensure examinations. Whether or not such communication enables cheating could be a subject of another research pursuit.

The licensure examinations commonly administered involve paper-and-pencil tests (PPTs) of multiple choice objective questions. These objective tests are important in considering, among others, the decision-making of granting licensure accreditations (Hartman, 1986) by legal authorities. The test results of competency-based examinations are deemed valid and reliable indications of an individual’s ability or achievement (Hartman, 1986). Conducting these tests, however, is susceptible to “testing irregularities” such as widespread cheating and fraud involving (medical) licensure examinations (Lyons, 1984), and giving test answers to examinees (Siegel, 1985). Hartman (1986), in his Study entitled “Detecting Cheating on Multiple-Choice Examinations”, explained that the act of cheating is difficult to

completely define as it could take into a variety of forms (p. 4) such as answer copying by one or more examinees or the involvement of an unethical teacher who acts as room watcher before, during, and after the administration of multiple-choice examinations. Buss and Novick (1980) classifies cheating as a form of testing irregularity, along with others like inaccurate timing, nonstandard test administration, or administration of an incorrect testing material. Hartman conducted a research (1986) that developed and studied computerized methods that utilize analyses of patterns of incorrect test responses to determine the existence of test irregularities between pairs of examinees or larger groups. Data from fifth-graders were analyzed in a math subject test consisting of one hundred four (104) items and the language subject test consisting of eighty (80) items, which were subsequently subjected to class-by-class and item-by-item analysis using two computer programs namely "WIC.BAS" and "RUN.BAS". Findings show that test irregularities may be detectable, and that irregularities occurred in 5 to 8% of the 170 fifth-grade classrooms studied. Hartman stressed the importance of conducting an investigative study that incorporates other measures of assessing test irregularities, such as interviewing teachers, students, and examination administrators, examination of answer sheets, retesting, and longitudinal study of testing procedures, protocol, and of test administration. This argument suggests the necessity to explore testing procedures and to gather information from actual examination administrators, including proctors, in order to establish communicative practices that determine the occurrence and detection of testing irregularities, specifically in licensure examinations.

Minott (2018) utilized a small-scale grounded approach qualitative study to examine the beliefs of selected external examination invigilators (EEl) and to infer the kinds of activities that they perceive as important in the conduct of examinations

in the secondary and higher education levels. Through purposeful convenience or opportunity sampling, informal interviews and participant observation were utilized on five (5) EEs with 3-5 years of examination invigilation experience in a London secondary school. Results indicate that EEs place high importance in the way that they are rated according to their invigilation performance, in how they ensure examination intangibles (i.e. fairness, impartiality, and integrity), and in how they consistently implement examination procedures. This reinforces the need to highlight the importance of examination intangibles and procedures in examination policies at all levels of the education sector (Minott, 2018). Similarly, conducting an empirical study on EEs in licensure examinations in the Philippines could contextualize how their communicative practices help ensure the so-called examination intangibles in actual board competency examinations.

Saani & Tawiah (2017) conducted a study that examines the effect of training and development (T&D) on the work performance of invigilators of University of Cape Coast (UCC), Ghana. It utilized the census method on forty-nine (49) invigilators using questionnaire and work performance appraisal forms. Completed questionnaires were used in data analysis through Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis. The results of said study revealed that T&D programmes do not contribute much to the work performance of invigilators, unless they are satisfied with the appropriateness of these programmes in relation to their work as invigilators. The recommendation suggested in the study involves maximizing the trainees' satisfaction and effort to transfer the skills they have learned to improve their examination invigilation performance, which could be achieved presumably by using effective supervision and motivation strategies. In relation to licensure examinations, this particular study could be a reference point for

understanding how training or briefing sessions for room watchers and examination supervisors influence their communicative acts. In addition, it emphasizes the need to take a look at how examination supervisors use their interpersonal skills to guide the room watchers or other staff under their supervision to perform their duties and responsibilities properly and more effectively.

Irira (2014) pursued a study that examines the management of examinations at the Institute of Adult Education (IAE) in Tanzania. It identified examination challenges faced by the institution, such as the shortage of and uncommitted examination invigilators, the unattractive allowance offered for invigilation, lack of back-up electricity supply during power interruptions, and the setting of unrealistic examination-related deadlines. Findings revealed that one out of four senior officials of the IAE strongly agreed that the current examination management strategies of the Institute compromise the quality of examinations offered, and that attention to budgetary allocation and in careful planning and implementation should be prioritized by the management to ensure quality in test administration. The conduct of periodic workshops on examination invigilators and the formulation of clearly-written examination rules and regulations were among the suggestions in the said Study. Pursuing a similar research on examination rules and regulations may likewise be plausible, considering that the proper conduct of licensure examinations is grounded in the policies and guidelines implemented. This may also explore if the shortage of room watchers or available examination personnel is a factor in maintaining the integrity of licensure examinations. In cases of examination personnel shortage, the communicative practices of examination supervisors to address such problem could also be looked into.

Shehzad & Dogar (2020) conducted a qualitative study that explored the problems and malpractices during the examinations of Grade 5 and Grade 8 students in Punjab, Pakistan. Twenty-four (24) heads of Examination Cluster Centers were selected through simple random sampling technique for interview. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. Findings reveal some of the problems in the conduct of examinations, such as the incorrect assignment of number slips, shortage and misprinting of test papers, security and secrecy, inappropriate examination centers, and stringent monitoring & distributing of papers. On the other hand, the malpractices identified in the study include peeking and talking with other candidates (i.e. examinees), possession of cheating material, and the showing & exchanging of test papers. Among the reasons why such malpractices have been tolerated include competition among schools to attract students or parents, the students' desire to obtain higher scores, pressure on the teachers' part to show better performance, and the students' intent to be promoted to the next grade. These malpractices have been shown in the study to have contaminated the education system in the country of Pakistan. The said study could serve as a reference study on possibly exploring the prevalence of such problems and malpractices in Philippine licensure examinations, apart from the academic school setting. Specifically, discovering how examination supervisors and proctors resolve problems in licensure examinations through communication would enlighten how they cooperate to mitigate risks that potentially compromise the integrity of licensure examinations. It is worthy to note that licensure examinations as much as any other academic examination follow a schedule that prescribes the dates and times upon which the test subjects are to be administered. The limited time that regulatory bodies provide for conducting the examinations could serve as a crucial factor in the

observation and practice of communicative practices among examination invigilators to optimize performing all related activities attached to their respective duties and responsibilities in a time-bounded manner.

Snyman (1993) examined whether pre-employment paper-and-pencil tests (PPTs) are able to detect faking. The study attempted to address the concern of the question “Can an applicant try to produce scores that will not be an indicator of his/her honesty and still be hired?” One hundred (100) undergraduate students took three honesty tests in any of the following three conditions: answer honestly, fake good, or simulate another person. Findings have shown that honesty scales were “fakable”, but that validity scales were extremely effective in detecting subjects’ attempts at faking (Snyman, 1993). Meanwhile, subjects in the personality simulation condition obtained scores similar in the answer honestly condition, indicating that validity scales cannot detect responses that are simulated in nature. This study inspires looking at how examinee impersonation is prevented through the invigilation of room watchers and other exam supervisors in the professional licensure setting.

Balash et al. (2021) explored the security and privacy perceptions of student test-takers being proctored in remote examinations administered through online proctoring services that employ various student monitoring methods to curb cheating, including restricted (“lockdown”) browser modes, video/screen monitoring, local network traffic analyses, and eye tracking. This method of conducting examinations has been implemented by educational institutions in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. An analysis of user reviews of proctoring services’ browser extensions and an online survey subsequently was conducted among one hundred two (102) respondents. Findings imply that participants are concerned about both the amount and the personal nature of information shared with the exam proctoring

companies, though many participants recognize a trade-off between pandemic safety concerns and the invasive means by which proctoring services ensure examination integrity. It was suggested in the Study that institutional power dynamics and students' trust in their institutions may dissuade students' opposition to remote proctoring. The research privileges the view of online proctoring services in imposing restrictions upon student-examinees in an online setting. This creates an opportunity to examine the restrictions imposed by on room watchers or proctors as they interact with examinees during the administration of on-site licensure examinations. A similar study may also be explored if and when the conduct of Computer-Based Licensure Examinations (CBLE) is fully implemented.

It is evident in the above empirical literatures that the perspectives of examination personnel or invigilators assigned in the pedagogical context are privileged. The "voice" that had been muted or the perspective marginalized was the contextual explanation (or the meaning behind the act) of examination administration within the licensure examinations outside an academic environment. This muted voice/perspective considers examination personnel, including room watchers, not as the source of knowledge like the teachers who responded in the majority of those studies, but primarily as administrators of prescribed procedures in licensure examinations. As such, this study gives "voice" to the communication knowledge produced by examination invigilators, such as the examination coordinator, the building supervisors, the floor supervisors, and the room watchers, as they reveal their views on the act of licensure examination administration, and on how such views define their communication practices as examination volunteers, towards the reproduction of rule regime in licensure examinations to preserve its credibility, integrity, and inviolability.

Chapter III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Research Framework

This study is anchored on the Socio-Cultural Tradition of Communication Theory, which theorizes communication as the (re)production of social order (Craig, 1999). This involves looking at communication as a symbolic process that produces, maintains, repairs, and transforms reality (Carey, 1989 in Craig, 1999). In this tradition, communication is theorized through the use of meta-discursive vocabulary such as society, structure, practice, ritual, rule, socialization, culture, identity, and co-construction. In this tradition, one aspect that renders communication as plausible is the notion that each individual is shaped by the society, that every society has a unique culture, and that social actions have unintended effects (Craig, 1999). For communication to succeed, individuals depend upon one another on a shared context of social institutions and cultural patterns, reproduced and flexibly adapted upon interaction to maintain society and enable social change in the macro-level (Craig, 2016). As such, value is placed in the act of social interaction, through which rule regime as a structure of social order is made possible in the first place. As this tradition finds an interest on meta-discursive commonplaces such as individual agency and responsibility, the absolute identity of self, and in the naturalness of social order, the Study finds alignment in this tradition such that it places a point of view upon the collaboration and organization of examination invigilators and in the responsibility that each partakes to accomplish the conduct of licensure examinations. Overall, the social reality of test administration is constituted in the social interactions engaged individually by its human components.

The action orientation of the Socio-Cultural Tradition highlights communicative practices, which are actual means of expression in a lived world, provided the uniqueness of scenes and circumstances (Carbaugh, 1996). The activities performed through these communicative practices have symbolic values through which individuals express themselves into positions vis-à-vis others (Rothenbuhler, 1993) evident in implementing a rule system in an institution. Schmitt (1995) classifies *licensure examinations* as competency examinations administered by the state to determine whether an individual is worthy to be granted a license to practice. The involvement of people in administering licensure examinations calls for discovering their points of view within this context, as they perform examination administration roles consummated through social interaction to constitute the rule regime of licensure examination administration.

The ontological assumption in this Study involved defining the subjective dimension of reality in the point of view of the examination personnel on how licensure examinations are administered, which are deemed multiple and subjective based on their personal experiences. On the other hand, the epistemological assumption in this Study focused on identifying the contextual explanation, or the meaning behind the action, of administering licensure examinations as various examination personnel engage in the act of communication. It is believed that such knowledge is emergent only from the examination personnel themselves as the researched community.

Within the Socio-Cultural Tradition, this Study treats rule regime as a concept of structure that needs a thorough understanding of how people cooperate to accomplish a collective goal, despite their individual interests and orientations. This involves looking at how individuals and organized groups act collectively under the

contrasting forces of dependence and interdependence, as well as cooperation and conflict (Kurawa, 2011). This complexity could be demonstrated in Adam Smith's Division of Labor concept in which tasks are carried out through the specialized efforts of various individuals under an interdependent, organized working structure. With each individual focusing on a specific aspect of a particular work, productivity becomes attainable towards accomplishing goals and objectives.

The Socio-Cultural Tradition privileges consensus over change and conflict (Craig, 1999). Consensus is a principle essential in performing an institution's mandate. It facilitates actions that reproduce order, through communicative practices that promote coordination and unity of direction. The rule regime of each institution is grounded in the cluster of social relationships, roles, norms, and values shared by and within their interdependencies. It also serves as the foundation in the institutional knowledge that guides the performance of specific roles by each member of an institution, particularly in their respective duties and responsibilities. As their duties and responsibilities are effectively performed, a certain degree of consensus in an institution is established, and a sense of normality is achieved in which institutional problems that arise become manageable to solve. This supports the notion that institutions are systems of authority and power that constitutes a particular social order.

Rules are implemented in public institutions to sustain their public functions (Ceva, 2022). But it is not sufficient to acknowledge that institutional rules are just a set of instructions to perform any activity towards accomplishment. It is also crucial to understand the boundaries produced by role differentiation, the conduct embraced in the performance of these roles, and how the rules that govern such roles are designed and applied. Appreciating public institutional action would then need the

analysis of individual communicative practices and actions that form a coherent whole that is capable of realizing its core mandate. On this premise, regulatory bodies are treated as institutions that consist of people who exercise role-related duties and responsibilities that are coordinated by institutional rules. Such applies in the way that examination personnel are designated to take responsibility for the success (and failure) of licensure examinations.

This study is undertaken within the *Interpretive School* of Organizational Communication, such that it looks at communication as one that produces the organization (Deetz, 2001). In this context, the regulatory body is continually produced (and reproduced) by the interactions among its examination personnel, through their engagement in interactions that shape new or modify existing organizational structures, processes, and behaviors.

Research Questions

Using the above framework, this Study assumed that rule regime (as a structure of social order) is reproduced through the communicative practices of personnel assigned in licensure examinations. These interactions are discursive in nature, performing authority and responsibility to maintain order. Thus, the empirical data from the participants in this Study could provide answers to the following questions:

1. *What are the communicative practices of assigned personnel in the conduct and administration of licensure examinations?*
2. *How do their communicative practices reproduce rule regime in the context of licensure examinations?*

Chapter IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study embraced a Qualitative communication research paradigm with a discursive framing under the *Discourse of Understanding*, in which the subject position of the knower is in “productive, dialectical tension” (Mumby, 1997, p.6) with the object position of what is being known (i.e. the examination personnel). This view assumes a praxeological assumption that conceives of communication in this Study as the creation of meaning, which is “essentially symbolic” (Mumby, 1997, p. 7) or constitutive of the practices of examination personnel in the conduct of licensure examinations. The process of knowledge production in this Study is dialogical in nature, which would involve the researcher engaging in actual in-depth interviews with participants of the Study. The knowledge produced in this Study is an understanding of the meaning of practices of licensure examination personnel in communicating as they participate in the administration of licensure examinations to reproduce the structure of a rule regime. In this sense, rule regime is treated as a structure of authority, a pattern of relationships socially constructed through interaction among individual members (Saludadez, 2021).

Under the Interpretive School of Organizational Communication, this Study utilized an *inductive* approach in which knowledge is created by generating theory using the data obtained from the participants of the research (Saludadez, 2021). The data to be gathered were subjected to transcription, coding and thematic analysis for the identification of common themes that led to theoretical propositions on rule regime reproduction in the communicative practices in conducting licensure examinations.

The main approach in the theoretical pursuit of this Study is *Ethnomethodology* (abbreviated as “EM”), as it provides for the location of meaning in the communicative practices in the conduct of licensure examinations, which helped create an understanding – a contextual explanation – of how assigned accomplish such as examination supervisors, room watchers, and other essential examination personnel their duties and responsibilities. Williams (2001) formally defines EM as an approach in sociology that studies the “common-sense” resources, procedures, and practices through which members of a society interpret their everyday life and how these social interactions, when mutually recognized within particular contexts, create orderliness. The accomplishment of various activities would be highlighted in order to establish the meaning behind the context of test administration in the perspective of examination personnel.

This view was made consistent with the *Socio-Cultural Tradition* of Communication Theory (Craig, 1999) in which the researcher and the participants in the Study co-construct reality and interpret it in specific ways (Magut, 2016). As such, this involved understanding and explaining various possible meanings of licensure examination administration under a natural setting in search of relativity, detail, and flexibility (Jwan & Ong’ondo, 2011).

As explained by Lindlof and Taylor (2019), EM aims to answer the research question “How do ‘they’ do it?” In this study, EM is employed to explore how examination personnel administer procedures in the conduct of licensure examinations. It is expected that interviewing and engaging with these examination personnel produced emergent conceptualizations on the communicative methods that they use to perform their duties and responsibilities to accomplish the act of administering licensure examinations, reproducing rule regime in effect.

The concept of Ethnomethodology as a qualitative research approach was introduced by Harold Garfinkel in 1967 (Lindlof & Taylor, 2019). EM aims to understand the *folk procedures* that people use for performing sensible acts in their daily activities. It recognizes the act of experiencing activities and the role that people play to accomplish these. As such, this method is focused on the construction of the meaning through social and conversational practices (Sacks, 1963 in Lindlof & Taylor, 2019). Specifically, it looks at the situational resources as well as the sequence of activities that communicators use to establish the plausibility of an event. This methodological focus provides a lens for research on the resources used and the sequence of procedures performed by involved examination personnel in licensure examinations. Moreover, in the intent of accomplishing the administration of licensure examinations, EM could classify the communicative acts of examination personnel as “indexical”, as they implicitly establish contextual resources for meaning in pursuit of successful interaction (Lindlof & Taylor, 2019). This leads to the need for examination personnel to depict their actions as relevant contributions towards producing a logical, coordinated social action in the conduct of examinations.

Garfinkel also highlighted the role of “accounting” in pursuit of seeking and providing contextual explanations from participants of *what they think they are doing* (Heritage, 1984 in Lindlof & Taylor, 2019). EM treats actions of people involved as subject to the principle of accountability and it assumes that people are concerned with producing recognizable actions (Laurier & Bodden, 2020 in Kobayashi, 2020). This opens the plausibility of exploring participants through EM in justifying their communicative behavior to accomplish their duties and responsibilities when immersing themselves in the administration of licensure examinations. It is to be

considered, however, that being “accountable” should not be understood as a moral term in this context; rather, it is a means of describing how people make their actions seem rational to a particular situation or context where certain events take place (Ten Have, 2016 in Nickerson, 2023). To quote Garfinkel (1967), “Ethnomethodological studies analyze everyday activities as members’ methods for making those same activities visibly rational and reportable for all practical purposes, i.e. ‘accountable’, as organizations of commonplace everyday activities.” In this view, Garfinkel asserts that people, being members of a society, actively create and maintain social reality within a continuous process of reconstruction and accomplishment (Ten Have, 2016 in Nickerson, 2023) through folk methods, such as tacit knowledge, routine practices, and ordinary language (Lynch, 2001). Hence, it is presumed that the participants’ social interactions contribute to the social order of rule regime that aims to preserve the integrity of licensure examinations.

Nickerson (2023) contends that EM is a means of formulating observations and inquiries into social interactions in a way that emphasizes how individuals make sense of their own worlds, rather than theoretical frameworks already created by social scientists. It is the aim of ethnomethodological investigations to understand how members of a society make rationalities or considerations backed by common sense in performing actions (Nickerson, 2023); these considerations and practices should then be observable and reportable from the point of view of social scientists in investigative inquiries, and comprehensible in the conduct of social action (Liddicoat, 2023).

Ten Have (2016) cites that EM places more interest in the competencies exhibited by the members of a certain collective, and less in individuals per se. This methodology suits the study’s intent to look at the collective capacities of

examination supervisors, room watchers, and other examination personnel to engage in communicative acts of speaking, knowing, understanding, and being responsive to situations that ensure the integrity of licensure examinations. As members of such a collective, these examination personnel are able to interpret others who likewise belong to the same collective.

In the 1960s, EM had been used as a way of examining various people-processing institutions, examples of which are schools or universities, welfare offices, and police departments (Clayman, 2001 in Nickerson, 2023). Clayman (2001) highlights that EM studies aim to reveal that members of people-processing institutions undertake considerations based on their “lived world” knowledge of what actions or outcomes would be reasonable and necessary for a particular situation, rather than from the criteria set forth by the rules of these organizations. As an approach, EM calls for the pursuit of or “struggle” for meaning, instead of placing mere assumptions of meaning within people when they say or do something.

Studies conducted within EM have revealed that formal rules set forth by people-processing institutions do not capture the judgment that sensible individuals can implement such rules in a concrete manner (Nickerson, 2023). In effect, there exists a discrepancy between formal rules and the activities undertaken by members of these institutions, which may have crucial implications in understanding how people-processing institutions often make consequential official designations of people (e.g. “room watcher” or “floor supervisor”) and how these consistently fit to actions (e.g. “proctoring” or “examination invigilation”).

Research Participants

For this study, I selected qualified participants based on sound judgment, largely due to the limitation of individuals who can serve as primary data sources for

this study. Specifically, this involves focusing on the subgroup of examination personnel wherein the participants have performed similar occupations and have obtained relevant experience (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012).

The following examination personnel designations had one participant each (n=1): Examination Coordinator, Building Supervisor, Attendance Supervisor, Supply Officer, Floor Supervisor, Supply Aide, Room Watcher/Proctor, and Security Officer. Each participant possessed relevant experience of having served in at least (3) calendar years within such designations, in view of being able to provide information regarding communicative practices on the basis of significant knowledge or familiarity (Tongco, 2007) with the procedures as well as the duties and responsibilities from a variety of professional licensure examinations conducted in the past. They are classified either as officials/employees of the regulatory body or as regular outsider volunteers (including the Security Officer) whose services are utilized more especially when licensure examinations are held in weekdays.

For purposes of convenience in the conduct of this study, the research participants were purposively selected from the pool of examination volunteers managed and maintained by the Examination Section under the Licensure and Registration Division of the researcher's place of work assignment. Table 1 below shows the Demographics Profile of the Examination Personnel Participants:

Table 1.
Demographics Profile of the Participants

Participant	Gender	Age	Personnel Background	Experience
Key Informant A	Female	49 years old	Room Watcher	8 years (since 2015)
Key Informant B	Female	30 years old	Floor Supervisor	5 years (since 2018)
Key Informant C	Female	31 years old	Building Supervisor	10 years (since 2013)
Key Informant D	Female	54 years old	Exam Coordinator	13 years (since 2010)
Key Informant E	Female	30 years old	Attendance Supervisor	4 years (since 2019)
Key Informant F	Male	29 years old	Supply Officer	5 years (since 2018)
Key Informant G	Male	24 years old	Supply Aide	3 years (since 2020)
Key Informant H	Male	48 years old	Security Officer	12 years (since 2011)

Key Informant A (Room Watcher) is a regularly-outsourced volunteer proctor of the regulatory body. She has extensive experience in serving as room watcher for eight (8) years up to present, and has been assigned frequently in other capacities in licensure examinations, such as Floor Supervisor and Building Supervisor.

Key Informant B (Floor Supervisor) is a staff of the Examination Section of the regulatory body, regularly employed for more than five (5) years. She is likewise frequently assigned as Room Watcher, Floor Supervisor, and Building Supervisor in various licensure examinations. As staff in the Examination Section, she assists in the preparation of examination venues and materials to be used during scheduled licensure examinations.

Key Informant C (Building Supervisor) is the unit head of the Examination Section of the regulatory body, employed for more than ten (10) years. She helps oversee the preparation and conduct of licensure examinations held. She is regularly

assigned as Building Supervisor in small, medium, and large-scale licensure examinations.

Key Informant D (Exam Coordinator) is the Chief of the Licensure & Registration Division (LRD) of the regulatory body. Prior to being promoted to her present position, she previously served as unit head of the Examination Section for eight (8) years and has been regularly assigned as Exam Coordinator in various examinations, alternate to the Regional Director. She is also assigned occasionally as Attendance Supervisor.

Key Informant E (Attendance Supervisor) is a staff of the Examination Section, employed for more than four (4) years. She assists in the preparation of communication letters and documents to be used in organizing the activities of the licensure examinations. Prior to being employed in the Agency, she had years of experience in organizing and administering examinations for aspiring students in a local seminary in Leyte.

Key Informant F (Supply Officer) is a staff of the Examination Section, regularly employed for more than 5 years. Being the only male personnel in the section, he is frequently assigned as Supply Officer and Supply Aide in licensure examinations. He assists in the posting of list of examinees in rooms to be utilized within the testing center/s. He also assists in organizing the supplies and materials to be utilized for the licensure examination.

Key Informant G (Supply Aide) is an outsourced janitor of the regulatory body, assigned as Supply Aide in licensure examinations for more than three (3) years.

Key Informant H (Security Officer) is a policeman regularly designated as Security Officer in licensure examinations for more than twelve (12) years.

Figure 1 below illustrates the typical hierarchy of personnel in the practice of licensure examination administration:

Figure 1.
Hierarchy of Examination Personnel in Licensure Examinations
(Source: Licensure Division, 2022)

Site Access

To gain authority to conduct research from the participants, a letter-request was submitted to the Regional Director of the Agency for his consent (see *Appendix “A”*), informing him of the nature and intent of this Study, what information was obtained from the participants, who are qualified to participate in the Study, and the extent of confidentiality of the information obtained from them.

Likewise, a letter-request was submitted to each participant for their consent respectively (see *Appendix “B”*), informing them of the nature and intent of this Study, what information was needed from the participant, how the researcher gathered data, and the extent of confidentiality of the information obtained from the participant.

Data Collection

Ethnomethodology adopts an approach to research that emphasizes on the local and situated nature of social action (Liddicoat, 2023). As such, the study intended to collect data that can be analyzed to reveal underlying processes through which social order or orderliness is created or maintained.

To achieve this, the main method that had been employed to generate data for this Study is the conduct of in-depth Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) using open-ended questions with each of the participant (*see Appendix "C"*). The researcher engaged in in-depth conversations about their thoughts on the duties and responsibilities, including the procedures that they follow when involved during licensure examinations. A mixture of semi-structured interview and informal conversations was utilized in engaging with the participants to obtain data that are as natural and genuine as possible. In addition, it facilitated the understanding of naturally occurring instances of social interaction.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

To answer the first research question, it is deemed important that concepts should be formulated from the data obtained from the participants. These concepts are aimed to discover the communicative practices of assigned examination personnel. With this, the analysis and interpretation of data in this study have an underpinning in the Grounded Theory Method (GTM) of Glaser and Strauss. Creswell (2007) characterized GTM as focused on building a theory (or concept) which is grounded in data from the field by analyzing activities, procedures, or interactions which involve a number of individuals. These led to the assignment of codes from their narratives, which allowed theorizing that provide meaningful insights to courses of action not explicitly described by pre-existing communication theories.

To answer the second research question, the participants' narratives were subjected to Thematic Analysis. Clustering the data sets through the codes generated to describe their communicative practices, these codes were analyzed to derive and surface main themes used to construct a theoretical proposition on rule regime reproduction in licensure examinations.

The main themes that surfaced resulted from an analysis of the participants' communicative practices. The narratives were sorted, categorized, and labelled based on the similarity of their patterns and features to represent a communicative act. Each communicative act was subjected to *dimensionalization* (Lindlof & Taylor, 2019) to develop deeper meanings from the participants' narratives. In each category or dimension, specific attributes and characteristics of the participants' narratives were examined for interpretation within the theoretical perspective of Craig's Socio-Cultural Tradition of Communication Theory.

A matrix of qualitative data was used to present the generated codes from each data set, to facilitate the analysis of the participants' narratives, and to assign themes that surfaced from the analysis of the acts of communication similarly observed among the participants, as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2.

Matrix of Qualitative Data Analysis

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>“What I do is I usually roam around my area of responsibility to check if Room Watchers are following the mandated procedures... to attend to queries and concerns if any. I listen first and then answer clearly, direct to the point ... While the examination is on-going, I roam around to monitor and check the room watchers ... to find out if all examinees have already reported and if not, I ask the room watchers how many examinees have not arrived yet.” (Key Informant B)</p>	<p><i>Roaming Around</i></p>	<p>They strategize socialization to align the knowledge of rules.</p>	<p>(1) RULE ALIGNMENT</p>
<p>“I really do a regular room-to-room visit to check the examinees, the room watchers, and especially the floor supervisors before and during the examination ... I roam around, usually using my eye contact and hand signals, especially when checking the rooms.” (Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Roaming Around</i></p>	<p>They socialize to align action.</p>	
<p>“I have to roam around to observe people, to pay attention to situations, to ensure that the testing area is peaceful and silent enough so as not to disturb the examinees as they take their test.” (Key Informant H)</p>	<p><i>Roaming Around</i></p>	<p>They align actions and observations.</p>	
<p>“The first thing an Exam Coordinator does is to visit the testing site. If you are the Exam Coordinator, you really have to be there.</p>	<p><i>Resolving Issues</i></p>	<p>They resolve conflicts to align understanding of rules.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>You need to see what is going on, monitor how the assigned personnel manage things, and of course, to do decision-making when your intervention is necessary.” (Key Informant D)</p> <p>“When I call people’s attention, I always talk in a nice way. I control the tone of my voice; I do not talk or act aggressively because it could worsen the situation. I try to remain calm; I always base my explanations to the rules and regulations implemented by the Agency in its examinations. For example, if an examinee is unruly or has a distraught behavior inside the room, I assist in calming the situation. I do not immediately treat it as a violation, because it is quite normal for examinees to get stressed while under pressure. But I assist in de-escalating.” (Key Informant H)</p>	<p><i>Resolving Issues / Restraining Tension</i></p>	<p>They align their emotions with what the rules prescribe.</p>	
<p>“It is really a challenging job, because sometimes you not only manage the building, you also need to manage your patience, your temper, your facial expressions, including the words and instructions you tell other people. Sa’yo lahat kasi, eh. (<i>Everything is yours.</i>) The responsibility, the accountability, and even the blame.” (Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Retaining Professional Composure</i></p>	<p>They project professionalism in reference to rules.</p>	
<p>“I just remain calm, alert, and attentive when conflicts or problems arise. I just make myself available and reliable in whatever circumstances that may occur. What</p>	<p><i>Retaining Professional Composure</i></p>	<p>They display professional demeanor congruent to what is required by rules.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>matters is as a Floor Supervisor, you really have to maintain an open communication.” (Key Informant B)</p> <p>“When I call people’s attention, I always talk in a nice way. I control the tone of my voice; I do not talk or act aggressively because it could worsen the situation. I try to remain calm; I always base my explanations to the rules and regulations implemented by the Agency in its examinations” (Key Informant H)</p> <p>I also ask the Building Supervisor for confirmation on the number of rooms in his/her building.” (Key Informant D)</p> <p>“Upon arrival of the examinees, I check their names in the list of examinees and ascertain their identities vis-à-vis their Notice of Admission (NOA) and the Seat Plan. When done, I lead them to their assigned seat following the seat plan arrangement. If the number of examinees assigned in the room is now complete, I will have the attendance checking to ensure if they are properly seated according to their assigned seat number.</p> <p>At the end of the exam, we submit the Room Watcher’s Report, Seat Plan, and Examinees Record of Attendance, and then the FS checks whether we have properly accomplished all the forms, and then we tally if we have the same statistics and information.”</p>	<p><i>Retaining Professional Composure</i></p> <p><i>Reviewing Exam Statistics</i></p> <p><i>Reviewing Exam Statistics</i></p>	<p>They align authority and human gestures.</p> <p>They establish information as basis for implementing rules.</p> <p>They organize information as basis for implementing rules.</p>	<p>(2) RULE IMPLEMENTATION</p>

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>(Key Informant A) “Once the Building Supervisor instructs the distribution of the test questionnaires, we count and check if the number of test booklets/questionnaires tally with the number indicated in the Floor Supervisor’s Distribution and Accountability Form. If the numbers tally, then I distribute the test questionnaires to the room watchers in each room, with the help of my Supply Aide. In the event that the room watchers failed to distribute the test questionnaires properly, meaning if they gave Set A to an examinee that should have been given Set B or vice-versa, we retain the set of the first subject to avoid confusion on the part of the examinee and to easily verify and consolidate statistics.”</p>	<p><i>Reviewing Exam Statistics</i></p>	<p>They review numbers to implement consistent rules.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant B) “By 8:00 a.m., we are quite pressured to report our statistics to the Exam Coordinator. Kailangan niya kasi yung data (<i>he/she needs the data</i>) to inform the Central Office about how many examinees were on our list, how many were absent, and how many examinees actually took the examination. ... This is why I ask data from my floor supervisors ASAP, and compare their numbers with each room they covered para may check-and-balance (<i>so there would be check-and-balance</i>).”</p>	<p><i>Reviewing Exam Statistics</i></p>	<p>They establish information as proof of rule implementation.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant C) “At the end of every subject, dapat tally ang</p>	<p><i>Re-Checking Documents</i></p>	<p>They evaluate rule</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>number of examinees at saka yung number ng test booklets at answer sheets. Kapag may discrepancy, o kaya kung kulang ‘yung nai-submit sa amin na test booklet o answer sheet, kami ang accountable, hahanapin pa namin ‘yung examinee para lang masecure na maisasauli yung nawawalang papeles. <i>(the number of examinees and the number of test booklets and answer sheets should tally equally. If there are any discrepancies, of if there are missing pieces in the submissions, we are held accountable, we need to locate the examinee just to ensure that the missing papers are returned.)</i>” (Key Informant A)</p>		<p>effectivity and account for lapses.</p>	
<p>“The room watchers will submit to the Floor Supervisor a brown envelope containing the Answer Sheets, as well as the bundle of used test questionnaires. With the help of the Supply Aide, we count the number of answer sheets that we received and the number of test questionnaires from each room. We always make sure that the count tallies with the number of examinees present and the total indicated/label on the brown envelope. After that, we seal with a packing tape the brown envelopes and sign across the sealing tapes on the flaps of the envelopes.” (Key Informant B)</p>	<p><i>Re-Checking Documents</i></p>	<p>Exam supervisors review subordinates’ implementation of rules.</p>	
<p>“Once I am done assigning the proctors in their rooms, I make sure next that the other examination personnel are able to sign in</p>	<p><i>Re-Checking Documents</i></p>	<p>Implementing rules demands information through documents.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>the attendance sheets and payroll sheets. Then I re-check every page of the attendance and payroll sheets to ensure that all fields that require signing have signatures.” (Key Informant E) “Once nakapag-submit na lahat ng Floor Supervisors, tinutulungan ko si Building Supervisor mag-balot ng overall packaging. Pati nasa sealing ng used TQs. Kapag nai-pack na lahat, babalik na ako sa opisina, escorted ako ni Security Officer, saka ko iretrieve yung Test Questionnaire para sa susunod na subject ng araw na iyon. (<i>Once all Floor Supervisors have submitted, I assist the Building Supervisor in the over-all packaging, including the sealing of used TQs. Once everything has been packed, I would return to the Office, as escorted by the Security Officer, and then I would retrieve the Test Questionnaire for the next subject of the examination day.</i>)”</p>	<p><i>Retrieval Procedures are Ensured</i></p>	<p>They provide order through organizing materials.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant F) “We seal with a packing tape the brown envelopes and sign across the sealing tapes on the flaps of the envelopes.”</p>	<p><i>Retrieval Procedures are Ensured</i></p>	<p>They assure order in rule implementation by organizing outputs.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant B) “After every subject, I wrap the TQs including all Answer Sheets as consolidated for turn-over to the Office.”</p>	<p><i>Retrieval Procedures are Ensured</i></p>	<p>They assure order in rule implementation by safeguarding outputs.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant C) “Pinapa-tawag kami minsan ng Supply Officer, lalo na kapag mabibigat o mararami</p>	<p><i>Retrieval Procedures are Ensured</i></p>	<p>Implementing rules requires socialization to</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>yung mga dadalhing boxes. Kadalasan, mga lalaki po ang pinupull-out para tumulong. Nakakahiya naman po kapag babae, mahirap naman silang obligahin tumulong magbuhat ng mga mabibigat na kahon. (<i>The Supply Officer often summons us to help, especially if there are many, heavy boxes to carry. Usually, male supply aides are being called to help. It is quite shameful if females would be obliged to carry heavy boxes.</i>)”</p> <p>(Key Informant G)</p>		<p>ensure support.</p>	
<p>“I reprimand the watchers discreetly if I catch them sleeping. And then I would walk slowly around in each floor under my area, and sometimes I would notice the room watchers paying attention to me. Occasionally, other exam personnel would say nga maisog an akon nawong (<i>that I have an angry face</i>), but I do not deny that.”</p> <p>(Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Reprimanding Personnel Who are Not Performing their Duties</i></p>	<p>They socialize to enforce compliance to rules.</p>	<p>(3) RULE COMPLIANCE</p>
<p>In fact, I also roam around to inspect if the room watchers observe wearing the proper attire. If the FS sees that they are not wearing proper attire, we reprimand them.”</p> <p>(Key Informant B)</p>	<p><i>Reprimanding Personnel Who are Not Performing their Duties</i></p>	<p>They enforce compliance to observe authority.</p>	
<p>“Dito rin namin ini-indicate (Room Watcher’s Report) kung may incidents ng cheating o kaya kapag may examinee na nag-violate ng rules, yung hindi sumunod sa proper dress code o di kaya yung nag-cellphone.</p>	<p><i>Reporting of Incidents and Violations of Procedures</i></p>	<p>They acknowledge failures of communication to maintain order.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p><i>(We also indicate here if there are cheating incidents or if there are any examinees who violated rules, those who did not follow the proper dress code or those who use cellphones.)"</i></p>			
<p>(Key Informant A) "While the examination is on-going, I start accomplishing forms and reports to be given to the Building Supervisor so that we have synchronicity in terms of information about the rooms I supervise."</p>	<p><i>Reporting of Incidents and Violations of Procedures</i></p>	<p>They acknowledge failures of communication.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant B) "The stapled forms submitted by the room watchers at the end of the examination, and the reports of each Floor Supervisor, lahat yan (<i>all of those</i>) form part of the overall report of conduct of the Building Supervisor, nasinu-submit namin (that we submit) to Central Office for documentation upon conclusion of the licensure examination."</p>	<p><i>Reporting of Incidents and Violations of Procedures</i></p>	<p>They acknowledge that rules cannot be complied at all times.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant C) "Building a good communication with them helped me maintain the cooperation I need to ensure a smooth and clean conduct of licensure examinations."</p>	<p><i>Reporting of Incidents and Violations of Procedures</i></p>	<p>Compliance to rules is reinforced by open communication.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant C) "If ever I am able to observe any unusual occurrences, I immediately report it to the assigned BS."</p>	<p><i>Reporting of Incidents and Violations of Procedures</i></p>	<p>Resolving failures in communication involves complying to authority.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant H) "By regularly monitoring the examination personnel, I get to know them personally; I ask their opinions and even their concerns</p>	<p><i>Reporting of Issues</i></p>	<p>They address conflicts in rule interpretation.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>during the conduct of examinations. Sometimes kasi nahihya silang magsulat samga report forms nila (<i>they are shy of writing down in their report forms</i>). So ako na mismo ang nagre-reach out (<i>I myself reach out</i>) to get their feedback.” (Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Reminding of Exam Procedures to Prevent Cheating</i></p>	<p>If rules are preserved, the reliability of exam results is preserved.</p>	<p>(4) RULE PRESERVATION</p>
<p>“Every once in a while, when the examination is on-going, I look at my room watchers and notice what they do. If they sleep, I wake them up and remind them to focus. I also prohibit them from talking and loitering in the hallways or in the examination room. If I catch them talking to others, I make eye contact to emphasize that I am listening to what they are saying and then I nod my head to show that I can understand them loud and clear.” (Key Informant B)</p>	<p><i>Reminding of Exam Procedures to Prevent Cheating</i></p>	<p>If rules are preserved, organizational reputation or identity is preserved.</p>	
<p>“I would usually remind and instruct the Building Supervisors to be extra careful, making sure that cheating is prevented, that cellphones would not be used by anyone, both examinees and room watchers, and that all test questionnaires and answer sheets are accounted for. Sometimes, I emphasize to the Building Supervisors that we do not want our Region to be tarnished with the legacy of having one examination anomaly, much less more than that.” (Key Informant D)</p> <p>“I remind the Room Watchers to properly fill-out their respective forms and distribute</p>	<p><i>Reminding of Exam Procedures to Prevent Cheating</i></p>	<p>Integrity of examinations is preserved by how</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>accordingly their ID/AS sets and Test Questionnaires. Ultimately, I just use or apply the procedures mandated by the Central Office when it comes to the conduct of the licensure examination... I usually remind and give proper instructions to the examination personnel prior to the start of the examination proper. I instruct Floor Supervisors to remind their room watchers that examinees should use ballpen in writing and pencil in shading.” (Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Cheating</i></p>	<p>instructions are provided to accord with rules.</p>	
<p>“On our part in the Examination Section, we also have other reports to collect, which is why we specified which forms should not be fastened in the Conduct Folder but need to just be inserted within. We need these other reports also.” (Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Reminding of Exam Procedures to Prevent Cheating</i></p>	<p>Rule consistency requires organizing information.</p>	
<p>“I tell my Floor Supervisors to surrender their cellphones before the start of the examination because we want to avoid the possibility of them taking pictures of unused test questionnaires. They might leak the questions, which will compromise the integrity of our examinations. Especially the room watchers, we do not want them to take photos of anything, that includes not only the test questionnaires but also the examinees’ faces and their names. We are trying to maintain the examinees’ data privacy as well as the security of administering the licensure examinations.”</p>	<p><i>Removing Materials that Compromise Exam Integrity</i></p>	<p>Preserving examination integrity means rule neutrality.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>(Key Informant C) “If there are examinees that brought their review materials, we usually confiscate them. We return those materials only at the end of the entire examination. And then, I also make sure that the examinees’ personal belongings are placed inside their bags. All their bags are placed in one place inside the examination room, either in front or at the side of the room.”</p>	<p><i>Removing Materials that Compromise Exam Integrity</i></p>	<p>Order is maintained by regulating materials in the test environment.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant B) “Pinapa-kolekta sa akin ni Floor Supervisor kung may sobrang Test Booklets, kapag may mga absent na examinee. (<i>The Floor Supervisor instructs me to collect excess Test Booklets, if there are absent examinees.</i>”</p>	<p><i>Removing Materials that Compromise Exam Integrity</i></p>	<p>Rule effectivity entails preventing misuse of examination materials.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant G) “Magkakandarapa si Floor Supervisor kung wala siyang Supply Aide. Magagahol siya sa oras gawin lahat, pag-pack, pagbibilang, maiksi lang naman ang oras sa pagitan ng mga subject. (<i>The Floor Supervisor would find things hard without a Supply Aide. He/she will have a hard time doing everything, counting, packing, since time is too limited between subjects.</i>)”</p>	<p><i>Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency</i></p>	<p>They preserve the consistency of information as required by the rules.</p>	
<p>(Key Informant G) “Ang ginagawa ko po talaga ay mag-assist sa Floor Supervisor, sundin ang instructions niya gaya ng pagbigay ng brown envelopes sa bawat room, pagkuha ng sapat na supplies para sa buong araw doon sa</p>	<p><i>Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency</i></p>	<p>They preserve rules by following authority and instruction.</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>Supply Officer. (<i>What I really do is to assist the Floor Supervisor, follow his/her instructions such as handing out brown envelopes to each room, getting ample examination supplies for the day from the Supply Officer.</i>)” (Key Informant G)</p>			
<p>“I make sure to accompany the Supply Officer to the Office to turn-over the answer sheets and the test booklets. I usually sit near the packages and boxes so that I could easily defend the materials in case there are attempts to steal or damage them. The goal is to bring everything to the Office in one piece, without damages. Otherwise, the Supply Officer and I would be held accountable.” (Key Informant H)</p>	<p>Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency</p>	<p>They preserve the integrity of the materials as evidence of rule implementation.</p>	
<p>“Usually, tinutulungan naman ako ng Security Officer to secure the area, na kami lang ang may access sa mga gagamiting supplies, kagaya ng test booklets, answer sheets, hindi yan pupwedeng makita o mahawakan lang ng kahit sino. (<i>Usually, I am assisted by the Security Officer to secure the area in which we have exclusive access to the supplies to be used, such as test booklets and answer sheets. These cannot be seen nor touched by just anyone.</i>)” (Key Informant F)</p>	<p>Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency</p>	<p>They preserve rules by restricting access to examination materials.</p>	
<p>“The reporting actually helps me see early on kung ilang actual examinees meron ang</p>	<p>Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency</p>	<p>Cooperation and consistency preserve</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>bawat Floor Supervisor ko (<i>if how many actual examinees does each of my Floor Supervisors have</i>). All of those numbers, I simply add them up and then, ayan, may total number na ako for my building (<i>there it is, I have a total for my building</i>).” (Key Informant C)</p>		<p>rule integrity.</p>	
<p>“(But) at all times, we should wear our respective badges. The badge identifies us, whether yung naka-suot (<i>the bearer</i>) is the Building Supervisor, a Floor Supervisor, a Room Watcher, etc. It signifies that you are an authorized person who can go around and look at what is going on.” (Key Informant C)</p>	<p><i>Respective Badges are Worn</i></p>	<p>Identity symbolizes authority.</p>	<p>(5) RULE AUTHORITY</p>
<p>“It is important that Security Officer assigned should report for duty in the exam site wearing their official uniform. It gives others the impression that a uniformed officer is present and ready to defend the integrity of the licensure examinations being administered, no matter what.” (Key Informant H)</p>	<p><i>Respective Badges are Worn</i></p>	<p>Exercising authority protects society.</p>	
<p>If the Room Watchers cannot personally resolve their concerns or the concerns of the examinees, they usually turn to the Floor Supervisor to ask for help. Kaya importanteng nakikita ang FS ng kanyang mga room watchers. (<i>That’s why it is essential that the FS is visible to his/her room watchers.</i>) (Key Informant B)</p>	<p><i>Referring Issues to Higher Authority</i></p>	<p>Authority of rules demands visibility.</p>	
<p>“If we do not know the solution to any</p>	<p><i>Referring Issues to Higher</i></p>	<p>Authority acknowledges</p>	

EXCERPTS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES	ANALYSIS	REPRODUCTION OF THE RULE REGIME
<p>problem, we refer the matter to our Floor Supervisor.” (Key Informant A) “Since I am in-charge of assigning proctors to each room, I go to the school assignment very early on the day (or first day for multiple day exams). Upon my arrival, I prioritize the Room Watchers/Proctors to sign their attendance record sheets first. I require them to present to me their Certificate of Assignment and any valid ID for identity verification, before I assign them their room number. Once they have a room number, I instruct them to get their room watcher’s kit from the Supply Officer and then to immediately proceed to their assigned rooms. Once I am able to assign at least 1 room watcher per room, I proceed to assigning them with their partners.” (Key Informant E)</p>	<p><i>Authority</i></p> <p><i>Recording of Accountable Persons is Ensured</i></p>	<p>limitation of rule knowledge.</p> <p>The exercise of rule authority is a priority.</p>	

Ensuring Plausibility in the Findings

Plausibility is defined as a technique for ensuring rigor in the conduct of qualitative research, which involves locating the truths and the realities in the study, adopting a critical approach, and acknowledging the complexities of managing “truths” in research (Savin-Baden & Major, 2010). It is also described by Fulton (2010) as the ability of a text to connect the reader to the subject’s world.

Saludadez (2021) highlighted the concept of *plausibility* as a mark of good, dependable qualitative communication research. In observance of this essential research principle, this Study ensures the plausibility of the research through *empirical plausibility* (i.e. evaluating whether the meaning makes sense to the participants of the study or to the researched community) and *theoretical plausibility* (i.e. ensuring the alignment of meaning with existing literatures or to the researcher community). In terms of empirical plausibility, the researcher consulted with the officials of the Agency as well as the participants who have responded to the study, to determine whether the interpretations or findings are in accordance with the testimonies they have provided and to match emerging data themes with technical terms and definitions as established by the Agency. In terms of theoretical plausibility, the researcher related its findings to similarly-established research papers or journals to ensure alignment of what test administration or examination invigilation means in other related narratives.

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study presents in this chapter the communicative practices of assigned licensure examination personnel occupying various roles in licensure examinations, and how their communicative practices reproduce rule regime in the conduct and administration of licensure examinations. Findings were based on the following research questions:

1. What are the communicative practices of assigned personnel in the conduct and administration of licensure examinations?
2. How do their communicative practices reproduce rule regime in the context of licensure examinations?

Communicative Practices of Examination Personnel

A total of fifteen (15) communicative practices were identified per the Key Informant Interview (KII) of the eight (8) participants. These practices are discussed in detail below.

Roaming Around

Even before the start of the examination proper, the Floor Supervisor conducts physical and visual surveillance by thoroughly inspecting the rooms under his/her supervision, as detailed by Key Informant B:

“What I do is I usually roam around my area of responsibility to check if Room Watchers are following the mandated procedures in the conduct of the exam, and at the same time, to attend to queries and concerns if any. I listen first and then answer clearly, direct to the point.” (Key Informant B)

The practice of roaming around helps exam supervisors gather statistics on the examination and helps them fill-out their forms accurately.

“While the examination is on-going, I start accomplishing forms and reports to be given to the Building Supervisor so that we have synchronicity in terms of information about the rooms I supervise. I understand that BS also needs my data as I am under his supervision. I also inspect if the examinees were able to properly fill-out their ID sheets and properly detached the answer sheets from their ID sheet sets.” (Key Informant B)

Roaming around the lobby during the course of the examination enables visibility of the Floor Supervisor to the Room Watchers. This enables easier access to the Floor Supervisor in case the Room Watchers encounter a problem or any incident peculiar to the regular course of examination administration.

“By roaming around, I make my presence felt, not only to the room watchers but also to the examinees. If the examinees feel inconvenient or have any concerns in their rooms, they may approach or inform the Floor Supervisor.” (Key Informant B)

Like the Floor Supervisor, the Building Supervisor already conducts physical and visual surveillance as soon as he/she arrives in his/her area of responsibility. The Building Supervisor inspects all rooms and floors in the building, and coordinates with each Floor Supervisor in case of any concerns or problems to be addressed, as explained by Key Informant C.

“Upon arrival, I check or verify if the forms in my examination kit are complete, and if I have sufficient sealing tapes. I bring with me a stapler, staple wires, paper clips, paper fastener, and a paper puncher. I also get

*to know or familiarize my staff, who the floor supervisors that will report to me, who is my supply officer, and if the Security Officer is already in the premises. I do initial coordination with them for the conduct of the licensure examination. I roam around to inspect if the rooms are clean and well-ventilated. ... I really do a regular room-to-room visit to check the examinees, the room watchers, and especially the floor supervisors before and during the examination. Now, once the examination is on-going, I begin to fill out my Building Supervisor's Report, the Delivery Receipts, and other forms in my kit. And then, dumi-diskarte ako (**I strategize**). I roam around, usually using my eye contact and hand signals, especially when checking the rooms. (Key Informant C)*

Upon arrival, the Exam Coordinator observes the overall situation in the testing site. He/she performs an inspection of the rooms, floors, and buildings where the examinations are being held.

"The first thing an Exam Coordinator does is to visit the testing site. If you are the Exam Coordinator, you really have to be there. You need to see what is going on, monitor how the assigned personnel manage things, and of course, to do decision-making when your intervention is necessary." (Key Informant D)

The Exam Coordinator also witnesses crucial events in the conduct of the licensure examination, such as opening of sealed boxes of Test Questionnaires, distribution of Test Questionnaires, and the submission of used TQs and answer sheets to the Regional Office after the end of the subject.

"I also do inspection everywhere in all of my coverage of testing sites, so that I can see how procedures are being implemented. I look at how they

open the TQ boxes, to whom did the Building Supervisors distribute the questionnaires to, what time they open, and how many TQ bundles have been distributed.” (Key Informant D)

As the examination progresses, the Exam Coordinator conducts surveillance in all the schools in his/her area of responsibility. Key Informant D sees this as the Exam Coordinator’s main task.

“I am usually authorized to use an official vehicle to roam around my area, from one school (testing site) to another, and before I leave each school, I make sure that I have inspected all essential areas. I also ask the Building Supervisor for confirmation on the number of rooms in his/her building.” (Key Informant D)

Roaming around within the building helps detect unwarranted movements not only by examinees but also by assigned examination personnel. This helps reduce unnecessary communication between room watchers and other examination personnel that could cause disturbance in the testing site. It is also helpful in ensuring that no unauthorized individuals are within the testing site premises and in preventing the occurrence of incidents that might disrupt the conduct of examinations.

The Security Officer immediately performs surveillance activities upon arrival in his/her assigned area of responsibility.

“I usually arrive first at the testing site at around 5:00 a.m. and I initially do random checking around the area, and to be ready to assist whenever needed. Then I accompany the SO (Supply Officer) to get the Test Questionnaire from the Office. When we return to the testing site, I would wait for the opening of the TQ box upon declaration by the BS (Building

Supervisor) and then I do my rounds again to inspect for any hidden cheating materials or codigos. I do this at multiple times in a day for the whole duration of the examination. If ever I am able to observe any unusual occurrences, I immediately report it to the assigned BS.” (Key Informant H)

Prior to the start of the subject in a licensure examination, the Security Officer escorts the Supply Officer to and from the Office to retrieve the boxes of Test Questionnaires to be used. Once the Test Questionnaires are distributed, the Security Officer also inspects the Floor Supervisors as they deliver their Test Questionnaires to their assigned testing rooms.

Per Key Informant H, the Security Officer is not supposed to stay still, sitting down, and should pay close attention to any action happening in the duration of the examination.

“I have to roam around to observe people, to pay attention to situations, to ensure that the testing area is peaceful and silent enough so as not to disturb the examinees as they take their test. This is why I walk gently, silently like a cat while I observe the surroundings. I also use hand signals to get the attention of anyone in the area.” (Key Informant H)

In the duration of each subject of the licensure examination, room watchers are tasked to monitor the examinees. This includes watching out for their behavior, body movements, facial expressions, and other gestures.

*“Usually ang ginagawa namin (**What we do usually is**), one proctor stays at the front and the other at the back, roaming around the room to assist examinees in case they need to ask questions or if they have*

clarifications to raise, and of course to oversee possible acts of cheating.”

(Key Informant A)

During the progress of the examination proper, the Attendance Supervisor may opt to conduct an inspection of each room to ensure that all room watchers who signed in the Attendance Record sheets have indeed reported to their proper room assignment and are rendering actual service.

“I make eye contact and hand signals especially when I roam the area to visit the assigned rooms of the proctors. I also utilize the time to visit each room and check if there are proctors who lacked signatures in the Attendance Record sheets and Payroll sheets. I wear my badge as Attendance Supervisor whenever I do my rounds for each room, so they would recognize me.” (Key Informant E)

As the last subject of the entire examination period is on-going, the Attendance Supervisor is expected to receive the examination allowances from the Disbursing Officer. Upon receipt of the examination allowances, the Attendance Supervisor will be held responsible in the distribution of examination allowances to all exam personnel before the end of the examination, as detailed below by Key Informant E.

“While the last subject is in progress on the last day of the examination, I personally hand-out the honoraria to each examination personnel. Then, I make sure to ask a copy of the Floor Supervisor’s Attendance Report which will be attached to the attendance and payroll sheets and submitted to the Disbursing Officer at the end of my duty as Attendance Supervisor. I make sure that the honoraria had been properly handed-out to the appropriate person.” (Key Informant E)

After payment, the Attendance Supervisor collects the badges from all Room Watchers and other examination staff, and submits all badges to the Supply Officer.

Resolving Issues

In cases where the Building Supervisor reports an issue or concern with his/her area of responsibility, the Exam Coordinator steps in to resolve the problem.

“I assist the exam personnel kapag hindi na nila kaya sa level nila (if they cannot solve problems in their own level). The key word is to communicate with the involved parties. For instance, if there is a lacking copy of Test Questionnaire in a bundle, I would normally call the Regional Office to ask for a buffer copy, or to verify kung bakit kulang (why there is a deficiency). If may sobrang TQ (if there is an excess TQ), I let them use any excess. But I tell them to write any incident on their reports, especially for the Building Supervisor, Floor Supervisor, and Room Watchers.” (Key Informant D)

The Exam Coordinator does not utilize any coordinator-specific reports or forms during the conduct of the examination. Per Key Informant D, he/she only signs the report of the Building Supervisor, noting the details stated in the report.

“We do not really accomplish any forms on our part; we are more of an observer of events, we oversee. We also take note of significant events that happened. Now, if we think we are done with our job on the field, we can even go back to the Regional Office to inspect the delivery of used TQs and answer sheets from each school.” (Key Informant D)

Retaining Professional Composure

Despite encountering issues, Key Informant B stressed out the importance of maintaining an open communication to the room watchers and even to the examinees when necessary.

“I just remain calm, alert, and attentive when conflicts or problems arise. I just make myself available and reliable in whatever circumstances that may occur. What matters is as a Floor Supervisor, you really have to maintain an open communication.” (Key Informant B)

Being a person of authority, the Building Supervisor often experiences challenging situations while managing the conduct of examinations in his/her area of responsibility. By going around the entire building and being visible to other authorized persons under his/her supervision, it enables the Building Supervisor to witness incidents, both good and bad, that define how the licensure examination proceeds as administered.

*“Sometimes, I express my frustration when I see something that goes ‘off’. But, human as we are, I treat these as normal behaviors. I have to let it out a little in order for me to release the tension. When you catch them doing something wrong, you also exercise your own judgment on how to deal with the situation properly. In resolving problems or conflicts during the licensure examination, I evaluate the situation and information collected, and then I relay the same properly to the exam coordinator and discuss the possible solutions. It is really a challenging job, because sometimes you not only manage the building, you also need to manage your patience, your temper, your facial expressions, including the words and instructions you tell other people. Sa’yo lahat kasi, eh. **(Everything***

is yours.) The responsibility, the accountability, and even the blame.”

(Key Informant C)

The Security Officer provides overall assistance to the Building Supervisor, the Floor Supervisors, and the Room Watchers in ensuring security, peace, and order within their respective areas of responsibility. He/she provides the necessary intervention to maintain the ideal environment of the testing site.

“When I call people’s attention, I always talk in a nice way. I control the tone of my voice; I do not talk or act aggressively because it could worsen the situation. I try to remain calm; I always base my explanations to the rules and regulations implemented by the Office in its examinations. For example, if an examinee is unruly or has a distraught behavior inside the room, I assist in calming the situation. I do not immediately treat it as a violation, because it is quite normal for examinees to get stressed while under pressure. But I assist in de-escalating.” (Key Informant H)

Reviewing Exam Statistics

As examinees arrive in their assigned rooms, the Room Watcher reviews the names and the number of examinees in his/her room assignment.

“Inside the examination room, first things first, I delegate with my co-proctor of the certain tasks we do during the conduct of the exam. Upon entering my room assignment, I check the list of examinees posted outside the number of examinees we have in that room. We check if the chairs are complete and properly arranged according to the seat plan, and we re-arrange if not. We open windows for proper ventilation, switch on lights and electric fans. We also check our kit for completeness, we

get the list of examination program and write the program on the board (e.g. blackboard or whiteboard). Then we get the Room Watcher's Report and Identification/Answer Sheet sets. We count the ID/AS sets and record it in the Room Watcher's Report. Then, upon arrival of the examinees, I check their names in the list of examinees and ascertain their identities vis-à-vis their Notice of Admission (NOA) and the Seat Plan. When done, I lead them to their assigned seat following the seat plan arrangement. If the number of examinees assigned in the room is now complete, I will have the attendance checking to ensure if they are properly seated according to their assigned seat number. And once they are in their assigned seat number, we distribute their ID sheet (Identification Sheet) & Answer Sheet set.” (Key Informant A)

The Floor Supervisor has the responsibility to properly distribute the test questionnaires to each room under his/her area of responsibility.

“Once the Building Supervisor instructs the distribution of the test questionnaires, we count and check if the number of test booklets/questionnaires tally with the number indicated in the Floor Supervisor's Distribution and Accountability Form. If the numbers tally, then I distribute the test questionnaires to the room watchers in each room, with the help of my Supply Aide. In the event that the room watchers failed to distribute the test questionnaires properly, meaning if they gave Set A to an examinee that should have been given Set B or vice-versa, we retain the set of the first subject to avoid confusion on the part of the examinee and to easily verify and consolidate statistics.” (Key Informant B)

Upon the start of the first subject of the examination schedule, the Building Supervisor is tasked to report the examinee statistics as soon as possible to the Exam Coordinator.

*“By 8:00 a.m., we are quite pressured to report our statistics to the Exam Coordinator. Kailangan niya kasi yung data (**he/she needs the data**) to inform the Central Office about how many examinees were on our list, how many were absent, and how many examinees actually took the examination. By 8:15 a.m., we should have been able to report the statistics in a Messenger group chat initiated para diyan (**for that purpose**). This is why I ask data from my floor supervisors ASAP, and compare their numbers with each room they covered para may check-and-balance (**so there would be check-and-balance**).” (Key Informant C)*

Being consistent in reporting examinee statistics to the Exam Coordinator is vital in monitoring the physical count of examinees in a testing site. This also helps establish how many test questionnaires were used and how many answer sheets have to be accounted for at the end of each subject.

*“The reporting actually helps me see early on kung ilang actual examinees meron ang bawat Floor Supervisor ko (**if how many actual examinees does each of my Floor Supervisors have**). All of those numbers, I simply add them up and then, ayan, may total number na ako for my building (**there it is, I have a total for my building**). Then, I just see to it that every time we submit answer sheets and test questionnaires to the Office, the total number that I have is equal to the number of examinees actually present in my area.” (Key Informant C)*

When the Exam Coordinator inspects each testing site, he/she usually asks for the Building Supervisor's statistics on the actual number of examinees as well as the number of absentees in each venue.

"We have a group chat for statistics reporting in Messenger. But because we are also being pushed by Central Office to submit our stats ASAP, ni-reremind ko na lang lahat ng mga Building Supervisor na dalian ang submission (I remind all Building Supervisors to expedite the submission) in the group chat. I also ask the Building Supervisor for confirmation on the number of rooms in his/her building." (Key Informant D)

Key Informant D also revealed that after the examination, the Regional Director prepares a Report of Conduct of Examination to be submitted to the Central Office upon conclusion of the scheduled examination. The Exam Coordinator is responsible in maintaining a ready list of statistics for all testing sites under his/her area of responsibility. This helps organize information as needed for reporting the overall examination conduct to the Central Office.

Re-Checking Documents

When examinees finish answering questions on a particular subject, they submit their used Test Questionnaires and Answer Sheets to the Room Watcher. Room watchers affix their signature on the examinee's Notice of Admission and count the submitted Test Questionnaires and Answer Sheets.

"At the end of every subject, dapat tally ang number of examinees at saka yung number ng test booklets at answer sheets. Kapag may discrepancy, o kaya kung kulang yung nai-submit sa amin na test booklet o answer sheet, kami ang accountable, hahanapin pa namin yung

examinee para lang ma-secure na maisasauli yung nawawalang papeles. (the number of examinees and the number of test booklets and answer sheets should tally equally. If there are any discrepancies, of if there are missing pieces in the submissions, we are held accountable, we need to locate the examinee just to ensure that the missing papers are returned.)” (Key Informant A)

Once the room watchers collected the used test questionnaires and answer sheets, they submit these to their Floor Supervisor who in turn re-counts the number of test booklets and answer sheets they submitted. Answer sheets are placed in a long brown envelope, while the test questionnaires are bundled together.

“At the last subject of the entire examination, we collate all the ID sheets of the examinees, place these in the long brown envelope provided, and submit the envelope to the Floor Supervisor. We make sure that the number of ID sheets is equal to the number of examinees who actually took the examination in our room assignment.” (Key Informant A)

The Floor Supervisor re-checks the documents that the Room Watchers submitted, such as the used Test Questionnaires and Answer Sheets.

“The room watchers will submit to the Floor Supervisor a brown envelope containing the Answer Sheets, as well as the bundle of used test questionnaires. With the help of the Supply Aide, we count the number of answer sheets that we received and the number of test questionnaires from each room. We always make sure that the count tallies with the number of examinees present and the total indicated/label on the brown envelope.” (Key Informant B)

On the other hand, the Attendance Supervisor also practices the re-checking of documents in his/her custody, verifying if all assigned room watchers and exam personnel were able to completely fill-out the attendance record sheets and the general payroll sheets.

“Once I am done assigning the proctors in their rooms, I make sure next that the other examination personnel are able to sign in the attendance sheets and payroll sheets. Then I re-check every page of the attendance and payroll sheets to ensure that all fields that require signing have signatures.” (Key Informant E)

Retrieval Procedure is Secured

The Supply Officer is in-charge of the retrieval and transport of examination materials from the regulatory Body to the testing site.

“As Supply Officer, I have to report to the Agency Office on the first day of the examination by 4:00 a.m. I am assigned in loading the examination supplies and other examination materials to the assigned vehicle. I also make sure that the said materials are transported ahead of time to the testing site. After I unload the materials containing the examination kits, I have to travel back to the Agency to get the test questionnaire booklets. Upon arrival in the testing site, I facilitate the un-boxing of the test questionnaires fifteen (15) minutes before the start of the subject, with the go-signal of the Building Supervisor.” (Key Informant F)

The Supply Officer is also tasked to monitor the sufficiency of supplies and examination materials in the testing site. Among the resources that he needs to manage include wrapping papers, mother envelopes, packaging tapes, and cutters.

This helps secure that all personnel who will submit documents can properly facilitate their submissions of used examination paraphernalia.

“I also distribute mother envelopes and the brown envelopes for the ID sheets and answer sheets to the Floor Supervisors. I see to it that all Floor Supervisors have enough so that they can secure their submissions as well.” (Key Informant F)

The Supply Officer often seeks the help of Supply Aides, particularly male ones, when retrieving the boxes of Test Questionnaires from the Office for deployment in their respective testing sites.

*“Pinapa-tawag kami minsan ng Supply Officer, lalo na kapag mabibigat o mararami yung mga dadalhing boxes. Kadalasan, mga lalaki po ang pinupull-out para tumulong. Nakakahiya naman po kapag babae, mahirap naman silang obligahin tumulong magbuhat ng mga mabibigat na kahon. **(The Supply Officer often summons us to help, especially if there are many, heavy boxes to carry. Usually, male supply aides are being called to help. It is quite shameful if females would be obliged to carry heavy boxes.)**” (Key Informant G)*

The Building Supervisor is in-charge of the opening of sealed boxes containing the Test Questionnaires to be used for each examination subject to be administered. These boxes are usually opened fifteen (15) minutes prior the start of the examination subjects, to give Floor Supervisors and their respective Supply Aides ample time to proceed to their areas of responsibility and distribute the Test Questionnaire bundles to each room.

“I am assisted by the Supply Officer in handing out the Test Questionnaire bundles after opening the boxes, and I call each Floor

*Supervisor to come to me to receive the bundles. For example, Floor Supervisor assigned for rooms 1 to 7 will approach me to receive the TQs, then FS hands the test booklets to the Supply Aide lalo na kung maramihan (**especially if these are voluminous**), then they go. And then the next FS assigned for rooms 8 to 14 will approach me, receive the TQs and then disperse to their room coverage after, so on and so forth, until I distribute all bundles to all Floor Supervisors. After every subject, I wrap the TQs including all Answer Sheets as consolidated for turn-over to the Agency.” (Key Informant C)*

Per Key Informant C, at the end of every subject, all Floor Supervisors submit the mother envelope packages of examinee answer sheets to the Building Supervisor, along with all the bundles of used Test Questionnaires usually carried by the Supply Aide. Key Informant B also described the procedures on how the Floor Supervisor manages all examination materials and paraphernalia submitted by the Room Watchers.

“After counting the test questionnaires and answer sheets, we seal with a packing tape the brown envelopes and sign across the sealing tapes on the flaps of the envelopes.” (Key Informant B)

Prior to the actual turn-over of used test questionnaires and answer sheets to the Building Supervisor, the Floor Supervisor compiles all brown envelopes submitted by the Room Watchers containing the answer sheets in their respective rooms. Assisted by the Supply Aide, the Floor Supervisor packs and seals all brown envelopes in one package called the “Mother Envelope”. It is a wrapping paper used to pack the compiled brown envelopes containing the answer sheets. The mother envelope for answer sheets is sealed and signed on all sealed corners using a

permanent marker, prior to submission to the Building Supervisor. Figure 2 below shows a sample from the Examination Section of how each mother envelope should be properly labelled by the Floor Supervisor prior to submission to the Building Supervisor.

Figure 2.

Answer Sheets Mother Envelope Labelling sample (Source: Key Informant B)

NAME OF EXAM	DATE OF EXAM
NAME OF SUBJECT	
AS = ##	
NAME OF TESTING SITE	NUMBER OF ROOMS
LOCATION OF TEST SITE	NUMBER OF ENVELOPES

While the examination is in progress for the last subject, the Floor Supervisor collects and counts the examinees' ID sheets, ensuring that the number tallies with the actual number of examinees who took the examination, and that each ID sheet is properly filled-out by the examinees, as inspected, counted, and checked by the room watchers. Similar to the answer sheets, ID sheets are placed in brown envelopes by the room watchers and compiled by the Floor Supervisors into a sealed and signed mother envelope, submitted to the Building Supervisor before the end of the examination. Figure 3 below shows a sample of how ID sheet mother envelopes are labelled.

Figure 3.

ID Sheets Mother Envelope Labelling sample (Source: Key Informant B)

Notable in the labelling of the packages that Floor Supervisors submit to their Building Supervisors are important details of the licensure examination, such as the name and date of the examination, the subject label for the answer sheets (or ID sheets), the total number of sheets submitted, the name of the school where the examination was held, the city and region of the testing location, the number of rooms covered by the Floor Supervisor, and the number of envelopes contained inside the mother envelope package. These details help facilitate the accuracy of examination statistics maintained by the Floor Supervisor and the Building Supervisor in their areas of responsibility.

As per Key Informant B, at the end of the entire examination, all mother envelopes of answer sheets and ID sheets, and all used Test Questionnaires in the last subject, must be endorsed by the Floor Supervisor to the Building Supervisor for consolidation. Overall, the Floor Supervisor is responsible in managing all materials utilized in the course of the examination and in ensuring that all used examination paraphernalia under his/her area of responsibility are accounted for and turned over to the Building Supervisor.

Per Key Informant F, the Supply Officer collects all used Test Questionnaire bundles, checks whether the bundle in each room has been turned over, and then places all bundles back to the Test Questionnaire boxes. Once all Test

Questionnaire bundles have been returned, the Building Supervisor places inside the TQ box the unused/excess Test Questionnaires along with the Floor Supervisors' Test Questions Distribution & Accountability Form. The Supply Officer seals the TQ box using a packaging tape, to be signed by the Building Supervisor in its taped edges.

Per Key Informant C, the Building Supervisor compiles all the mother envelope packages of examinee answer sheets submitted by all Floor Supervisors in his/her area of responsibility into one overall package. All the packages are wrapped inside a sheet of brown wrapping paper, folded properly in all corners so as not to distort any materials contained inside the mother envelopes of the Floor Supervisors. The overall package containing all mother envelopes of examinee answer sheets is then sealed and signed by the Building Supervisor on all corners using a permanent marker, prior to submission to the Regional Office. Figure 4 below shows a sample from the Examination Section of how each overall package of the Building Supervisor should be properly labelled prior to submission to the Examination Section.

Figure 4.

Label on the Overall Packaging of the Answer Sheets (Source: Key Informant C)

Similarly, the ID sheets submitted by Floor Supervisors during the administration of the last examination subject are packed in one overall package by

the Building Supervisor, to be submitted to the Regional Office at the end of the entire examination. Figure 5 below shows a sample of how the overall packaging for ID sheets is labelled properly.

Figure 5.

Label on the Overall Packaging of the ID Sheets (Source: Key Informant C)

Per Key Informant C, the total number indicated in the label of the Building Supervisor should tally with the total number of ID/AS sets submitted by all Floor Supervisors. Another notable difference is that the labelling indicates the number of all the rooms supervised by the Building Supervisor and the number of packages (mother envelopes) submitted by the Floor Supervisors contained inside. These overall packages, along with the TQ sealed boxes, are submitted to the Regional Office by the Supply Officer, accompanied by the Security Officer in an official vehicle, for proper turn-over and accountability.

By the end of each examination subject, the Supply Officer helps the Building Supervisor in packing all used Test Questionnaires into the sealed boxes, as well as in the preparation of the Overall Packages of all answer sheets, as well as ID sheets during the last subject. The Supply Officer also assists the Building Supervisor in ensuring that Test Questionnaires and Answer Sheets have been properly and completely endorsed by all Floor Supervisors.

“Once nakapag-submit na lahat ng Floor Supervisors, tinutulungan ko si Building Supervisor mag-balot ng overall packaging. Pati nasa sealing ng

used TQs. Kapag nai-pack na lahat, babalik na ako sa opisina, escorted ako ni Security Officer, saka ko ire-retrieve yung Test Questionnaire para sa susunod na subject ng araw na iyon. (Once all Floor Supervisors have submitted, I assist the Building Supervisor in the over-all packaging, including the sealing of used TQs. Once everything has been packed, I would return to the Office, as escorted by the Security Officer, and then I would retrieve the Test Questionnaire for the next subject of the examination day.)”

(Key Informant F)

Reprimanding Personnel

There are cases in which assigned personnel violate the examination rules. For instance, the Floor Supervisor monitors the dress code or attire observed by the room watchers assigned under his/her area of responsibility, as per Key Informant B.

“In fact, I also roam around to inspect if the room watchers observe wearing the proper attire. If the FS sees that they are not wearing proper attire, we reprimand them.” (Key Informant B)

The Building Supervisor also exercises his/her authority in reprimanding room watchers who are caught sleeping or not performing their tasks properly.

*“Sometimes, I stand by the doors watching the examinees and even the room watchers for unusual movements. I reprimand the watchers discreetly if I catch them sleeping. And then I would walk slowly around in each floor under my area, and sometimes I would notice the room watchers paying attention to me. Occasionally, other exam personnel would say nga maisog an akon nawong (**that I have an angry face**), but I do not deny that.” (Key Informant C)*

Reporting of Incidents & Violations

One of the requirements of the Room Watcher is the accomplishment of various forms or reports to be submitted to their assigned Floor Supervisor. In the images below are samples of the forms that room watchers accomplish in the course of the licensure examination. Figure 6 below shows a sample of the Room Watcher's Report, which describes in detail the setup within their room assignment. This form is utilized throughout the entire examination, signed by the room watchers, for submission to the Floor Supervisor for further review.

*“The Room Watcher’s Report details the counting of the allocated Test Questionnaires in our room vis-à-vis the examinees listed in the room and the actual number of examinees present here. Then we declare the names of the absent examinees as well as in which seat number they were assigned, we submit these details to the FS, and if any, we remove them from the counting of actual examinees present. Dito rin namin ini-indicate kung may incidents ng cheating o kaya kapag may examinee na nag-violate ng rules, yung hindi sumunod sa proper dress code o di kaya yung nag-cellphone. **(We also indicate here if there are cheating incidents or if there are any examinees who violated rules, those who did not follow the proper dress code or those who use cellphones.)**” (Key Informant A)*

Figure 6.
Room Watcher's Report sample (Source: Key Informant A)

ROOM WATCHER'S REPORT			
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR:			
<input type="checkbox"/> ELEMENTARY <input type="checkbox"/> SECONDARY MAJOR:		REGIONAL OFFICE/TEST CENTER : DATE/S OF EXAMINATION : SCHOOL / BUILDING : ROOM / GROUP NUMBER :	
I. EXAMINEE IDENTIFICATION ANSWER SHEETS SETS ACCOUNTABILITY REPORT			
IDENTIFICATION / ANSWER SHEETS		SERIAL NUMBER/S	
	QUANTITY	FROM	TO
A. ID/AS SETS ALLOTTED			
B. ADDITIONAL SET/S REQUESTED			
C. TOTAL SET/S DISTRIBUTED			
D. EXTRA SET/S RETURNED			
II. NUMBER OF EXAMINEES			
PER LIST :	COMPLETE :	REMOVALS :	
ADDED TO THE LIST :	ABSENT :	PRACTICAL ONLY :	
TOTAL LISTED:	ABANDONED :	BOARD PASSER :	
	INCOMPLETE :	Others, please specify :	
A. NAME OF EXAMINEE/S WHO IS/ARE ABSENT	SEAT NO.	D. NAME OF REMOVAL EXAMINEE/S	SEAT NO.
1		1	
2		2	
3		3	
4		4	
5		5	
B. NAME OF EXAMINEE/S WHO ABANDONED	SEAT NO.	E. NAME OF PRACTICAL ONLY EXAMINEE/S	SEAT NO.
1		1	
2		2	
3		3	
4		4	
5		5	
C. NAME OF EXAMINEES WHO TOOK SOME SUBJECTS (INCOMPLETE)	SEAT NO.	F. NAME OF EXAMINEE/S WHO IS/ARE CIVIL ENGINEER/S OR X-RAY TECHNOLOGIST/S LICENSURE EXAM PASSER (Please specify Profession and License No.)	SEAT NO.
1		1	
2		2	
3		3	
4		4	
5		5	
III. DETAILED REPORTS			
A. MISHANDLING OF ANSWER SHEET (DANGLING ERROR)	NAME OF EXAMINEES	SEAT NO.	ACTION/S TAKEN
B. CHEATING / COLLUSION/S			
C. UNUSUAL INCIDENT/IRREGULARITIES			
IV. COMMENTS/RECOMMENDATIONS (For System Improvement of the Conduct of Exam)			

It is notable that the Room Watcher's Report provides the room watchers a space to which they can write their feedback, comments, or suggestions to improve the conduct of licensure examinations.

Aside from the Room Watcher's Report, the room watchers also accomplish the Seat Plan by having the examinees affix their signature below their pictures and names in the said form. Figure 7 below shows a sample of the Seat Plan. This is utilized to verify the identity of the examinees and subsequently avoid misrepresentation or impersonation in the licensure examinations.

Figure 7.
Seat Plan sample (Source: Key Informant A)

SEAT PLAN						
NAME OF EXAMINATION: L						
PLACE OF EXAMINATION:			SCHOOL/BUILDING: NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL /			
DATE OF EXAMINATION:			ROOM/GROUP NO.: 1			
INSTRUCTION: Room Watcher-1 shall pass around this form to the examinees while Room Watcher-2 will check and fill-up the REMARKS portion.						
	Signature:	Seat No. 4				
	Signature:	Seat No. 5				
	Signature:	Seat No. 6				
	Signature:	Seat No. 8				
	Signature:	Seat No. 7				
I/WE CERTIFY TO THE BEST OF MY/OUR KNOWLEDGE THAT THE ABOVE PICTURES OF EXAMINEES ARE ONE AND THE SAME PERSONS APPEARING ON THEIR NOTICES OF ADMISSION AND PERSONALLY TOOK THE LICENSURE EXAMINATION.						
Remarks:						
Day 1 - Room Watcher 1 _____ Signature over Printed Name			Day 1 - Room Watcher 2 _____ Signature over Printed Name			
Day 2 - Room Watcher 1 _____ Signature over Printed Name			Day 2 - Room Watcher 2 _____ Signature over Printed Name			
Day 3 - Room Watcher 1 _____ Signature over Printed Name			Day 3 - Room Watcher 2 _____ Signature over Printed Name			
Actual no. of Columns used:	1 ()	2 ()	3 ()	4 ()	5 ()	Others: _____
No. of Examinees Per Column:	[]	[] []	[] [] []	[] [] [] []	[] [] [] [] []	Others: _____

In addition to the Seat Plan, the room watchers also instruct the examinees to affix their signature right beside their seat number, one-by-one in the List of Examinees to confirm their attendance and room assignment. Figure 8 below shows a sample of the List of Examinees per room, provided in the kit of Room Watchers.

Figure 8.
List of Examinees sample (Source: Key Informant A)

Page 1

Licensure Examination for [REDACTED]
 September 2020

School : [REDACTED] Address: [REDACTED]
 Building : BASIC EDUCATION
 Floor : GROUND Rm/Grp No.: 1

Seat No.	Last Name	First Name	Middle Name	School Attended	Birthdate	APPLIC. NO.
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						
13						
14						
15						
16						
17						
18						
19						
20						
21						

REMINDERS:
 USE SAME NAME IN ALL EXAMINATION FORMS. IF THERE IS AN ERROR IN SPELLING, DATE OF BIRTH, SCHOOL NAME, OR APPLICATION NO. PLEASE REPORT TO THE APPLICATION DIV. BEFORE THE EXAMINATION OR KINDLY REQUEST YOUR ROOM WATCHERS TO CORRECT IT ON THE FIRST DAY OF EXAMINATION.

At the end of every subject, the room watchers record the actual time of submission of the examinees, and have them sign in the Examinees Record of Attendance (see Figure 9 below for sample), as proof of submission of their assigned Test Questionnaire and Answer Sheet.

Figure 9.
Examinees Record of Attendance sample (Source: Key Informant A)

		EXAMINEES RECORD OF ATTENDANCE																			
		Licensure Examination For:					School/Building:					Room/Group No.:									
SEAT NO.	NAME OF EXAMINEES (In Print)	1 st SUBJECT				2 nd SUBJECT				3 rd SUBJECT				4 th SUBJECT				5 th SUBJECT			
		DATE:				DATE:				DATE:				DATE:				DATE:			
		SIGNATURE	TIME	SET	NO. OF PAGES	SIGNATURE	TIME	SET	NO. OF PAGES	SIGNATURE	TIME	SET	NO. OF PAGES	SIGNATURE	TIME	SET	NO. OF PAGES	SIGNATURE	TIME	SET	NO. OF PAGES
1																					
2																					
3																					
4																					
5																					
6																					
7																					
8																					
9																					
10																					
11																					
12																					
13																					
14																					
15																					
16																					
17																					
18																					
19																					
20																					
21																					
22																					
23																					
24																					

IMPORTANT: This form must shall be accomplished by the examinees and roomwatchers. All examinees are required to SIGN, indicate the time he/she submitted the Test Questionnaire, the SET (A or B) received and used in the examination and the number of pages returned under the SUBJECT taken. For COMPLETE examination, the word 'ABANDONED' should be written by the Room Watcher opposite the name of the examinees, under the subject he/she FAILED to take. For REMOVAL examination, the examinee should write the word 'PASSED' after his/her signature, under the subject he/she previously passed.

The above basic forms are stapled together and submitted to the Floor Supervisor at the end of the last subject of the entire examination. These forms serve as their main communication mechanism to their Floor Supervisor to synchronize statistics of examinees and other relevant information regarding the examination conducted.

“At the end of the exam, we submit the Room Watcher’s Report, Seat Plan, and Examinees Record of Attendance, and then the FS checks whether we have properly accomplished all the forms, and then we tally if we have the same statistics and information.” (Key Informant A)

When room watchers receive their allocated Test Questionnaires, they also fill-out the Test Questionnaire Accountability Form as shown below in Figure 10. This form is used to determine the actual number of test booklets allocated and received.

Figure 10.

Test Questionnaire Accountability Form sample (Source: Key Informant A)

TEST BOOKLETS/TEST QUESTIONS SETS ACCOUNTABILITY FORM PER SUBJECT						
PART I						
CONFIDENTIAL PRINTING ROOM						
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR:			REGION:	CITY		
SUBJECT:			SCHOOL/BUILDING: NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL			
DATE OF EXAM:			ROOM: 12			
NO. OF TEST BOOKLET/TEST QUESTIONS SETS ALLOTTED			SERIAL NUMBERS (for Test Booklets only)			
16	SET A	8				
	SET B	8				
COUNTER:			CHECKER:			
PRINTED NAME & SIGNATURE			PRINTED NAME & SIGNATURE			
PART II						
RECEIPT OF TEST BOOKLETS / TEST QUESTIONS SETS						
1. NUMBER OF TB/TQ SETS RECEIVED -----			SET A	SET B	TOTAL	NO. OF PAGES SET A SET B
2. EXTRA/EXCESS TB/TQ SETS RETURNED (if any) -----						
3. ADDITIONAL TB/TQ SETS REQUESTED (if any) -----						
4. TOTAL NUMBER OF TB/TQ SETS DISTRIBUTED -----						
PRINTED NAME AND SIGNATURE OF:						
ROOM WATCHER/PROCTOR 1			ROOM WATCHER/PROCTOR 2			
PART III						
ROOM WATCHERS / PROCTORS' CERTIFICATION (END OF SUBJECT)						
This is to certify that as Room Watchers/Proctors of Room/Group No. _____ we COUNTED and RECEIVED a total of _____ USED TEST BOOKLETS/TEST QUESTIONS SETS from the examinees assigned in the room/group. They are found complete and intact.						
ROOM WATCHER/PROCTOR 1			ROOM WATCHER/PROCTOR 2			
Signature Over Printed Name OFFICE TELEPHONE NO.			Signature Over Printed Name OFFICE TELEPHONE NO.			

Upon receipt, room watchers distribute the Test Questionnaires to the examinees; examinees with assigned odd number seating receive Set “A” Questionnaires while those with assigned even number seating receive Set “B” Questionnaires. In case the room has absent examinees, the room watchers return the unused test booklets to the Floor Supervisor at once along with the said form for proper accounting, and so that excess test booklets may not be misused.

Just like room watchers, Floor Supervisors also utilize forms or reports to manage examination information. Upon accomplishment, the Floor Supervisor submits the forms to the Building Supervisor. Utilizing forms is a communication practice to inform the Building Supervisor of crucial information about the coverage of rooms as well as the room watchers being supervised.

The main form utilized by the Floor Supervisor is the Floor Supervisor’s Report, a sample of which can be seen in Figure 11a and Figure 11b below. This form is used to record the number of answer sheets actually utilized per room, as well as the number of examinees within the area of supervision of the Floor Supervisor. This form is also utilized to record any incident that deviates from the examination procedures, such as during cases of dangling of ID sheet and Answer Sheet sets between examinees, cheating incidents, mishandling of examination paraphernalia, and other incidents that are peculiar to the regular conduct of examinations. Floor Supervisors may also utilize the Floor Supervisor’s Report to submit their comments, suggestions, and recommendations that may be used to help improve the systems and procedures in place for the conduct of licensure examinations. Their comments, suggestions, and recommendations are forwarded through this report to the Building Supervisor before the end of the examination, and for further submission to the top management of the Agency for consideration.

Figure 11a.
 Floor Supervisor's Report sample (Page 1) (Source: Key Informant B)

	FLOOR SUPERVISOR'S REPORT
INSTRUCTION: This form shall be submitted to the Building Supervisor at the end of the examination with the Room Watcher's Reports, Examinees Record of Attendance and Seat Plan.	
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR: _____	REGIONAL OFFICE/TEST CENTER: _____
DATE/S OF EXAMINATION: _____	SCHOOL/BUILDING: _____

A. NUMBER OF ANSWER SHEETS PER SUBJECT													B. NUMBER OF EXAMINEES									
ROOM/ GROUP NOS.	SUBJECT												IN THE LIST	ADDED TO LIST	TOTAL LISTED	ABSENT	COMPLETE	REMOVALS	ABANDONED	INCOMPLETE	PRACTICAL ONLY	BOARD PASSER
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12										
16																						
17																						
18																						
19																						
TOTAL																						

C. INCIDENT REPORT DURING THE CONDUCT OF EXAMINATION

1. DANGLING CASES (One examinee used other answer sheet, vice versa)

Room No.	Name of Examinee/s	Seat No.	Date/Time	Subject	Brief Description of Case/Report

2. COLLUSION/CHEATING/CONFISCATION OF CODIGOS

Room No.	Name of Examinee/s	Seat No.	Date/Time	Subject	Brief Description of Case/Report

3. MISHANDLING OF IDENTIFICATION/ANSWER SHEETS (ID/AS) AND/OR TEST QUESTIONNAIRES

Room No.	Name of Examinee/s	Seat No.	Date/Time	Subject	Brief Description of Case/Report

4. OTHER INCIDENTS

Room No.	Name of Examinee/s	Seat No.	Date/Time	Subject	Brief Description of Case/Report

5. UNAUTHORIZED PERSON/S WHO VISITED OR FOUND IN YOUR AREA

Figure 11b.
Floor Supervisor's Report sample (Page 2) (Source: Key Informant B)

	FLOOR SUPERVISOR'S REPORT
---	----------------------------------

NAMES OF EXAMINEES WHO DID NOT TAKE THE EXAMINATION (ABSENT)		
SEAT NO.	NAME	ROOM/GROUP ASSIGNED

NAMES OF REMOVAL EXAMINEES (TAKING ONLY ONE OR TWO SUBJECTS)		
SEAT NO.	NAME	ROOM/GROUP ASSIGNED

NAMES OF EXAMINEES ADDED TO THE LIST		
SEAT NO.	NAME	ROOM/GROUP ASSIGNED

NAMES OF EXAMINEES WHO TOOK SOME SUBJECTS BUT DID NOT CONTINUE TAKING THE EXAMINATION (ABANDONED)		
SEAT NO.	NAME	ROOM/GROUP ASSIGNED

NAMES OF EXAMINEES TAKING PRACTICAL EXAM ONLY		
SEAT NO.	NAME	ROOM/GROUP ASSIGNED

NAMES OF BOARD PASSER EXAMINEES				
SEAT NO.	ROOM GROUP	NAME	Profession	License No.

REMARKS: (COMMENTS/RECOMMENDATION/OBSERVATIONS OR SUGGESTIONS THAT CAN HELP IMPROVE THE SYSTEMS AND PROCEDURES IN THE CONDUCT OF LICENSURE EXAMINATIONS)

CERTIFIED CORRECT:

PRINTED NAME & SIGNATURE
FLOOR SUPERVISOR

NOTED BY:

PRINTED NAME & SIGNATURE
BUILDING SUPERVISOR

To properly ensure accountability in handling examination paraphernalia, the Floor Supervisor utilizes the Floor Supervisor's Test Question Distribution & Accountability Form, as seen in Figure 13a and Figure 13b below.

Figure 13a.

Floor Supervisor's Test Questions Distribution & Accountability Form sample (Page 1) (Source: Key Informant B)

	FLOOR SUPERVISOR'S TEST QUESTIONS DISTRIBUTION & ACCOUNTABILITY FORM
---	---

LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR: _____ SCHOOL: _____
 SUBJECT: _____ BUILDING: _____
 DATE: _____ ROOM/GROUPS: **1-5**

FLOOR SUPERVISOR _____

COUNTER: _____

 PRINTED NAME & SIGNATURE

CHECKER: _____

 PRINTED NAME & SIGNATURE

TO BE ACCOMPLISHED BY CPR SUPERVISOR		TO BE ACCOMPLISHED BY FLOOR SUPERVISOR					
ROOM/ GROUP NO.	ACTUAL NUMBER ALLOTTED	ACTUAL NUMBER RECEIVED	ADDITIONAL REQUESTED (if any)	EXCESS RETURNED (if any)	TOTAL NUMBER DISTRIBUTED	NO. OF SETS W/ MISSING PAGES	REMARKS
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
TOTAL	36						

1. NO. OF SETS REQUESTED FROM BUILDING SUPERVISOR: SET A _____ SET B _____

2. NO. OF SETS RETURNED TO BUILDING SUPERVISOR: SET A _____ SET B _____

CERTIFIED CORRECT:
 FLOOR SUPERVISOR

 Signature over Printed Name

BUILDING SUPERVISOR

 Signature over Printed Name

Figure 14b.

List of Examinees with Discrepancies Form sample (Page 2) (Source: Key Informant B)

	LIST OF EXAMINEES WITH DISCREPANCIES IN NAME, DATE OF BIRTH & SCHOOL GRADUATED FROM FOR VERIFICATION AND CORRECTION
--	--

III. CORRECTION ON SCHOOL GRADUATED FROM

Room No.	NAME OF EXAMINEE	FROM	TO	SIGNATURE
		SCHOOL GRADUATE FROM	SCHOOL GRADUATE FROM	

CERTIFIED CORRECT:			
DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3	DAY 4
ROOM WATCHER – 1	ROOM WATCHER – 1	ROOM WATCHER – 1	ROOM WATCHER – 1
NAME:	NAME:	NAME:	NAME:
SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:
OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:
CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:
ROOM WATCHER – 2	ROOM WATCHER – 2	ROOM WATCHER – 2	ROOM WATCHER – 2
NAME:	NAME:	NAME:	NAME:
SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:
OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:
CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:

NOTED BY:

 FLOOR SUPERVISOR
Signature Over Printed Name

 BUILDING SUPERVISOR
Signature Over Printed Name

According to Key Informant B, before the end of the examination, the Floor Supervisor collects and compiles the Room Watcher’s Reports per room in his/her area of responsibility. He/she signs in each Room Watcher’s Report to validate the information indicated by the room watchers in their report. Subsequently, the Floor Supervisors submit all collated Room Watcher’s Reports to their Building Supervisor.

Per Key Informant C, the Building Supervisor also has a specific report and set of forms to fill-out and manage during the entire conduct of the licensure

examination, comparable to the reports and forms accomplished by the Room Watchers and the Floor Supervisors.

*“The Building Supervisor’s documents are collated, filed and fastened in a green expanding folder labelled as “Conduct of Examination Folder”. Aside from the Building Supervisor’s reports and forms, he/she also compiles all the reports of the Floor Supervisors, as well as that of all Room Watchers in his/her building. The stapled forms submitted by the room watchers at the end of the examination, and the reports of each Floor Supervisor, lahat yan (**all of those**) form part of the overall report of conduct of the Building Supervisor, na sinu-submit namin (**that we submit**) to the Central Office for documentation upon conclusion of the licensure examination.” (Key Informant C)*

The Conduct of Examination Folder also serves as guide in establishing the statistics to process the checking of examinees’ answers. Figure 15 below is a form called “Sequence of Reports” utilized by the Building Supervisor, as inserted in their respective green expanding folders during the preparation by the Examination Section, for proper guidance during the conduct of the examination.

Figure 15.

Sequence of Reports of the Building Supervisor (Source: Key Informant C)

“We instituted inserting the Sequence of Reports in the examination kits of the Building Supervisor so that they are guided in the compilation of all their reports. We understand that the Building Supervisor has many reports, and the sequence helps them arrange all of those reports. On our part in the Examination Section, we also have other reports to collect, which is why we specified which forms should not be fastened in the

Conduct Folder but need to just be inserted within. We need these other reports also.” (Key Informant C)

The primary document utilized by the Building Supervisor is the Building Supervisor’s Report, a sample of which can be seen in Figure 16a and Figure 16b below. This form is used to record the number of test questionnaires and answer sheets actually utilized per floor for each subject, as well as the number of examinees within the area of supervision of each Floor Supervisor under the Building Supervisor’s area of responsibility. It is also used to document the number of examinees listed in the building, the number of examinees added to the list (if any), the number of listed examinees absent during the examination, and the actual number of examinees who took the examination. Similar to the Floor Supervisor’s report, the Building Supervisor’s Report is also utilized to record any incident that deviates from the examination procedures, such as during cases of dangling of ID sheet and Answer Sheet sets between examinees, cheating incidents, mishandling of examination paraphernalia, and other incidents that are peculiar to the regular conduct of examinations as observed by the Floor Supervisor/s and/or the Security Officer deployed in the building. It also provides a space in Page 2, where the Building Supervisor can provide his/her remarks and recommendations to help improve the conduct of future licensure examinations. The Building Supervisor’s Report is signed by the Building Supervisor itself, as noted by the assigned Examination Coordinator.

Figure 16a.
Building Supervisor's Report sample (Page 1) (Source: Key Informant C)

BUILDING SUPERVISOR'S REPORT														
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR : <input type="text"/>						DATE/S OF EXAM : <input type="text"/>								
REGIONAL OFFICE/TEST CENTER : <input type="text"/>				SCHOOL : <input type="checkbox"/> NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL				BUILDING : <input type="text"/>						
I. NUMBER OF EXAMINATION PAPERS RECEIVED PER SUBJECT														
FLOOR SUPERVISOR/S	NO. OF ROOMS	NO. OF TEST QUESTIONNAIRES AND ANSWER SHEETS SETS PER SUBJECT												NO. OF EXAMINEES
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
<input type="text"/>	1-5													
<input type="text"/>	6-10													
<input type="text"/>	11-15													
<input type="text"/>	16-19													
TOTAL	19													

II. NUMBER OF EXAMINEES:			
1. NO. OF EXAMINEES PER LIST	<input type="text"/>	5.1. NO. OF COMPLETE	<input type="text"/>
2. NO. OF EXAMINEES ADDED TO THE LIST	<input type="text"/>	5.2. NO. OF REMOVALS	<input type="text"/>
3. TOTAL NO. OF EXAMINEES LISTED	<input type="text"/>	5.3. NO. OF ABANDONED	<input type="text"/>
4. LESS NO. OF ABSENT EXAMINEES	<input type="text"/>	5.4. NO. OF INCOMPLETE	<input type="text"/>
5. TOTAL NO. OF EXAMINEES WHO TOOK THE EXAM	<input type="text"/>		

TAC-EXM-COE-01
 Rev. 02
 August 24, 2022
 Page 1 of 2

Figure 16b.
Building Supervisor's Report sample (Page 2) (Source: Key Informant C)

BUILDING SUPERVISOR'S REPORT												
<p>III. INCIDENT REPORT DURING THE CONDUCT OF EXAMINATION:</p> <p>A. DANGEROUS CASES (ID/Answer Sheet Interchanged)</p> <p>Room No: <input type="text"/> Floor Bldg: <input type="text"/> Room No: <input type="text"/> Floor / Bldg: <input type="text"/> Room No: <input type="text"/> Floor / Bldg: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Examinees involved:</p> <p>1. <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/> 1. <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/> 1. <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/></p> <p>2. <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/> 2. <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/> 2. <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Action Taken: <input type="text"/> Action Taken: <input type="text"/> Action Taken: <input type="text"/></p> <p>B. COLLUSION / CHEATING CASES</p> <p>Name of Examinees: <input type="text"/> Name of Examinees: <input type="text"/> Name of Examinees: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Seat No. <input type="text"/> Room <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/> Room <input type="text"/> Seat No: <input type="text"/> Room <input type="text"/></p> <p>Action Taken: <input type="text"/> Action Taken: <input type="text"/> Action Taken: <input type="text"/></p> <p>C. OTHER UNTOWARD INCIDENTS</p> <p><input type="text"/></p> <p><input type="text"/></p> <p>Room No: <input type="text"/> Floor/Bldg. <input type="text"/> Room No: <input type="text"/> Floor/Bldg: <input type="text"/> Room No. <input type="text"/> Floor/Bldg <input type="text"/></p> <p>D. NAME OF UNAUTHORIZED PERSON WHO VISITED THE AREA DURING THE EXAMINATION (Indicate time of arrival and purpose) <input type="text"/></p> <p>E. REMARKS/RECOMMENDATION: <input type="text"/></p> <p><input type="text"/></p> <p>REPORTED BY: <input type="text"/> BUILDING SUPERVISOR</p> <p>NOTED BY: <input type="text"/> CHIEF, LICENSURE AND REGISTRATION DIVISION/EXAM COORDINATOR</p> <p>Date: SEPTEMBER 21, 2022</p> <p>Date: SEPTEMBER 21, 2022</p>												

TAC-EXM-COE-01
 Rev. 02
 August 24, 2022
 Page 2 of 2

Figure 17 above shows a sample of the Delivery Receipt for Answer Sheets, Used/Excess/Extra (Unused/Spoiled) Test Question Sets. This form is maintained in two (2) copies by each Building Supervisor for each subject, in aid of maintaining the total statistics emanating from the number of answer sheets and the number of used and unused test questionnaires of each Floor Supervisor. It also records the number of sealed boxes of test questionnaires opened by the Building Supervisor for distribution. The Building Supervisor affixes his/her signature in every sheet. This form is submitted by the Supply Officer, together with the sealed boxes of Test Questionnaires and the package of all answer sheets as packed by the Building Supervisor, after the end of each examination subject.

On the other hand, Figure 18 below shows a sample of the Delivery Receipt for PERRCs (Permanent Examination Registration Record Cards), Mailing Envelopes, and Identification Sheets. This form is now primarily used for the delivery of ID sheets, as PERRCs are no longer utilized and Mailing Envelopes from examinees are no longer collected during examinations. This Delivery Receipt is maintained in two (2) copies by each Building Supervisor throughout the entire examination, to record the total number of ID sheets used, as recorded in the rooms covered by each Floor Supervisor. Likewise, the Building Supervisor affixes his/her signature in every copy of the Delivery Receipt. This form is submitted by the Supply Officer, along with the package of all ID sheets as packed by the Building Supervisor, to the Regional Office at the end of the entire examination conduct. It is worthy to note that the total number of ID sheets should also tally with the total number of answer sheets and used test questionnaires, as reported in the Building Supervisor's Report, as collected from the information from each Floor Supervisor and Room Watchers under the Building Supervisor's area of responsibility.

retained in the envelope of extra ID/AS sets provided for each Building Supervisor in his/her examination supplies box.

Figure 19.

Delivery Receipts for Sealed Extra & Spoiled Examinee Identification / Answer Sheets Sets sample (Source: Key Informant C)

	DELIVERY RECEIPT
SEALED EXTRA & SPOILED EXAMINEE IDENTIFICATION/ANSWER SHEETS SETS	
INSTRUCTION:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This form is to be accomplished by the Building Supervisor at the end of the examination. Extra ID/Answer Sheet Sets shall be delivered to the Examination Section after the last subject. 2. The Building Supervisor shall properly seal, label and sign across the sealing tape of the package. 3. The Building Supervisor will be held responsible for the actual counting of the sets inside the sealed package. 	
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR: _____	
DATE/S OF EXAMINATION: _____	
SCHOOL AND BUILDING: _____	
<u>EXTRA AND SPOILED EXAMINEE ID/ANSWER SHEETS SETS</u>	
TOTAL = _____	
Submitted by:	
_____ Building Supervisor <small>(Signature Over Printed Name)</small>	Date: _____
Received by:	
_____ Supply Custodian, Examination Section <small>(Signature Over Printed Name)</small>	Date _____ Time _____

The Building Supervisor is required to accomplish the form “List of Absentees” to record the names of examinees that were not present during the course of licensure examination scheduled. Said form lists the last name, first name, and middle initial of the absent examinee, including the room and seat numbers where the examinee was supposedly assigned. The Building Supervisor accomplishes this form in two (2) copies, one to be fastened in the Conduct of Examination Folder and one to be simply inserted in the folder, to be used by the Examination Section in compiling information on absent examinees in the licensure examination conducted. Figure 20 below shows a sample of the List of Absentees form.

Figure 20.

List of Absentees Form sample (Source: Key Informant C)

LIST OF ABSENTEES					
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR :		§			
DATE/S OF EXAMINATION :		§			
REGIONAL OFFICE/TEST CENTER:		T			
SCHOOL/BUILDING :		§			
	NAME			ROOM NO.	SEAT NO.
	LAST NAME	FIRST NAME	M.I.		
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					
14					
15					
16					
17					
18					
19					
20					
21					
22					
23					
24					
25					
26					
27					
28					
29					
30					
31					
32					
33					
34					
35					

Submitted by:

§
BUILDING SUPERVISOR
(Signature Over Printed Name)

TAC-IXM-CDE-03
 Rev. 02
 August 24, 2022
 Page 1 of 1

The Building Supervisor is also responsible in documenting test questions that are seemingly incomplete or questionable. Per Key Informant C, there are instances in some licensure examinations in which some of the questions do not have multiple choices to which the examinee can select the answer/s from. The Building Supervisor uses the Report on Incomplete/Questionable Test Questions Form to

As part of managing examination materials and examinee statistics in his/her area of responsibility, the Building Supervisor accomplishes a Certification on Untampered/Sealed Boxes, a sample of which is shown in Figure 22 below.

Figure 22.
Certification of Untampered/Sealed Boxes sample (Source: Key Informant C)

	ROOM NUMBERS	USED TEST QUESTIONS SETS	UNUSED TEST QUESTIONS SETS	FLOOR SUPERVISOR	SIGNATURE
1.	1-5				
2.	6-10				
3.	11-15				
4.	16-19				
5.					
6.					
7.					
8.					
TOTAL					

BUILDING SUPERVISOR
(Signature Over Printed Name)

SUPPLY OFFICER
(Signature Over Printed Name)

SECURITY OFFICER
(Signature Over Printed Name)

SECURITY OFFICER
(Signature Over Printed Name)

Date: SEPTEMBER 19, 2022

Said form is used in certifying that the boxes of test questionnaires delivered to the Building Supervisor for each subject had not been tampered and remained intact upon counting and distribution at the designated time of opening of sealed boxes (i.e. fifteen [15] minutes before the start of each examination subject). It also

includes a portion that tallies the number of used and unused test questionnaires from each Floor Supervisor who affixes their respective signatures to ascertain the statistic of the Building Supervisor in the said form. This form is accomplished in one (1) copy for each subject, signed by the Building Supervisor, as well as the Supply Officer and the Security Officer present during the examination.

Upon the distribution of test questionnaires by the Floor Supervisors, they submit to the Building Supervisor their respective Floor Supervisor's Test Questions Distribution & Accountability Form (see Figure 13a & Figure 13b). The Building Supervisor signs each of the form submitted to certify that the data listed by the Floor Supervisor in the forms are correct. The Building Supervisor staples all of these forms from each Floor Supervisor and places the stapled forms inside the Test Questionnaires box, to be returned to the Regional Office after the end of the examination subject.

In maintaining the integrity of the conduct of the licensure examination, the Building Supervisor is assisted by the assigned Security Officer. To ascertain the presence of a security officer in his/her building, the Building Supervisor accomplishes the Record/Certification of Attendance of Security Officers. The Building Supervisor writes the name of the assigned security officer in the form, signs the form to signify that the security officer identified has reported in the building, and inserts the said form in the Conduct of Examination Folder for report consolidation by the Examination Section. Figure 23 below shows a sample of the Record/Certification of Attendance of Security Officers.

Figure 23.

Record/Certification of Attendance of Security Officers sample (Source: Key Informant C)

	RECORD/CERTIFICATION OF ATTENDANCE OF SECURITY OFFICERS
---	--

T O: BUILDING SUPERVISOR: _____
Name of Building Supervisor

School/Building

BEARER: _____
Printed Name of [] Security Officer

is assigned as Security Officer in your school/building to: escort the [] service vehicle; secure the retrieval and delivery of test materials from the [] Confidential Room to the assigned school and vice-versa; witness the opening of sealed boxes of test booklets; make regular rounds and see to it that there are no unauthorized persons in the area; and maintain peace and order during the conduct of Licensure Examination for/of _____ on _____

Head, Examination Section

NOTE:

The Building Supervisor should sign opposite the date indicated below to signify the attendance of above-named []:

DATE	SCHOOL/BLDG.	PRINTED NAME AND SIGNATURE OF BUILDING SUPERVISOR
_____	_____	_____

Found in the examination kit of the Building Supervisor is the Security Officer's Report of Activities in the Testing Center. The said report is given by the Building Supervisor to the assigned Security Officer who will accomplish and sign one (1) copy of it for each examination day. This form is used by the assigned Security Officer to record the time of various activities in the duration of the licensure examination conducted, as well as to list any observation or remarks in each activity. Upon conclusion of the examination, the assigned Security Officer submits the report to the Building Supervisor, while the Building Supervisor includes the Security Officer's Report for fastening in the Conduct of Examination Folder. Figure 24 below shows a sample of the Security Officer's Report of Activities in the Testing Center.

Figure 24.

Security Officer's Report of Activities in the Testing Center sample (Source: Key Informant C)

SECURITY OFFICER'S REPORT OF ACTIVITIES IN THE TESTING CENTER		
LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR:	[REDACTED]	
DATE/S OF EXAMINATION:	[REDACTED]	
REGIONAL OFFICE/ TEST CENTER:	[REDACTED]	
SCHOOL & BUILDING:	[REDACTED]	
ACTIVITIES	TIME	OBSERVATION/REMARKS
1. Witness the release of TQ boxes from the Confidential Printing Room		
2. Escort the sealed boxes bring to the Testing Center		
3. Witness the opening of the sealed TQ boxes		
4. Observe and walk around the building to check if there are unauthorized persons		
5. Approach and disperse group suspicious examinees with bunch of papers		
6. Observe and walk around to clear the lobbies/floors of examinees who finished early ahead of other examinees		
7. Randomly check the comfort rooms and other corners of the building		
8. Escort the sealed boxes of test papers to the [REDACTED] - Rating Division		
9. Other untoward incidents, if any:		

Reported by:

Signature over Printed Name

Agency and Designation: _____

NOTE: This form must be submitted to the Building Supervisor on the last day of examination.

TAC-EXM-COE-08
Rev. 02
August 24, 2022
Page 1 of 1

The Security Officer utilizes the Report of Activities in the Testing Center as provided by the Building Supervisor upon reporting for duty.

“I am provided by the Building Supervisor of a Security Officer’s Report Form (which is 1 form per day for the duration of the examination). I record in this form all the activities that happened during the day, like the time of retrieval of the TQ boxes, time of opening of the TQ boxes for each subject, findings during the time I roam around the building, upon checking the comfort rooms, and even when unauthorized persons approach the area, I put those details in the report.” (Key Informant H)

In addition, the Security Officer also signs some of the reports of the Building Supervisor, such as the Certification of Untampered/Sealed TQ Boxes (Figure 22) and the Report on Violation by Examinees as shown in Figure 25a and Figure 25b below to report acts of cheating or other prohibited acts that have been detected from examinees. The Report on Violation by Examinees is to be accomplished by the Room Watchers assigned in the room where the violation has been detected, indicating the name of the examinees who made the violation, the examinee’s room and seat assignment, the cheating/prohibited act detected, the time of detection, the subject being administered when the violation took place, and the action taken by the responsible examination personnel. Aside from the Room Watchers, the Security Officer, together with the Building Supervisor and the assigned Floor Supervisor, also signs in the said form to certify the information that has been declared surrounding the incident reported. In the event that no cheating/prohibited acts have been reported, the Security Officer still signs in the report, as likewise signed and consolidated by the Building Supervisor in his/her Conduct of Examination Folder.

Figure 25a.

Report on Violation by Examinees sample (Page 1) (Source: Key Informant C)

	REPORT ON VIOLATION BY EXAMINEES AGAINST RULES AND REGULATIONS ON THE ADMINISTRATION OF LICENSURE EXAMINATIONS

LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR:	
DATE/S OF EXAMINATION:	
SCHOOL/BLDG:	
NAME OF SUBJECT:	

I. NAME OF ERRING EXAMINEE BEING REPORTED:

NAME	BUILDING	ROOM NO.	SEAT NO.

II. ACTS OF CHEATING*	TIME	SUBJECT	ACTION TAKEN
1. Impersonation or employing another person to take the exam in his/her behalf;			
2. Leakage of exam questions, including the act of taking out from the exam room any question in the exam, copying and/or divulging the content of the exam to any individual or entity;			
3. Collusion with any exam personnel of the Commission or third person for the purpose of obtaining favorable results in the exam or gaining access thereto through illegal means;			
4. Possession or use of codigo, crib sheets or other exam paraphernalia such as books, notes, review materials, and other printed materials containing principles or excerpts thereof, coded data/information/formula that are not authorized by the Board; prohibited calculators (including programmable calculators or with embedded functions); cellular phones; Bluetooth earplugs; transmitters; beepers; smart watches; portable computers or other similar electronic gadgets/devices which have photographic features or which are capable of communicating or transmitting information;			
5. Passing of notes or other suspicious objects to other examinees during the exam;			
6. Engaging in conversation, including helping or asking help from any person, by means of words, signs, gestures, codes and other similar acts in the course of the exam for no valid reason;			
7. Copying or referring to any solution, answer or work of another examinee or allowing another examinee to copy or refer to his/her solution, answer or work;			
8. Employing fraud in accomplishing and/or submitting exam records (includes tampering of exam records/documents, attaching fake picture in the seat plan, etc.);			
9. Switching of exam papers and/or seats or examinee number switching;			
10. Making or leaving any distinguishing mark in the exam answer sheet;			
11. Continuous answering of the exam after the announcement by the proctor that the time is up;			
12. Giving or receiving money, food or any consideration for the purpose of extending undue favor, advantage or treatment to any examinee.			

Figure 25b.

Report on Violation by Examinees sample (Page 2) (Source: Key Informant C)

REPORT ON VIOLATION BY EXAMINEES AGAINST RULES AND REGULATIONS ON THE ADMINISTRATION OF LICENSURE EXAMINATIONS			
III. PROHIBITED ACTS*	TIME	SUBJECT	ACTION TAKEN
1. Bringing of deadly weapons inside the exam venue. The prohibition applies even to those who have permits to carry firearms outside of their residence;			
2. Bringing and/or drinking alcoholic drinks and/or smoking cigarettes within the premises of the exam venue;			
3. Entering the exam venue under the influence of liquor, illegal drugs or other intoxicating substance;			
4. Accepting or receiving anything, including food, from any person while the exam is in progress.			
5. Loitering, talking or discussing the test questions and/or answers inside or near the exam room which tend to distract or disturb the conduct of the exam.			
6. Engaging in any violent, indecent, disorderly, threatening or offensive behavior or language (e.g. bullying, harassment, etc.) within the exam premises, whether directed to a co-examinee or exam personnel, while the exam is ongoing.			
7. Other similar acts			

*Per Memorandum Order No. [REDACTED]

III. NAME OF ROOM WATCHER/S:

DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3	DAY 4
ROOM WATCHER – 1			
NAME:	NAME:	NAME:	NAME:
SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:
OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:
CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:
ROOM WATCHER – 2			
NAME:	NAME:	NAME:	NAME:
SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:
OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:	OFFICE:
CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:	CONTACT NO.:

IV. WITNESSES:

BUILDING SUPERVISOR	FLOOR SUPERVISOR	SECURITY OFFICER
NAME: [REDACTED]	NAME: [REDACTED]	NAME:
SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:	SIGNATURE:

Per Key Informant C, said form is accomplished in five (5) copies by the Building Supervisor, signed by the Security Officer in all 5 sheets.

“From time to time, I regularly monitor the examinees and all the exam personnel. The key here is to implement fully the policies and procedures mandated by the Office. If there are untoward incidents, I report them to the Exam Coordinator or the concerned personnel as soon as possible.”

(Key Informant C)

Per Key Informant A, room watchers may also sit in conspicuous areas of the room where the examinees are visible enough to be noticed for significant body movements. The room watchers are ultimately responsible in the prevention of cheating incidents or other irregularities while the examination is in progress. The Report on Violations of Examinees is utilized to put on record any incident involving examinees who violated examination rules and regulations.

Reporting of Issues

The Building Supervisor also conducts surveillance to gain feedback from the floor supervisors, room watchers, and examinees, in terms of how the examination was conducted in general, how the physical environment of the examination venue affected the overall conduct of the examination, and how procedures in distributing examination materials were implemented.

*“Building a good communication with them helped me maintain the cooperation I need to ensure a smooth and clean conduct of licensure examinations. By regularly monitoring the examination personnel, I get to know them personally; I ask their opinions and even their concerns during the conduct of examinations. Sometimes kasi nahihiya silang magsulat sa mga report forms nila (**they are shy of writing down in their report forms**). So ako na mismo ang nagre-reach out (**I myself reach out**) to get their feedback.” (Key Informant C)*

Reminding of Procedures to Prevent Cheating

Once the Floor Supervisor arrives in the examination venue or testing site, he/she is informed of the coverage of rooms to supervise. Upon receiving the examination kit from the Supply Officer, he/she proceeds to the coverage of rooms to

inspect the rooms and to communicate with the assigned room watchers, particularly to guide them in providing instructions to examinees and in filling-out their respective forms.

“Before the start of the exam, I usually meet the Room Watchers under my supervision to give them proper instructions to examinees and some reminders (during the Briefing Orientation). I also meet with my assigned Supply Aide to check if the supplies I need are complete. Sinasabihan ko rin yung Supply Aide ko na dapat kasama ko siya dito sa area of responsibility ko. (I also instruct my Supply Aide to remain with me in my area of responsibility.)” (Key Informant B)

The Floor Supervisor also provides instructions to the Supply Aide to assist examinees who cannot immediately find their assigned rooms, especially in large examination venues where rooms are scattered across the entire area. This helps save time in accommodating examinees within wide testing centers.

The Floor Supervisor constantly gives the room watchers other instructions to properly manage the examination proceedings within their assigned rooms.

“Ako personally, I remind the room watchers, kapag wala sa List of Examinees niyo, huwag niyong i-aadmit. (Personally, I remind the room watchers that if the examinee is not in your List of Examinees, do not admit them.) I advise them to be cautious for potential impersonation, always check and compare the faces of the examinee with what is in your Seat Plan. Now, if there are late examinees, si Building Supervisor naman ang bahala diyan. (The Building Supervisor takes care of them.) Also, I regularly check if the chairs within the room are properly arranged and numbered according to the Seat Plan. I also

check if the Room Watchers have written the correct information on the board to guide the examinees of the progress or schedule of the examination.” (Key Informant B)

If the Room Watchers are tasked to be vigilant in their respective rooms, the Floor Supervisors are also tasked to be extra vigilant in supervising all rooms under their area of responsibility. The Floor Supervisor conducts physical and visual surveillance to check room watchers and ensure that they are awake and committed to the tasks of maintaining the integrity of the licensure examination.

“Every once in a while, when the examination is on-going, I look at my room watchers and notice what they do. If they sleep, I wake them up and remind them to focus. I also prohibit them from talking and loitering in the hallways or in the examination room. If I catch them talking to others, I make eye contact to emphasize that I am listening to what they are saying and then I nod my head to show that I can understand them loud and clear.” (Key Informant B)

Per Key Informant C, the Building Supervisor also gives reminders to room watchers.

Aside from the floor supervisors, I remind the Room Watchers to properly fill-out their respective forms and distribute accordingly their ID/AS sets and Test Questionnaires. Ultimately, I just use or apply the procedures mandated by the Central Office when it comes to the conduct of the licensure examination.” (Key Informant C)

Coordination and communication are vital aspects that the Building Supervisor undertakes during the conduct of licensure examinations. Maintaining

consistency in administering procedures of conducting licensure examinations serves as a core function in the Building Supervisor's duties.

“That is why, I usually remind and give proper instructions to the examination personnel prior to the start of the examination proper. I instruct Floor Supervisors to remind their room watchers that examinees should use ballpen in writing and pencil in shading, that examinees taking Mathematics as Field of Specialization during Licensure Examination for Teachers may only be allowed to use their calculators on the last subject which is on their FOS, and that the Floor Supervisors should constantly monitor how their room watchers fill-out their reports and forms. I really demand consistency because it is crucial in making sure that our examination is truthful and secure.” (Key Informant C)

Overall, the Exam Coordinator oversees how procedures are implemented. As such, he/she usually communicates with the Building Supervisors assigned in the schools or testing sites within his/her area of responsibility.

*“I usually ask them, kumusta dito? Wala bang naging problema? (**How are things here? Were there no problems?**) Did you instruct your Floor Supervisors to monitor their Room Watchers to be vigilant? Things like that. I would usually remind and instruct the Building Supervisors to be extra careful, making sure that cheating is prevented, that cellphones would not be used by anyone, both examinees and room watchers, and that all test questionnaires and answer sheets are accounted for. Sometimes, I emphasize to the Building Supervisors that we do not want our Region to be tarnished with the legacy of having one examination anomaly, much less more than that.” (Key Informant D)*

Removing Prohibited Materials that Compromise Exam Integrity

In order to maintain the integrity of the examinations in each room, the Floor Supervisor ensures that no unnecessary or prohibited objects are visibly present in their assigned rooms.

“If there are examinees that brought their review materials, we usually confiscate them. We return those materials only at the end of the entire examination. And then, I also make sure that the examinees’ personal belongings are placed inside their bags. All their bags are placed in one place inside the examination room, either in front or at the side of the room. The plastic envelopes containing the Notice of Admission (NOA) of each examinee, we place them beside their respective seats.” (Key Informant B)

The Building Supervisor enforces that all examinees should surrender their cellular phones and electronic gadgets to their room watchers, that all room watchers should surrender their devices likewise to the Floor Supervisor, and that all floor supervisors should surrender their devices to the Building Supervisor, to be returned only upon submission of the ID sheets, used test questionnaires, and used answer sheets by the examinees at the end of the last subject of the examination day.

“I tell my Floor Supervisors to surrender their cellphones before the start of the examination because we want to avoid the possibility of them taking pictures of unused test questionnaires. They might leak the questions, which will compromise the integrity of our examinations. Especially the room watchers, we do not want them to take photos of anything, that includes not only the test questionnaires but also the examinees’ faces and their names. We are trying to maintain the

examinees' data privacy as well as the security of administering the licensure examinations.” (Key Informant C)

The Floor Supervisor takes custody of the cellular phones and other electronic gadgets brought to the examination venue by all room watchers assigned under his/her area of responsibility. Prior the start of the first subject on the examination day, the Floor Supervisor collects the room watchers' cellular phones, and places the phones in a transparent envelope. These cellular phones will only be returned to the room watchers upon submission of the used test questionnaires and answer sheets from their rooms, at the end of the last subject of the examination day.

“I also tell the room watchers to return the cellular phones of the examinees only after submitting the used TQs and answer sheets after the last subject of the day. I remind them to be careful in returning the gadgets, so as to avoid losses on our part. We do not want to be responsible for lost cellular phones, as much as lost test questionnaires and answer sheets.” (Key Informant B)

Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency

Per Key Informant F, the Supply Officer is responsible in securing that all examination supplies are accounted for, not within the reach of unauthorized examination personnel.

*“Usually, tinutulungan naman ako ng Security Officer to secure the area, na kami lang ang may access sa mga gagamiting supplies, kagaya ng test booklets, answer sheets, hindi yan pupwedeng makita o mahawakan lang ng kahit sino. **(Usually, I am assisted by the Security Officer to secure the area in which we have exclusive access to the supplies***

to be used, such as test booklets and answer sheets. These cannot be seen nor touched by just anyone.)” (Key Informant F)

The Supply Aide provides assistance to the Floor Supervisor in the delivery of Test Questionnaires to and from the examination rooms covered.

“Kapag naibigay na po kay Floor Supervisor yung mga Test Booklets, ako po ang taga-bitbit. Siya naman po ang nagdi-distribute ng booklet sa mga room watcher kada room. (Once the Floor Supervisor receives the Test Booklets, I carry the booklets. He/she distributes those booklets to the room watchers in each room.)” (Key Informant G)

The Supply Aide occasionally assists the Floor Supervisor in filling-out his/her forms through running errands to each room to collect the names of absent examinees, as well as the number of absent examinees per room. He/she receives instructions from the Floor Supervisor and provides assistance as necessary.

“Ang ginagawa ko po talaga ay mag-assist sa Floor Supervisor, sundin ang instructions niya gaya ng pagbigay ng brown envelopes sa bawat room, pagkuha ng sapat na supplies para sa buong araw doon sa Supply Officer. (What I really do is to assist the Floor Supervisor, follow his/her instructions such as handing out brown envelopes to each room, getting ample examination supplies for the day from the Supply Officer.)” (Key Informant G)

Key Informant G expressed his concern to any Floor Supervisor who does not have a Supply Aide during actual licensure examinations. This suggests the Supply Aide’s important role in assisting the Floor Supervisor throughout the entire examination.

“Magkakandarapa si Floor Supervisor kung walasiyang Supply Aide. Magagahol siya sa oras gawin lahat, pag-pack, pagbibilang, maiksi lang naman ang oras sa pagitan ng mga subject. (The Floor Supervisor would find things hard without a Supply Aide. He/she will have a hard time doing everything, counting, packing, since time is too limited between subjects.)” (Key Informant G)

At the conclusion of every examination subject, the Security Officer provides assistance by escorting the Supply Officer in transporting the overall packages of answer sheets and the sealed boxes of used Test Questionnaires from the examination venue to the Office.

“I make sure to accompany the Supply Officer to the Office to turn-over the answer sheets and the test booklets. I usually sit near the packages and boxes so that I could easily defend the materials in case there are attempts to steal or damage them. The goal is to bring everything to the Office in one piece, without damages. Otherwise, the Supply Officer and I would be held accountable.” (Key Informant H)

Respective Badges are Put in Place

Key Informant C also the importance of wearing appropriate attire as a Building Supervisor, as it is a symbol of authority within the place of examination.

*“As Building Supervisor, I would usually wear a dress or a blouse paired with black/denim pants and closed shoes. But at all times, we should wear our respective badges. The badge identifies us, whether yung naka-suot (**the bearer**) is the Building Supervisor, a Floor Supervisor, a Room Watcher, etc. It signifies that you are an authorized person who can go around and look at what is going on.” (Key Informant C)*

The Security Officer highlights the importance of wearing his official uniform as a symbol of authority, much like how Key Informant C mentioned in the KII as Building Supervisor. It highlights the importance of being physically present.

“It is important that the Security Officer assigned should report for duty in the exam site wearing their official uniform. It gives others the impression that a uniformed officer is present and ready to defend the integrity of the licensure examinations being administered, no matter what.” (Key Informant C)

Referring Issues to Higher Authority

The Room Watcher is also tasked to resolve issues in the examination room. If the Room Watcher cannot resolve issues, he/she usually refers the matter to the Floor Supervisor.

If we encounter odd behaviors during the progress of the examination, the first thing we do is de-escalate. We simply ask what the problem is and provide solution after. But we are not allowed to give hints to examinees if there are difficult questions, as it is strictly against the rules. If we do not know the solution to any problem, we refer the matter to our Floor Supervisor.” (Key Informant A)

Per Key Informant A, during break time, or in between the time allocated for each subject of the examination proper, room watchers are advised to remain inside their assigned room to monitor the examinees and maintain the physical environment of the room assigned to them. They are likewise advised to refrain from talking to co-room watchers in other rooms. This speaks of the need to follow the rules set by higher authority.

“I am not an employee of the Agency. So I really make sure that I always follow all the rules of the examination as a room watcher. I do not want to be suspended or worse, black-listed from being able to serve as a volunteer in licensure examinations.” (Key Informant A)

Also per Key Informant A, Room Watchers are responsible for the proper utilization of the ID Sheet and Answer Sheet (ID/AS) sets of all examinees. They are tasked in ensuring that each examinee utilizes his/her own ID/AS set, and not those of anyone else. As each examination subject begins to be administered, each examinee detaches the bottom answer sheet in their ID/AS set, and the room watchers collect the ID/AS sets of each examinee, placed in the respective brown envelopes of examinees. Together, these brown envelopes are bundled, labelled properly with the name and seat number of each examinee, and are maintained throughout the examination duration.

The physical presence and visibility of a higher authority, such as the Floor Supervisor, is also a key factor in the referral of issues of the room watchers.

*“If the Room Watchers cannot personally resolve their concerns or the concerns of the examinees, they usually turn to the Floor Supervisor to ask for help. Kaya importanteng nakikita ang FS ng kanyang mga room watchers. **(That’s why it is essential that the FS is visible to his/her room watchers.)** (Key Informant B)*

Recording of Accountable Persons is Ensured

The Attendance Supervisor is tasked to record the names, time of attendance, and area of responsibility of the examination personnel exercising authority. He/she provides assignment to assigned personnel such as room watchers and floor supervisors about their area of responsibility.

“Since I am in-charge of assigning proctors to each room, I go to the school assignment very early on the day (or first day for multiple day exams). Upon my arrival, I prioritize the Room Watchers/Proctors to sign their attendance record sheets first. I require them to present to me their Certificate of Assignment and any valid ID for identity verification, before I assign them their room number. Once they have a room number, I instruct them to get their room watcher’s kit from the Supply Officer and then to immediately proceed to their assigned rooms. Once I am able to assign at least 1 room watcher per room, I proceed to assigning them with their partners.” (Key Informant E)

Per Key Informant E, the Attendance Supervisor normally reports to his/her assigned building or school not later than 5:30 a.m. This is in order to have ample time in assigning room watchers across all rooms in the building.

The Attendance Supervisor proceeds to inform the Building Supervisor of the status of assignment of room watchers in each room. Normally, the Attendance Supervisor first ensures that every room has at least one watcher assigned. Otherwise, the Building Supervisor could contact the Exam Coordinator to ask for replacement of wait-listed room watchers in case there are absent volunteers.

The Attendance Supervisor also monitors the attendance of other crucial examination personnel such as Floor Supervisors, Supply Officer, Supply Aide, Security Officer, and the Building Supervisor itself. He/she assists in monitoring that assigned examination personnel have already reported to the building; he/she informs the Regional Office, through the Exam Coordinator, in case assigned persons of authority have not yet reported, for possible replacement or to facilitate contact on whereabouts.

The Attendance Supervisor uses two (2) forms during the distribution of assignment to assigned examination personnel. Figure 26a and Figure 26b below are samples of the Attendance Record Sheets filled-out by all concerned examination personnel upon arrival and reporting to the Attendance Supervisor. The Attendance Record sheets are accomplished in two (2) copies.

Figure 26a.
Attendance Record sheet sample for Over-all Exam Personnel
 (Source: Key Informant E)

OVER-ALL EXAMINATION PERSONNEL ATTENDANCE RECORD								CENTRAL SCHOOL
Name of Examination:								
NO.	NAME	DESIGNATION	MARCH 19, 2023				NO. OF DAYS PRESENT	AMOUNT
1	[REDACTED]	BUILDING SUPERVISOR	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,440.00
2	[REDACTED]	ATTENDANCE SUPERVISOR	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,380.00
3	[REDACTED]	SUPPLY OFFICER	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,380.00
4	[REDACTED]	FLOOR SUPERVISOR	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,380.00
5	[REDACTED]	FLOOR SUPERVISOR	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,380.00
6	[REDACTED]	FLOOR SUPERVISOR	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,380.00
7	[REDACTED]	SUPPLY AIDE	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,220.00
8	[REDACTED]	SUPPLY AIDE	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,220.00
9	[REDACTED]	SUPPLY AIDE	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,220.00
10	[REDACTED]	SECURITY OFFICER	IN: _____ OUT: _____ SG: _____					1,380.00
11								-
12								-
13								-
14								-
15								-
NOTES:							TOTAL:	11,380.00

 Building Supervisor

 Attendance Supervisor

Figure 26b.
 Attendance Record sheet sample for Room Watchers
 (Source: Key Informant E)

OVER-ALL EXAMINATION PERSONNEL ATTENDANCE RECORD							CENTRAL SCHOOL
Name of Examination:							
NO.	NAME	DESIGNATION	MARCH 19, 2023			NO. OF DAYS PRESENT	AMOUNT
1		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
2		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
3		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
4		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
5		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
6		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
7		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
8		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
9		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
10		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
11		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
12		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
13		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
14		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
15		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	IN: _____ SIG: _____ ROOM No.: _____	OUT: _____			1,260.00
NOTED:						TOTAL:	18,900.00
			_____ Attendance Supervisor				
_____ Building Supervisor							

The exam personnel writes his/her *time-in* (i.e. the time of arrival in the building) and *time-out* (i.e. time of finish for the examination day), and affixes his/her signature. In the Attendance Record sheet for Room Watchers, the room watcher also writes his/her assigned room number in the sheet. These Attendance Record sheets are signed both by the Building Supervisor and the Attendance Supervisor in each copy. Notable in the Attendance Record sheet is the amount of examination allowance provided for each assigned personnel.

Figure 27a.
 General Payroll sheet sample for Over-all Exam Personnel
 (Source: Key Informant E)

GENERAL PAYROLL											
Agency MARCH 19, 2025											
CONTROL NUMBER:											
We acknowledge the receipt of the sum shown opposite our names as full payment for the services rendered for the period stated:				To payment of daily and breakfast allowance to Examination Personnel in the conduct of LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR held on:							
NO.	NAME	POSITION	DATES PRESENT	Total No. of Days Present	ALLOWANCES			No.	Net amount Received	SIGNATURE OF PAYEE	
					Meal	Daily Rate	additional				
1		BUILDING SUPERVISOR	MARCH 19, 2025	1	320.00	1,120.00		1	1,440.00		
2		ATTENDANCE SUPERVISOR	->>	1	320.00	1,060.00		2	1,380.00		
3		SUPPLY OFFICER	->>	1	320.00	1,060.00		3	1,380.00		
4		FLOOR SUPERVISOR	->>	1	320.00	1,060.00		4	1,380.00		
5		FLOOR SUPERVISOR	->>	1	320.00	1,060.00		5	1,380.00		
6		FLOOR SUPERVISOR	->>	1	320.00	1,060.00		6	1,380.00		
7		SUPPLY AIDE	->>	1	320.00	900.00		7	1,220.00		
8		SUPPLY AIDE	->>	1	320.00	900.00		8	1,220.00		
9		SUPPLY AIDE	->>	1	320.00	900.00		9	1,220.00		
10		SECURITY OFFICER	->>	1	320.00	1,060.00		10	1,380.00		
11								11	-		
12								12	-		
13								13	-		
14								14	-		
15								15	-		
CERTIFIED: Services have been duly rendered as stated								APPROVED FOR PAYMENT: 15,180.00			
Noted: Attendance Supervisor Building Supervisor Regional Director											
REQUEST FOR PAYMENT:				CERTIFICATION: This is to certify that the above named persons rendered their services on the dates opposite their respective names.				CERTIFIED: Each employee whose name appears above has been paid the amount indicated opposite his/her name.			
Budget Officer				Chief Administrative Officer				Disbursing Officer			

Figure 27b.
 General Payroll sheet sample for Room Watchers
 (Source: Key Informant E)

GENERAL PAYROLL											
Agency MARCH 19, 2025											
CONTROL NUMBER:											
We acknowledge the receipt of the sum shown opposite our names as full payment for the services rendered for the period stated:				To payment of daily and breakfast allowance to Room Watchers in the conduct of LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR held on:							
NO.	NAME	POSITION	DATES PRESENT	Total No. of Days Present	ALLOWANCES			No.	Net amount Received	SIGNATURE OF PAYEE	
					Meal	Daily Rate	additional				
1		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	MARCH 19, 2025	1	320.00	940.00		1	1,260.00		
2		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		2	1,260.00		
3		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		3	1,260.00		
4		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		4	1,260.00		
5		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		5	1,260.00		
6		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		6	1,260.00		
7		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		7	1,260.00		
8		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		8	1,260.00		
9		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		9	1,260.00		
10		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		10	1,260.00		
11		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		11	1,260.00		
12		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		12	1,260.00		
13		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		13	1,260.00		
14		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		14	1,260.00		
15		ROOMWATCHER/PROCTOR	->>	1	320.00	940.00		15	1,260.00		
CERTIFIED: Services have been duly rendered as stated								APPROVED FOR PAYMENT: 18,900.00			
Noted: Attendance Supervisor Building Supervisor Regional Director											
REQUEST FOR PAYMENT:				CERTIFICATION: This is to certify that the above named persons rendered their services on the dates opposite their respective names.				CERTIFIED: Each employee whose name appears above has been paid the amount indicated opposite his/her name.			
Budget Officer				Chief Administrative Officer				Disbursing Officer			

Figure 27a and Figure 27b above, on the other hand, show a sample of the General Payroll sheets, where each assigned personnel affixes his/her signature to acknowledge receipt of the payment for the examination allowance. Per Key Informant E, the exam personnel already signs on the General Payroll sheet prior to the receipt of the honoraria itself, so as not to cause distractions during the exam proper.

The Attendance Supervisor also collects one (1) copy of the Floor Supervisor's Attendance Report (see Figure 12) from each Floor Supervisor in the building, as attachment for the liquidation of funds disbursed for the licensure examination. The Attendance Supervisor is responsible in ensuring that all room watchers assigned to the Floor Supervisor have properly and completely signed in the form. Once all Attendance Record sheets and Payroll sheets have been adequately filled-out, the Attendance Supervisor submits these documents to the Disbursing Officer for the disbursement of the examination allowances.

Synthesis of the Communicative Practices

To interpret the narratives of the participants, codes were identified and assigned as communicative practices of the participants. Summarized in the Table 3 below are the communicative practices performed by participants across various examination roles in licensure examination administration.

Table 3.
Communicative Practices of Examination Personnel

EXAM PERSONNEL	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES
Room Watcher (Proctor)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing Exam Statistics • Reporting of Incidents & Violations • Referring Issues to Higher Authority • Roaming Around • Re-checking Documents
Floor Supervisor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reminding to be Extra-Careful • Reporting of Incidents • Roaming Around • Removing Materials that Compromise Examination Reliability • Reminding of Procedures • Retaining Professional Composure • Reviewing Exam Statistics • Retrieval of Used Paraphernalia is Secured
Building Supervisor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roaming around and Reminding Personnel • Removing Prohibited Materials • Reporting of Incidents • Reviewing Exam Statistics • Reprimanding Personnel not Performing Duties • Respective Badge Wearing • Retaining Professional Composure • Reporting of Issues • Retrieval Procedure of Used Materials is Secured
Exam Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roaming around • Reminding of Administrative Procedures • Resolving Issues • Reviewing Exam Statistics
Attendance Supervisor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recording of Accountable Persons is Ensured • Re-checking Documents • Roaming around
Supply Officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieval of Used Paraphernalia is Secured • Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency
Supply Aide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rendering Support to Ensure Consistency • Retrieval of Used Paraphernalia is Secured
Security Officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roaming around • Reporting of Incidents and Violations • Retaining Professional Composure • Respective Badge Wearing • Retrieval of Used Paraphernalia is ensured.

The Exam Coordinator acts as the overall official in-charge of the conduct of the licensure examinations. Reporting directly to the Exam Coordinator, the Building Supervisor is responsible for the overall supervision of the conduct of the examinations within a specific building or testing site. Reporting directly to the Building Supervisor is the Floor Supervisor, who is responsible in supervising the conduct of examinations within a specific number of rooms in a given building or testing site. Reporting directly to the Floor Supervisor are Room Watchers, responsible in specifically implementing examination procedures to be administered to examinees within their respective room assignments. Each of these personnel has a two-way flow of communication. The Exam Coordinator engages in communication exchange with the Building Supervisor; the Building Supervisor engages in communication exchange with the Exam Coordinator and the Floor Supervisor; the Floor Supervisor engages in communication exchange with the Building Supervisor and the Room Watcher; and the Room Watcher engages in communication exchange with the Floor Supervisor. They follow a vertical chain of command which should be followed for it to be functional.

On the other hand, there are other examination personnel who are associated with various examination supervisors in the examination. Reporting directly to the Building Supervisor are the Attendance Supervisor, the Supply Officer, and the Security Officer. Reporting directly to the Floor Supervisor is the Supply Aide. They also share a two-way flow of communication with their supervisors within the organized structure. They do not have direct communication engagement with the examinees, but each personnel are positioned to perform communicative practices to other examination personnel, as supervised by their immediate supervisors.

In response to the first research question, fifteen (15) communicative practices can be summed up in the above analysis, to wit:

1. Examination personnel roam around the testing site.
2. Examination personnel resolve issues and restrain tensions.
3. Examination personnel retain professional composure.
4. Examination personnel review examination statistics.
5. Examination personnel re-check documents.
6. Examination personnel ensure retrieval procedures.
7. Examination personnel reprimand those who do not perform their duties.
8. Examination personnel report incidents and violations of procedures.
9. Examination personnel report issues.
10. Examination personnel give reminders of administrative procedures to prevent cheating.
11. Examination personnel remove materials that compromise examination integrity.
12. Examination personnel render support to ensure consistency.
13. Examination personnel wear respective badges.
14. Examination personnel refer issues to higher authority.
15. Examination personnel ensure the recording of accountable persons.

Reproducing Rule Regime in Licensure Examinations

In the previous section, the communicative practices of personnel in licensure examinations were identified as summarized in Table 3. The codes which emerged during the analysis of the Key Informant Interview of the participants were subjected to further thematic analysis to arrive at five (5) main themes using dimensionalization (Lindlof & Taylor, 2019) wherein specific attributes and characteristics of categorized narratives from each communicative practice were examined in order to surface how the communicative practices reproduce rule regime in the context of licensure examinations.

Described below are the five (5) main themes generated to explain the context of reproducing rule regime in licensure examinations.

Rule Alignment

Rule alignment involves the act of socializing to produce order in the licensure examination. It serves as a strategy in unifying knowledge to produce consistent actions and to make consistent decisions. The act of roaming around is a socialization that holds knowledge among personnel pertaining to examination rules together. Examination personnel watch out for concerns and queries, and they go on to monitor the proceedings, socializing with other personnel in different ways such as eye contact, hand gestures, observing from afar, and paying attention to situations. It helps attain peace and order in the place where licensure examinations are held.

Aligning rules means to resolve conflicts, issues, and problems. The presence of the exam coordinator is an act of communication by itself, seeing to it that things go normally and as supposed to happen. But in the process of resolving irregularities, it takes a great deal of talent to prevent tension from spreading and to de-escalate. Exam personnel have to suppress conflicts, unruly behaviors, and

undue pressure. When examinees ask questions, exam personnel explain based on what the regulatory agency prescribes. Not all inconsistencies are violations, some just need the presentation of clarifications, and this requires aligning with rules through unity of action and orientation.

In any scenario of a licensure examination, professionalism of examination personnel is always necessary. Being professional puts order in a seemingly chaotic environment, where examinees feel the pressure of finishing the exam subjects that they take. This leads to situations of anxiety and misalignment of perceptions. Professional composure is key in alignment of responses to anxious situations. Rules require objectivity in being implemented. Professionalism, through words and actions, help align rules with reality. Temper, patience, facial expressions, and even attention are things that examination personnel manage to ensure order in aligning rules. Aggression does not produce order, nor does panic. The key is maintaining an open communication, listening to at least two sides of the situation. Where professionalism exists, order resides.

Rule Implementation

The implementation of prescribed rules demands order as a key ingredient. It uses information such as names, numerical figures, and seating arrangements as basis for rules to be implemented. This would require the effective utilization and processing of information relevant to the licensure examination conducted. As people use statistical information, they create a sense of order in promoting truth and consistency. Information utilized are based on what is seen and perceived by human senses, establishing consistency through verification or reviewing documents and reports.

The use of reports helps co-construct rule enforcement in licensure examinations. These documents serve as records that can be used to evaluate procedural effectiveness, the effectivity of rules, and the way they are implemented. This also involves assessing how assigned personnel did their tasks, whether they followed rules or made violations in the process. Nevertheless, order can be established through sheets of paper that contain useful information describing what happened, what went wrong, and what could be done to improve circumstances in implementing rules in the future. The mere act of affixing signatures in forms is a communicative act to signify truthfulness and supply of correct and accurate information, thus, order.

In implementing rules, examination materials are indispensable. Test questionnaires and answer sheets are things that should be managed, through the collective efforts of examination supervisors, room watchers, and supply officers/aides. It is through retrieval of needed materials where rule implementation begins, including accountability in the equation. The mere act of providing labels to packages to conceal answers and questions in booklets is an act of preventing leakage of sensitive information. By preventing conflict of interests, order is reproduced in licensure examinations.

Rule Compliance

Alienation to rules is something that compliance must address. When examination personnel roam around and catch up invigilators who sleep, these invigilators become a source of disorder in the testing site. By not performing what they are supposed to do, they create misalignment with the goals that the rule regime is built for. The act of reprimanding people who fail to do what they are supposed to do puts them back in a position of complying to do what is right, the rule

that should be imposed in reality. In some cases, even though personnel administer procedures in an organized manner, if they wear inappropriate attire in the course of their service, they become non-compliant by not following the proper dress code. This could distract examinees, which may destroy how authority is symbolized in a licensure examination. Non-compliance to rules sows disorder, which makes compliance an essential factor in attaining social order.

Failures of communication are part of the reality of administering licensure examinations. It serves as a challenge to personnel in ensuring that rules are adhered to in the future and miscommunications are addressed. Another challenge lies in the intent of examinees to cheat, to gain undue advantage in the examination. These factors challenge compliance to rules; these are communication problems that should be solved through communication itself. While violations of examination procedures or irregular incidents are treated as alienation from complying to rules, these could build rich experience among personnel in dealing with unique situations of conflict. Cooperation remains a strong force that holds order together when failure of communication takes place.

Complying with rules is a collective effort. When someone has a different interpretation of rules, this creates potential issues or misalignment of orientation to prescribed rules. It takes socialization to solicit opinions or views in how they understand rules as they are. Reaching out to re-create alignment of rules between exam supervisor and subordinate is one way of ensuring order in rules. It is through good communication where smooth, clean, and reliable licensure examinations are secured. Reporting issues to supervisors or to the concerned regulatory body is a culture of compliance and helps eradicate conflict.

Rule Preservation

In administering a licensure examination, inconsistency is a conflict. Where order in an exam is threatened, credibility and reliability are also in danger. This makes communication even more important as in preserving the rules that are in place to ensure social order. The act of giving reminders to subordinates serves as a measure of reinforcement to impose rules that should be imposed. Concurrent with the practice of roaming around is the act of reminding people that authority demands their full attention, focus, and dedication in whatever they are assigned to do. Through being distracted, personnel undermine the potential of examinees to engage in cheating or to violate the rules that are being enforced. This necessitates preserving rules in an examination, so that the results of the examination cannot be contested. The reputation of the governing body administering the licensure examination is always at stake. This would demand being accountable to preserving rules as they should be to people who exercise authority to enforce them.

Preserving the rules of the examination is an act of promoting neutrality within the testing site. It is strictly important to remove items in the site which could give undue advantage to any examinee persistent in passing the examinations the easy way. Worse, possessing prohibited materials such as codigos or cheat sheets in an examination would tarnish the measurement of the examinee's competence, knowledge, and preparedness to practice in his/her chosen field. It is the duty of the assigned room watcher and examination supervisor to prevent it from happening. Impersonation, for instance, is a fraudulent practice that is being prevented in licensure examinations, since it is the assumption of a false identity to provide answers to questions intended for another person. Impersonators are unauthorized people in the first place. They are a source of rule misalignment, which endangers

the credibility of examination results. Removing prohibited materials is an act of preserving integrity, and consequently, order.

To preserve the essence of rules in a rule system, consistency is the key. This means that accountable persons should have a support system that keeps them aligned with their duties and responsibilities, ensuring that they meet the requirements of the rules prescribed. Since licensure examinations are time-bounded, it is a practice for supply officers or supply aides to render support to their supervisors to expedite activities such as the submission of used examination materials and transporting them to the Office that administered the examination. Observing examination schedules is a means of preserving the rules. This makes it essential to provide instructions as a ritual of social interaction. When understanding becomes evident in interaction, social order is ensured.

Rule Authority

Any person who has the right to rule must make it evident that he/she deserves to do so. It is through the display of material proof of authority such as a badge by which authority is shown and demonstrated in the licensure examination. It also takes into account the observance of wearing proper dress code. It is a means of demanding respect, compliance, and alignment to the objectives of rule implementation. Badges serve as symbols of identity. Aside from badges, security officers wearing their uniforms resemble authority. The mere sight of authority is a communicative ritual, symbolizing the need to obey or to follow rules.

Recognizing authority is an act of cooperation. When issues arise in a licensure examination, arising from the limitation of knowledge and even of judgment, authority steps in to provide corrective measures and ensure that the examination rules are followed nonetheless. A rule cannot stand by itself without a

figure of authority that enforces it. This establishes the essence of authority in a rule regime. It is what drives the rule regime to exist, since authority is where a rule emanates.

In any rule regime, exercising authority is ensuring accountability. It designates people the responsibility to perform their respective functions in a licensure examination. But ensuring accountability also needs to be recorded and stored as information. It is also a means of preserving truth and compliance in the regime of ruling over people and structures. Before actions are performed, authority must be given to people who have the qualifications to do them. This ensures the observance of legality and legitimacy in exercising the right to rule in licensure examinations.

Synthesis of Rule Regime Reproduction

Using the lens of the Socio-Cultural Tradition of Communication Theory as proposed by Craig (1999), this Study has endeavored to establish the communicative practices of assigned personnel in licensure examinations, and how these communicative practices reproduce rule regime to accomplish the orderly conduct and administration of licensure examinations. The thematic analysis of codes that surfaced from the narratives of the participants in this Study facilitated the identification of a philosophical worldview on licensure examination administration as constructed by the assigned personnel. Considering that the assigned examination personnel utilize institutional knowledge of relationships, roles, and procedures to produce actions and interactions, this organized knowledge serves as the basis for their rational decision-making, a stable context of what administering licensure examinations means to them. Examination personnel are able to define, to interpret, to analyze situations, to make sound judgments, and to respond to situational

demands, all participating in the lived world of the licensure examination administration. The ethnomethodological nature of this Study also enabled the discovery of how examination personnel do what they do, through exploring the methods that they use, to produce communicative interactions that reflect social order in the licensure examination setting. These communicative interactions were examined in this Study for us to produce a contextual explanation of rule regime as enacted within the administration of licensure examinations. This rule regime is seen through the communication of the people interacting within the testing site, in the interpersonal activities that assigned personnel perform based on their principles, values, roles, and relationships. These interactions give form and identity to the regulatory body as the legitimate institution implementing such rule regime in licensure examinations.

In response to the second research question, this Study proposes that the communicative practices of personnel reproduced five (5) dimensions of rule regime in the licensure examination, to wit:

1. Roaming around, resolving issues, and retaining professional composure align knowledge and actions with the rules.
2. Reviewing exam statistics, re-checking documents, and securing retrieval procedures of examination paraphernalia are performed to ensure that rules are implemented.
3. Reprimanding, reporting of violations, and reporting of issues are done when rules are not complied.
4. Reminding procedures to prevent cheating, removing prohibited materials or items in the examination room, and rendering support to ensure consistency are meant to preserve the integrity of the examination process.

5. Finally, by putting in place respective badges, referring issues to higher authority, and recording of accountable persons, the established authority is recognized.

Chapter VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study sought to understand the communicative practices of assigned personnel in licensure examinations and how these communicative practices reproduced rule regime in the context of the licensure examination. This attempts to contribute an understanding of the act of administering a licensure examination and its rule regime structure in the field of communication, as constituted by examination personnel involved in it. Using ethnomethodology within the lens of the Socio-Cultural Tradition which theorizes communication as the reproduction of social order (Craig, 1999), I obtained and analyzed narratives from the lived experiences of eight (8) participants, each occupying respective licensure examination roles (n=1), such as Exam Coordinator, Building Supervisor, Floor Supervisor, Room Watcher, Attendance Supervisor, Supply Officer, Supply Aide, and Security Officer. These participants were selected from the pool of examination volunteers with rich experiences, as maintained in the regulatory body where I am employed. The data were collected using Key Informant Interview (KII) as guided by a semi-structured interview questionnaire to elicit semi-formal to informal responses. The data collected were initially subjected to Grounded Theory Method (GTM) to assign open codes or initial sub-themes from narratives that describe activities, procedures, or interactions constitutive of the participants' communicative practices. The coded narratives were further subjected to thematic analysis as categorized in order to surface main themes that symbolize how rule regime is reproduced in the licensure examination setting.

Along with the narratives, various illustrations were also presented to provide samples of the forms and labels used by examination personnel in the conduct of licensure examinations, such as but not limited to the Room Watcher's Report, Floor Supervisor's Report, Building Supervisor's Report, Delivery Receipts, List of Absentees, Report on Violation of Examinees, and Attendance Record sheets to establish and document information that guide them in implementing rules and examination procedures in the testing site. Core to their communicative practices are their individual principles, values, norms, and perceptions of judgment that are collectively displayed in their social interactions as persons of authority implementing rule systems in the licensure examination.

The findings of this Study indicated fifteen (15) communicative practices of licensure examination personnel, namely roaming around, resolving issues, retaining professional composure, reviewing exam statistics, re-checking documents, securing retrieval procedures, reprimanding people, reporting incidents and violations, reporting issues, reminding procedures to prevent cheating, removing prohibited materials or items in the examination room, rendering support to ensure consistency, the wearing of respective badges, referring issues to higher authority, and ensuring the record of accountable persons. Specifically, assigned examination personnel report to the testing site, wear their badges to display their authority, determine their area of responsibility, inspect and modify the examination area as needed, interact with examinees for their assigned seating arrangement, distribute identification and answer sheets as well as test questionnaires for each subject, account for examination statistics, write information in their respective forms or reports, submit these reports to their supervisor, and account for used test questionnaires and ID/answer sheets for submission to the regulatory body. By the end of the entire

duration of the examination, all assigned personnel receive their examination allowances as distributed by the Attendance Supervisor, in compensation for their service. During the examination, assigned examination personnel engage in vigilant surveillance to preserve examination integrity from acts such as cheating, the use of prohibited materials or devices, and other untoward incidents.

In the thematic analysis of the participants' narratives describing their communicative practices, five (5) main themes surfaced describing the dimensions of rule regime reproduction: rule alignment, rule implementation, rule compliance, rule preservation, and rule authority. Roaming around, resolving issues, and retaining professional composure align knowledge and actions with the rules. Reviewing exam statistics, re-checking documents, and securing retrieval procedures of examination paraphernalia are performed to ensure that rules are implemented. Reprimanding, reporting of violations, and reporting of failures are done when rules are not complied. Reminding procedures to prevent cheating, removing prohibited materials or items in the examination room, and rendering support to ensure consistency are meant to preserve the integrity of the examination process. Finally, by putting in place respective badges, referring issues to higher authority, and recording of accountable persons, the established authority is recognized.

Conclusion

Examination personnel's communicative practices reproduce rule systems in an institution. Their rituals of communication within social interactions define how they reproduce alignment of knowledge and information in ensuring rule compliance and preservation of authority. As social interactions take place, meanings of what they say or do are created. These meanings reproduce the rule regime.

Rule regime as a structure of social order is a reproduction of people's communicative acts. These acts shape, maintain, and even transform reality. But reality cannot be shaped, maintained, or transformed without being in it. People in alignment with the examination rules, performing reviews and documentary re-checks that ensure proper rule implementation, reprimanding and reporting when rule compliance is not achieved, preserving examination integrity, and recognizing established authority; these factors shape the rule regime of a credible and reliable licensure examination. These drive the achievement of goals and objectives in any institution with a rule system for administering licensure examination.

People have superiors to obey, goals to achieve, and interests to protect. Engaging in communication obeying superiors, achieving goals, and protecting interests is rule regime in action. There are rules that serve to satisfy institutional needs, but more importantly, people's needs. These rules make sense when people align in information and knowledge, and communicate to enact them. Implementing, complying to, and preserving rules reproduce order; and recognizing rule authority produces rule legitimacy.

Implications

This Study revealed that communicative practices in a licensure examination such as roaming around, reporting incidents, reprimanding, reminding subordinates, and reviewing documents, among others, are means of reproduction of an authoritative rule system. These communicative practices have been embraced by regulatory bodies granting licenses to passers of licensure examinations. This Study serves to recognize a contextual understanding of their lived world. The rule regime established by their actual official functions is seen in licensure examinations: alignment of rules, implementing them, enforcing compliance to rules, preserving

rule integrity, and exercising rule authority. By recognizing these forces that drive the accomplishment of an anomaly-free, credible licensure examination, further study on rule regime would be warranted, as regulatory bodies are continuously shaped (and re-shaped) as an organization. Policies on examination rules, procedures, personnel hierarchy, and interaction patterns could still change in response to institutional developments. Responding to institutional change may mean change in the rule regime structure being reproduced, which may be explained by a study on how rule regime is maintained under institutional developments.

This Study revealed communicative acts that aim to prevent cheating and to preserve examination integrity. But beyond these acts, there still exists a need to establish knowledge on the spatial dimension of rule regime in a licensure examination, on what the testing site and examination rooms look like, and what room watchers or examination supervisors do when they detect acts of cheating, bribery, or other forms of violation. These muted and marginalized aspects are not within the nature of this Study, which gives an opportunity for future researchers to explore the reality and knowledge that explain them using other lenses of communication. Exploring how rule regime is reproduced within a compromised testing environment could help discover communicative practices of examination personnel under circumstances of order resistance.

Recommendations

This Study reported findings establishing the communicative practices of examination personnel and the reproduction of rule regime within such context. In recognition of the need for further theorizing and research, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

Theoretical

Future studies on licensure examinations may use other traditions of communication theory as lens for theorizing communication. For instance, the use of the Socio-Cultural Tradition could explore the reproduction of rule regime in a computer-based licensure examination; the use of the Phenomenological Tradition could discover the essence of being an examination invigilator or a volunteer in licensure examinations by exploring their lived experiences and their views on participating in examination administration; the use of the Semiotic Tradition could help focus on discovering how examination forms or reports mediate the communication between room watchers and examination supervisors; the use of the Critical Tradition could explore actual experiences of personnel in situations where examination rules have been violated through cheating, codigos, and other practices; the use of the Rhetorical Tradition could explore the room watchers' art of giving instructions to licensure examinees; the use of the Cybernetic Tradition could discover how information provided by room watchers or examination supervisors are processed by the licensure examinees under existing room lay-outs or setting of the test environment; and the use of the Socio-Psychological Tradition could help determine the effects of the spatial dimension of the licensure examination on rule regime reproduction.

Methodological

A Feminist study may be explored to recognize the role of women in the licensure examination administration, as majority of the volunteers in the pool maintained by the participants are females ranging from the age of 20 to 65 years old. In addition, a study using Ethnography could explore the culture, or the everyday life, of room watchers and supervisors in licensure examinations.

Practical

The findings of the Study suggest regulatory bodies to ensure that assigned personnel in licensure examinations are well-oriented with the prescribed examination rules and procedures before the actual licensure examination schedule. The conduct of briefing orientation sessions and the distribution of manuals for each personnel could help keep them guided and aware of the appropriate steps to take as rule implementers during examination proper.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adams, T. (2016). Professional Self-Regulation and the Public Interest in Canada. In *Professions & Professionalism*, Vol. 6, No. 2, June 2006.
- Al Ghafri, M., Audeh, Y., & Al-Gadallah, M. (2019). Teaching to Test or Communicate. In *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, Vol. 10, No. 2 (June 2019), pp. 225-241.
- Albina, A.C., Balasabas, J.Y., Laquinon, B.J.I., Pampilo, M.H., & Caballero, L.J. (2022). Factors and challenges influencing the criminologist licensure examination performance through the non-passers' lens. In *European Journal of Educational Research*, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 365-380.
- Amanonce, J. & Maramag, A. (2020). Licensure examination performance and academic achievement of teacher education graduates. In *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, Vol. 9, No. 3 (September 2020), pp. 510-516.
- Bach, T., Jugl, M., Kohler, D. & Wegrich, K. (2022). Regulatory agencies, reputational threats, and communicative responses. In *Regulation & Governance*, Vol. 16, pp. 1042-1057.
- Balash, D. et al. (2021). Examining the Examiners: Students' Privacy and Security Perceptions of Online Proctoring Services. In *USENIX Symposium on Usable Privacy and Security (SOUPS)*, August 8-10, 2021, Virtual Conference.
- Black, K. (2010). *Business Statistics: Contemporary Decision Making*. 6th edition. John Wiley & Sons.
- Burns, T. & Carson, M. (2000). Actors, Paradigms, and Institutional Dynamics: The Theory of Social Rule Systems Applied to Radical Reforms. In Rogers Hollingsworth K.H. Muller, E.J. Hollingsworth (eds.) *Advancing Socio-Economics: An Institutional Perspective*, Rowman and Littlefield, Oxford, 2002.
- Burns, T. & Carson, M. (2003). Social Order and Disorder: Institutions, Policy Paradigms, and Discourses – An Interdisciplinary Approach. In P. Chilton & R. Wodak (eds.), *A New Agenda in Critical Discourse Analysis: Theory and Interdisciplinarity*, John Benjamins Publishing Co., Amsterdam/Philadelphia.
- Buss, W. G. & Novick, M. R. (1980). The detection of cheating on standardized tests: Statistical and legal analysis. In *The Journal of Law and Education*, Vol. 9, No. 9, pp. 1-64.

- Carbaugh, D. (1996). *Situating selves: The communication of social identities in American scenes*. Albany, NY: SUNY Press.
- Carey, J.W. (1989). *Communication as culture: Essays on media and society*. Winchester, MA: Unwin Hyman.
- Carpenter, D.P. (2010). *Reputation and Power: Organizational Image and Pharmaceutical Regulation at the FDA*. Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- Carpenter, D.P. & Krause, G.A. (2012). Reputation and Public Administration. In *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 72, No. 1, pp. 26-32. Wiley. JSTOR.org.
- Ceva, E. (2022). Institutional rules, roles, and the dynamics of public power. In *Jurisprudence 2022*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp. 443-448.
- Childs, R. & Umezawa, L. (2009). When the Teacher is the Test Proctor. In *Canadian Journal of Education*, Vol. 32, No. 3, pp. 618-651.
- Christensen, T. (2019). *Reputation Management in Public Agencies – The Relevance of Time, Sector, Audience, and Tasks*. University of Oslo: Norway.
- Clayman, S.E. (2001). Ethnomethodology: General. In N.J. Smelser & P.B. Baltes (eds.), *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, pp. 4865-4870. Oxford: Pergamon.
- Council on Licensure, Enforcement, and Regulation (CLEAR), 2004. <http://www.clearhq.org/mission>.
- Craig, R. (1999). Communication Theory as a Field. In *Communication Theory*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp. 119-161.
- Craig, R. (2016). Traditions of Communication Theory. In K.B. Jensen, E.W. Rothenbuhler, J.D. Pooley, and R.T. Craig (eds.), *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Creswell, J. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. 2nd edition, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- De Leon, J. (2016). Academic and licensure examination performances of BSN graduates: Bases for curriculum enhancement. In *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, Vol. 3, No. 4 (June 2016), pp. 64-72.
- Deetz, S. (2001). Conceptual Foundations. In L. Putnam & F. Jablin (eds.), *The New Handbook of Organizational Communication: Advances in Theory, Research, and Methods*. Sage Foundations, Inc.: pp. 3-46.

- Elias, N. (1970). *What is sociology?* Hutchinson, London.
- Ettien, A. (2018). A Study of Proctors' Involvement in National Examination Cheating: the Case of "College Prive MBF d'Abobo" Exam Center. In *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 22-27.
- Fiscal, R. & Roman, A. (2021). Pre-licensure examination as predictor of licensure examination for teachers result. In *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, Vol. 11, No. 1 (March 2022), pp. 136-142.
- Fulton, C.L. (2010). Plausibility. In A.J. Mills, G. Durepos, & E. Wiebe (eds.), *Encyclopedia of case study research*, Sage, pp. 682-684.
- Garfinkel, H. (1967). *Studies in Ethnomethodology*. Prentice Hall, Inc., New Jersey.
- Guralnik, D. B. (Ed.) (1976) *Webster's new world dictionary of the American language*. Cleveland: William Collins & World Publishing.
- Hartman, A. G. (1986). *Detecting Cheating on Multiple-Choice Examinations (Test Irregularities, Test Security)*. Tulane University, Louisiana.
- Hybels, S. & Weaver, R.L. (2001). *Communicating effectively*. New York, McGraw Hill.
- Irira, E.M. (2014). *Effective Management of Examinations as a Way of Achieving Quality Assurance: A Case of the Institute of Adult Education (IAE)*. Unpublished PhD Dissertation. Open University of Tanzania.
- Jwan, J.O. & Ong'ondo, C.O. (2011). *Qualitative Research: An Introduction to Principles and Techniques*. Eldoret: Moi University Press.
- Kane, M. (2005). The Role of Licensure Tests. In *The Bar Examiner*, Vol. 74 (February 2005), pp. 27-38.
- Kleiner, M. & Krueger, A. (2011). Analyzing the Extent and Influence of Occupational Licensing on the Labor Market. In *IZA Discussion Paper No. 5505*, Institute for the Study of Labor, Bonn, Germany, February 2011.
- Kurawa, S. (2012). Social Order in Sociology: Its Reality and Elusiveness. In *Sociology Mind*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 34-40.
- Laurier, E. & S. Bodden. (2020). Ethnomethodology / Ethnomethodological Geography. In A. Kobayashi (ed.), *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography*, 2nd ed. Elsevier, pp. 329-334.
- Liddicoat, A.J. (2023). Ethnomethodology. In J. Stanlaw (ed.), *The International Encyclopedia of Linguistic Anthropology*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118786093.iela0120/>

- Lindlof, T. & Taylor, B. (2019). *Qualitative Communication Research Methods*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.
- Lynch, M. (2001). Science and Technology Studies: Ethnomethodology. In N.J Smelser & P.B. Baltes (eds.), *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, pp. 13644-13647. Oxford: Pergamon.
- Lyons, R. D. (1984). Cheating on exams for doctors causes alarm. In *The New York Times*, April 3, 1984 issue, pp. 19 & 22.
- Magut, Z. (2016). Socio-cultural Tradition: From Theory to Research. In *Journal of Language, Technology, & Entrepreneurship of Africa*, Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 1-11.
- Minott, M. (2018). External Examination Investigators' (EIs) Beliefs and Inference About Activities They Consider Important: Implication for Examination Policy. In *Journal of Perspectives in Applied Academic Practice*, Vol. 6, No. 1 (April 2018), pp. 47-54.
- Mumby, D. (1997). Modernism, Postmodernism, and Communication Studies: A Rereading of an Ongoing Debate. In *Communication Theory*, Vol. 7, No. 1 (February 1997), pp. 1-28.
- Nickerson, C. (2023). *Using Ethnomethodology To Understand Social Order*. Simply Psychology. Accessed at <https://www.simplypsychology.org/what-is-ethnomethodology.html>
- Nitu, N. (2021). Importance of Communication in Public Administration. In *Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques*, No. 69, pp. 134-145. University of Craiova, Romania.
- Olszewski, B., Macey, D. & Lindstrom, L. (2006). The Practical Work of Coding: An Ethnomethodological Inquiry. In *Human Studies*, 29, pp. 363-380.
- Parsons, T. (1951). An outline of the social system. In T. Parsons, E.A. Shils, K.D. Naegele, & J.R. Petts (eds.), *Theories of Society*, pp. 30-79.
- Reyes, D. (2021, March 29). *What We Know About the May 2019 Civil Engineering Board Exam Scandal*. Engineer Dee's Blog. <https://engineerdeedee.com/may-2019-board-exam-scandal/>
- Rothenbuhler, E. (1993). Argument for a Durkheimian Theory of the communicative. In *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 43, No. 3, pp. 158-163.

- Rukundo, A. & Magambo, J. (2010). Effective Test Administration in Schools: Principals & Good Practices for Test Administrators in Uganda. In *African Journal of Teacher Education*, Vol. 1, No. 1 (October 2010), pp. 166-173.
- Saani, A. & Tawiah, M. A. (2017). Effect of Training and Development on Examination Invigilators' Work Performance at University of Cape Coast, Ghana. In *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, Vol. 7, No. 9, pp. 258-267.
- Sadiq, A. & Saeed, M. (2017). An Exploratory Study on Problems Faced by Students during Board Examination. In *Bulletin of Education and Research*, Vol. 39, No. 1 (April 2017), pp. 101-115.
- Saludadez, J. (2021). Notes from Unit III. Studying/Researching Organizational Communication. In *Comm 340: Organizational Communication*. UPOU MyPortal.
- Saludadez, J. (2021). Notes from Unit III. Evaluating Communication Research. In *Comm 390: Communication Research Paradigms*. UPOU MyPortal.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2012). *Research Methods for Business Students*, 6th edition. Pearson Education Limited.
- Savin-Baden, M. & Major, C.H. (2010). Qualitative Research Synthesis: The scholarship of integration in practice. In *New Approaches to Qualitative Research: Wisdom & Uncertainty*. New York, NY: Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Schmitt, K. (1995). What is Licensure. In James C. Empara (ed.), *Licensure Testing: Purposes, Procedures, and Practices*. Lincoln, NE: Buros Center for Testing.
- Schorr, A. (1985). Professional Practice as Policy. In *Social Service Review*, Vol. 59, No. 2 (June 1985), pp. 178-196.
- Sewell, W. (1992). A Theory of Structure: Duality, Agency, and Transformation. In *American Journal of Sociology*, 98, pp. 1-29.
- Shehzad, M. & Dogar, A.H. (2020). A Study on Problems and Malpractices Emerge during Examination of Grade 5 and Grade 8 Students in Punjab, Pakistan. In *Pakistan Journal of Education*, Vol. 37, No. 1, pp. 129-148.
- Shimberg, B., & Roederer, D. (1994). *Questions a legislator should ask*. Lexington, KY: The Council of State Governments.

- Shipunova, O. & Kuznetsov, D. (2015). Communication and the Natural Social Order. In *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol. 6, No. 3, S3. MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy.
- Siegel, S. (1985). 2 school officials accused of giving test answers to kids. In *The Times Picayune/The States-Item*, May 2, 1985, pp A-25-26.
- Snyman, J. (1993). Fakability of Paper and Pencil Honesty Tests. In *Applied H.R.M. Research*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 49-68.
- Streeck, W. & Schmitter, P. (1985). Community, market, state – and associations? The prospective contribution of interest governance to social order. In W. Streeck & P. Schmitter (Eds.) *Private interest government: Beyond market and state*, pp. 1-19, London: Sage.
- Strycker, R. (1994). Rules, Resources, and Legitimacy Processes: Some Implications for Social Conflict, Order, and Change. In *American Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 99, No. 4, pp. 847-910.
- Tannenberg, M., Bernhard, M., Gerschewski, J., Luhrmann, A., & van Soest, C. (2020). Claiming the right to rule: regime legitimation strategies from 1900 to 2019. *European Political Science Review*, (2021), Vol. 13, pp. 77-94.
- Ten Have, P. (2016). Ethnomethodology. In *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy*, pp. 1-12.
- Tongco, M.D. (2007). Purposive Sampling as a Tool for Informant Selection. In *Ethnobotany Research and Applications*, 5, pp. 147-158.
- Waeraas, A. & Maor, M. (2015). Understanding Organizational Reputation in a Public Sector Context. In *Organizational Reputation in the Public Sector*, Routledge, NY.
- West, R. & Turner, L. (eds). (2010). Organizational Information Theory. In West & Turner (eds.), *Introducing Communication Theory: Analysis and Application*, 4th edition, pp. 290-307. McGraw-Hill: NY.
- Williams, J. (2001). Phenomenology in Sociology. In N.J. Smelser & P.B. Baltes (eds.), *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, pp. 11361-11363. Oxford: Pergamon.

APPENDIX A

Letter-Request to the Regional Director of the Study Site

5 July 2023

THE REGIONAL DIRECTOR

Dear Sir:

I write to seek the consent of your good Office for the conduct of a Key Informant Interview (KII) of personnel from the Examination Section of the Licensure & Registration Division of your Regional Office, as well as examination volunteers outside your Agency. This KII is in view of gathering invaluable data for my dissertation with a working title "*Rule Regime in the Communicative Practices of Personnel in Licensure Examinations: An Ethnomethodological Study.*"

The study that I am currently working on intends to discover the communicative practices of the involved personnel in your Agency's licensure examinations and how the concept of the "rule regime" structure is manifested in the context of our licensure examinations. This study intends to give "voice" to the room watchers, floor supervisors, building supervisors, exam coordinators, and other essential examination staff who had been performing examination procedures in the licensure examinations, waiting to be "heard" in the academic realm.

The interview with the proposed participants would take place within the month of July 2023. The questions in the interview would focus on eliciting the participants' rich experience in undertaking communicative acts as they implement examination procedures in their own capacity. The participants would be purposively selected in the pool of examination personnel maintained in the database of the Examination Section.

Rest assured that the consent of the participants will likewise be sought; their real names will be concealed as key informants of my Study; and that the data to be generated in the KII will be used solely for academic purposes, towards the development of knowledge about licensure examination administration in the field of communication.

I hope for a favorable response anent this request. Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

YOURGIN O. MONTEJO
Researcher

Conforme:

APPENDIX B

Letter to the Participants

10 July 2023

Dear Madame/Sir:

I am Yourgin Oclares Montejo, a Doctor of Communication (DComm) student under the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies (FICS) of the UP Open University, currently taking up Comm 400 (Doctoral Dissertation).

In partial fulfillment of the said course, I am currently working on a dissertation with a tentative title "*Rule Regime in the Communicative Practices of Personnel in Licensure Examinations: An Ethnomethodological Study.*" This Study aims to discover the communicative practices of examination personnel like you, as well as to establish the concept of "rule regime" as manifested in the setting of the licensure examinations conducted by the Office.

Personally, I believe that your experiences as a volunteer personnel in the Office's licensure examinations are rich enough to generate invaluable data towards achieving the objectives of my Study.

In this connection, I write to seek your consent for a Key Informant Interview (KII) within the month of July 2023. The KII would focus on eliciting your rich experience in undertaking communicative acts as you undertake and implement examination procedures in your capacity as examination personnel.

Rest assured that your identity shall remain confidential in my Study, and that the data to be generated in the KII will be used solely for academic purposes, towards the development of knowledge about licensure examination administration in the field of communication.

I hope to obtain your full consent for the KII. Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

YOURGIN O. MONTEJO
Researcher

Conforme:

APPENDIX C

Guide Questionnaire for the Key Informant Interview (KII)

1. How do you understand the conduct of licensure examinations? How do you define it?
2. Based on your experience as Exam Coordinator / Building Supervisor / Attendance Supervisor / Floor Supervisor / Supply Officer / Supply Aide / Room Watcher / Security Officer, what is your primary responsibility in the conduct of licensure examinations?
3. What sequence of procedures do you implement in your capacity during licensure examinations?
4. What resources (or forms) do you need, if any, and how do you utilize them to perform your duties and responsibilities?
5. In fulfilling your duties and responsibilities, how do you communicate and interact with your co-personnel as well as the examinees in administering licensure examinations?
6. What body gestures do you make for interaction in your role in the licensure examinations?
7. What jargons do you use for interaction in your role in the licensure examinations?
8. What attire do you use during licensure examinations?
9. What communicative behaviors do you exhibit when facing problems or conflicts during the licensure examinations?
10. In your capacity, what activities do you do to preserve the integrity of the licensure examinations?
11. How do you maintain cooperation with your co-personnel in the conduct of licensure examinations?